

Université Grenoble Alpes

Ecole doctorale Sciences de la Terre, de l'Environnement et des Planètes

Habilitation à Diriger des Recherches (HDR)

Les plateformes de glace d'Antarctique et leurs liens avec le système climatique

Antarctic ice shelves and their links with the climate system

Nicolas C. Jourdain

nicolas.jourdain@univ-grenoble-alpes.fr

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Jury:

Masa Kageyama	Rapporteuse	LSCE/IPSL, CNRS-CEA-UVSQ, Gif sur Yvette, France
Stephen Rintoul	Rapporteur	CSIRO, Hobart, Tasmania, Australia
Eric Steig	Rapporteur	University of Washington, Seattle, United States of America
Helene Hewitt	Examinatrice	Met Office Hadley Centre, Exeter, United Kingdom
Frank Pattyn	Examineur	Université Libre de Bruxelles, Belgique
Ghislain Picard	Examineur	Université Grenoble Alpes, France

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FOREWORD

The *Habilitation à Diriger des Recherches* (HDR) is the highest university degree in France, and it is usually required to be the official main supervisor of a PhD student or to become professor. The reviewers of this manuscript are expected to evaluate my scientific level, the originality of my approaches, my ability to develop a broad research and technological strategy, and my ability to mentor young researchers, including Master's and PhD students.

I did my PhD on the coupling of ocean, sea-ice and atmosphere models, with the aim of studying mesoscale feedbacks. Since then, I have often switched between oceanography and atmospheric sciences, and part of my current work is related to glaciology. I believe that my strongest expertise today is in physical oceanography.

My postdoctoral years have been a journey of initiation in the South Pacific Ocean, from New Caledonia to Australia's east coast, with a French period in between. I really loved these years, both personally and scientifically. I believe that I produced some original contributions, but the general scientific strategy was then elaborated by my mentors, so here I only give a very short overview of my postdoctoral work (1st Part).

I started working on the 2nd part of this manuscript in the summer 2022 when I found a bit of time to try summarising how the current knowledge on Antarctic ice shelves emerged. As I did not find much about this in the recent publications, I turned to the old books reporting polar exploration and sometimes scientific observations. I then followed the arrival of seismic echo sounding, satellite observations and numerical models through the scientific publications. All that was so fascinating that it delayed a bit the release of this manuscript.

The 3rd part is a more classical description of my own research. To be clear, I don't do research alone, my work strongly relies on model development teams, on groups sharing field and satellite data, on discussions in international workshops and projects, and on fruitful and pleasant collaborations at IGE. In particular have been very lucky to work with talented PhD students, postdocs and engineers since I got my CNRS position.

In the last part of this manuscript, I provide indications for future possible research in the continuity of my present work.

CURRICULUM VITAE

Studies

Univ. Joseph Fourier, Grenoble, France	Earth & Universe	PhD	2008
Univ. Pierre & Marie Curie, Paris, France	Ocean & Atmosphere	Master's degree	2004
ENS/Paris-6 & 11, Montrouge, France	Physics & Chemistry	Agrégation	2003
Univ. Paris-Sud, Orsay, France	Physics	Honour's degree	2002

Employment

Researcher	CNRS-IGE	Grenoble	France	2013-present
Postdoc	CCRC-UNSW	Sydney	Australia	2011-2013
Self-employed	-	Maubeuge	France	2011
Postdoc	CNRS-LEGI	Grenoble	France	2009-2011
Postdoc	IRD	Nouméa	New Caledonia	2008-2009
Lecturer	Univ. J. Fourier	Grenoble	France	2005-2007

Community activities

Evaluation of Research:

- Editor of The Cryosphere: 22 papers published since 2021 under my editorship.
- Peer-Review of 5 to 12 papers per year in various international journals.
- Member of the evaluation panel of a large NSF research program.
- Regular evaluations of projects in France (ANR, LEFE) and abroad (Europe, UK, Belgium, Chile).
- Member of the evaluation committee for the national computing time requests since 2021 (GENCI).
- Examiner for 3 PhD theses in France and 2 PhD theses in Belgium (one as rapporteur).

Involvement in collaborative projects:

- **ISMIP** (Ice Sheet Model Intercomparison Project):
 - Member of the ocean focus group to establish the ISMIP6 forcing (Jourdain et al., 2020).
 - Coordinator of the ocean focus group for ISMIP7 (since the end of 2023).
- **MISOMIP** (Marine Ice Sheet Ocean Model Intercomparison Project):
 - Participant in the first phase (2016-2020).
 - Co-chair of the second phase since 2019 (De Rydt, Jourdain et al., 2024).
- **FRISP** (Forum for Research on Ice Shelf Processes):
 - Co-organiser of the annual meeting in 2018 in Aussois.
 - French representative on the steering committee since 2023.

Others:

- Member of the CLIMERI-France scientific steering committee (since 2023).
- Convenor of the 'Ice shelves and tidewater glaciers' session at EGU Assembly, Vienna (since 2019).
- Participation in 3 PhD advisory committees in France, 2 in Belgium and 1 in Korea.
- Member of the LGGE/IGE council (2016-2020).
- Code sharing: <https://github.com/nicojourdain>

Teaching

- 2024: Southern Ocean Summer School, 7-18 May 2024, Cargèse, Corsica, France.
- 2008: Teaching to students applying for the Secondary School Teaching Qualification (CAPES) in Nouméa, New Caledonia: physics & chemistry lectures (10h), practical work in mechanics (15h).
- 2006-2007: Examiner at the competitive entry exams to the French *Grandes Ecoles*, in Paris: "TIPE" (examination of scientific general knowledge and of skills in analysing scientific papers).
- 2005-2007: 3-year instructorship in the Physics Department in Grenoble University (France): mechanics lectures (170h) and practical glaciology (10h) for undergraduate students; oral preparation for students preparing the Secondary Teaching Qualification (CAPES, 24h).

Projects

Project coordination:

- [ANR-AIAI](#): Artificial Intelligence to improve the coupling between the Antarctic Ice sheet and the climate system (2023-2027, 567 k€) [Main coordinator].
- PEPR TRACCS – IMPRESION-ESM: Improving physical processes in ESMs (2023-2031 – 6M€) [co-lead with Romain Roehrig and Martin Vancoppenolle].
- UGA IRGA – DEEP MELT: Parameterising ocean-induced melt at the base of Antarctic ice shelves with deep emulators (2022-2023 – 47 k€) [Single coordinator].
- [Thomas Jefferson Fund](#) – Ice shelf-ocean interactions in Antarctica (2018-2020 – 10,000 USD).
- [ANR-TROIS AS](#): Towards a Regional Ocean Ice-Sheet Atmosphere modelling System (2015-2020, 296 k€). https://nicojourdain.github.io/projects_dir/trois_as/ [Single coordinator].
- Labex OSUG@2020 – [Tout le Monde se MAR](#) (2016-2018, 53 k€) [Single coordinator].
- [ARC DP](#): A regional coupled climate model for Australia (2018-2020, 327,000 AUD). [co-lead with Alex Sen Gupta et Daniel Argüeso]
- GENCI (national computing allocation): Coordination of the proposals for a few millions of CPU hours attributed every year from 2017 to 2024.

Coordination of Work Packages (WP) in European projects:

- Horizon Europe – WP2 in [OCEAN:ICE](#): Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica, Impacts on Climate and the Earth System (2022-2026, 8M€).
- H2020 – WPs 3,8,9 in [ESM2025](#): Earth System Models for the future (2021-2025, 11.3 M€).
- H2020 – WP4 in [PROTECT](#): Projecting sea level rise, from ice sheets to local implications (2020-2024, 10 M€).

Other significant contributions to projects:

- PEPR TRACCS – ISCLIM: Improving physical processes in ESMs (2023-2031 – 6M€).
- H2020 – [CRiceS](#): Climate Relevant interactions and feedbacks: the key role of sea ice and Snow in the polar and global climate system (2021-2025) [1 deliverable].
- H2020 – [TiPACCs](#): Tipping Points in Antarctic Climate Components (2019-2023) [data management plan; policy brief; 3 deliverables].
- [ANR-EIS](#): Elmer Ice Sheet (2020-2023).

Supervision

PhD students:

- Justine Caillet (2020-2024) is studying the past and future evolution of the Amundsen Sea and its glaciers using ocean and ice sheet modelling [agreement for 100% supervision with no HDR].
- Marion Donat-Magnin (2016-2019) worked on ice shelf melt projections for 2100 in the Amundsen region via ocean and atmospheric modelling [90% supervision; official supervision Hubert Gallée].
- Yue Li (2013-2018, at UNSW, Sydney) worked on modelling precipitation and air-sea interactions over the Maritime Continent [co-supervision with Alex Sen Gupta and Andrea Taschetto].

Postdocs:

- Antoine Nasser (2023-2024) is studying the representation of the ocean–ice–shelf interface using penalisation methods [ESM2025 project, co-supervised with Pierre Mathiot].
- Anna Olivé-Abello (2023-2025) is studying the Lagrangian representation of icebergs in an ocean model [OCEAN:ICE project, co-supervised with Pierre Mathiot].
- Christoph Kittel (2022-2024) is studying the role of the ocean-sea ice mesoscale on Tropical-Antarctic exchanges [CRiceS project].
- Cyrille Mosbeux (2022-2023) is developing high-resolution ice sheet configurations of the Amundsen sector for projections [TiPACCs and PROTECT; co-supervised with O. Gagliardini].
- Clara Burgard (2020-2023) worked on improving melt parameterisations for ice cap models, using physical and learning approaches [PROTECT project].
- Pierre Mathiot (2020-2023) worked on tipping points in the Southern Ocean and is developing the NEMO-Elmer/Ice coupled model [TiPACCs project].
- Lionel Favier (2017-2019) worked on the coupling between Elmer/Ice and NEMO in an idealised configuration [TROIS AS project].

Engineers:

- Pierre Mathiot (IR, 2023-2030) is working on the NEMO-Elmer/Ice coupling in TRACCS.
- Lucas Bastien (IR, 2023-2025) is working on the integration of Elmer/Ice in IPSL-CM (ESM2025).
- Nacho Merino (IR, 2017) worked on the NEMO-Elmer/Ice coupling for the TROIS AS project.
- Amine Drira (IE, 2016-2018) worked on the MAR website and on MAR simulations.

Master's students:

- Laurine Fiol (M2, 2024)
- Benjamin Bouissou (M2, 2022) [co-supervised with Clara Burgard]
- Alban Planchat (M2, 2020)
- Evgenia Valla (M2, 2018) [co-supervised with Martin Menegoz]
- Nicolas Mokus (M1, 2018)
- Svenya Chripko (M2, 2017)
- Marion Donat-Magnin (M2, 2016)
- Anna Vlug (M2, 2015)
- Pierre-Vincent Huot (M1, 2015)
- Yue Li (M2, 2012-2013) [co-supervised with Alex Sen Gupta]
- Anne Piron (M2, 2011) [co-supervised with Matthieu Lengaigne and Jérôme Vialard]

Scientific dissemination

Publications:

70 publications in international peer-reviewed journals (~3000 citations). See [full list](#).

Conferences and workshops:

Regular participation in EGU general assemblies, FRISP, ISMIP and MISOMIP workshops, and sporadically in other conferences. See [full list](#).

Sharing, management and publication of research data:

In my publications and those of the people I supervise, I share as much information as possible so that our results are as reproducible as possible. Sharing is generally done via Github and Zenodo. I'm also in charge of the Data Management Plan for the H2020 TiPACCs project. Increasingly, I'm also trying to make a selection of model outputs available to the community, as in these examples: [here](#), [here](#) and [here](#).

Field work

In 2013-2014, I worked for 2 months at Cap Prudhomme, near the Dumont d'Urville base in Adélie Land, Antarctica. We monitored the surface mass balance and atmospheric boundary layers properties, including blowing snow events.

Communication and Media

- I have contributed to about twenty press, radio and television interviews for national and regional media. See the [full list](#).
- I published 2 articles for the general public in *The Conversation - France* (see [here](#) and [there](#)), and I regularly update *Wikipedia* pages (mostly in French) on Antarctica and the Southern Ocean.
- I took part in a *policy brief* on Antarctic tipping points in Brussels in October 2023 (*On the need to consider ocean and ice sheets together*). See [the programme](#).

International visits of more than 2 weeks

- IRD Centre in Nouméa, New Caledonia, in 2012.
- University of New South Wales, Sydney, Australia, in 2013-2014.
- Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory, Columbia University, USA, in 2019.
- Department of Meteorology, Stockholm University, Sweden, in 2022 and 2023.
- Asian Water Research Centre, HCMC, Vietnam, in 2020 and 2022.

First part

Brief summary of postdoctoral activities

Tropical cyclones and climate variability in the Indo-Pacific region

*This part is dedicated to the inspiring mentors of my postdoctoral years:
Christophe Menkes, Mathieu Lengaigne, Jérôme Vialard, Gurvan Madec,
Patrick Marchesiello, Bernard Barnier, Alex Sen Gupta and Matthew England.*

Figure 1 – Mean precipitation over the Indo-Pacific region (mm/day, from the GPCP dataset over 1986-2015). The names of the main features presented in this part are indicated.

CHAPTER I

TROPICAL CYCLONES

The House of Mapuhi

The work presented in this chapter was initiated at the IRD centre of Nouméa, in 2008-2009, then finalized through remote collaborations in the ten following years. How did I end up studying tropical cyclones after a PhD on ocean–sea-ice–atmosphere interactions in Antarctica? I think they selected me for my skills in ocean–atmosphere regional modelling, and because my PhD thesis included a chapter on Antarctic mesocyclones, also called polar lows. And working on tropical cyclones in Nouméa was kind of appealing for me.

Tropical cyclones, also known as hurricanes or typhoons in their intense forms, are extremely powerful heat machines in which latent heat from ocean evaporation is partly converted to deep atmospheric convection and intense winds throughout the troposphere. Because of their destructiveness, predicting the cyclonic activity at seasonal or longer time scales remains a major challenge. This is why the first part of this postdoctoral work focused on the dynamics and genesis of tropical cyclones and their control by the large-scale climate dynamics and anthropogenic emissions.

The second part this postdoctoral work focused on the ocean response to tropical cyclones. The main motivation was to understand their “cold wake”, i.e., the sea surface cooling observed after the passage of tropical cyclones, which acts as a negative feedback mechanism for their intensity. A secondary motivation was to investigate the significance of a climatic warming of the ocean subsurface by tropical cyclones.

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The interannual variability in number of cyclogenesis can be partly explained by the general circulation. Several cyclogenesis indices based on a limited number of climate variables had therefore been defined to predict or explain cyclogenesis. We showed that none of them was able to fully explain the variability in cyclogenesis, especially in the South Pacific, where the large-scale is characterized by the SPCZ, the South Pacific Convergence Zone (Menkes et al. 2012). The north-south shifts of the SPCZ and its zonalization were shown to strongly control the interannual variability in number of cyclogenesis in the southeast Pacific (Vincent et al. 2011), but the control is weak in the southwest Pacific.

To understand the weak control of large-scale dynamics in the South Pacific, we ran the WRF atmospheric model (Weather Research and Forecast, Skamarock et al. 2005), with a large domain capturing the large-scale variability and a 2-way nested domain to represent tropical cyclones at higher resolution. Using a series of perturbed initial states and interannual simulations, we showed that a quarter of the variance in number of cyclogenesis events was stochastic, due to mesoscale dynamics. This explained the difficulty of predicting tropical cyclogenesis from large-scale indices (Jourdain et al., 2011).

In terms of future projections of cyclonic activity, the SPCZ was highly biased in the CMIP5 models and reliable regional projections required bias corrections (Dutheil et al., 2019). Using an emergent constraint method to correct the sea surface temperature, we found a significant reduction in future cyclogenesis in the South Pacific (-55%), while no significant change was found without any correction (Dutheil et al., 2020). This was explained by a stronger vertical wind shear in the corrected simulations, which is unfavourable to cyclogenesis.

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It was not trivial to study the ocean response to tropical cyclones because (i) the atmospheric reanalyses strongly underestimated their strength, and (ii) data assimilation in ocean reanalyses was only able to correct a tiny part of the missing sea surface response, due to overly weak cyclonic forcing (Jourdain et al., 2014).

Our first approach to study the ocean response to tropical cyclones was to correct a 30-year atmospheric reanalysis by prescribing analytical cyclonic winds based on a tropical cyclone database (Vincent et al., 2011a,b). For weak tropical cyclones, the sea surface cools due to stronger heat fluxes at the surface. For strong tropical cyclones, increased vertical mixing combined with increased upwelling explains most of the sea surface cooling, and is associated with sub-surface warming. We also found that the cyclone-induced cooling was strongly influenced by the background ocean stratification: the cold surface anomaly in the wake of a strong tropical cyclone ranged from 0.5 to 5°C depending on this background.

After these results, I built a theoretical framework to estimate the surface cooling inhibition by heavy rainfall under tropical cyclones based on observations (Jourdain et al., 2013). The largest impact was found in the Arabian Sea owing to the combination of strong rainfall and strong thermal stratification. By contrast, the Bay of Bengal displayed a smaller effect of rainfall on the cold wake because of the presence of a strong barrier layer. The overall effect of rainfall was overall quite weak (median of 7%), but not negligible as it reduced the cooling by more than 19% for 10% of the cases.

Another approach to study the ocean response to tropical cyclones was to force ocean simulations with the aforementioned WRF simulations and with the same simulations in which tropical cyclones were filtered out. We found that 60% of the heat injected at depth during the cyclonic season was released back to the atmosphere in the following winter, which modulates the climatic effect of tropical cyclones (Jullien et al., 2012).

Then, using a regional ocean–atmosphere coupled version of these models, we were able to estimate the influence of the numerous eddies found in the southwest Pacific (Jullien et al., 2014). Anticyclonic eddies have a deep mixed layer and act against cyclone-induced upwelling and mixing, thereby reducing the sea surface cooling by cyclones. In contrast, cyclonic eddies have a shallow mixed layer and promote stronger sea surface cooling through cyclone-induced upwelling.

While I was trying to develop an analytical formulation for the ocean response to tropical cyclones, I heard about Florent Gimbert’s PhD work on the observations of sea-ice inertial motions in the Arctic, and I proposed a very simple ocean–sea-ice model that helped understand these motions. It was used to provide evidence for a mechanical weakening of the Arctic sea ice from 1979–2001 to 2002–2008 based on observations (Gimbert et al., 2012a,b).

CHAPTER II

CLIMATE VARIABILITY IN THE INDO-PACIFIC REGION

Garrigarrang Nura

The work presented in this chapter was mostly conducted or initiated during my postdoctoral stay at the University of New South Wales in Sydney, from 2011 to 2014. It includes work on the large structures and modes of climate variability of the Indo-Pacific region: the South Pacific Convergence Zone (SPCZ), the El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO), the Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD), the Indo-Australian monsoon, and the East-Australian Current (**Fig. 1**).

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Precipitation on the South Pacific islands is largely related to the SPCZ variability. We found that during El Niño events, the entire SPCZ was shifted northward, and a southward shift occurred during La Niña events. In the strongest El Niño events (like 1982-83 and 1997-98), the SPCZ stopped being diagonal and extended zonally along the equator ([Vincent et al., 2011](#)). This contributed to show the need for a more complex characterisation of ENSO than a single index.

Ashok (2007) had already defined the *El Niño Modoki* (“a similar but different thing” in Japanese), which are ENSO events characterised by sea surface temperatures anomalies in the central Pacific, i.e., at the east end of the climatological warm pool. In contrast, the canonical ENSO events are characterized by sea surface temperatures anomalies in the eastern equatorial Pacific, in the region of the climatological equatorial cold tongue. We showed that the CMIP5 models were able to capture these two types of events with a realistic amplitude, despite biases in the spatial patterns and larger biases for the negative phases ([Taschetto et al., 2014](#)).

Before being hired at CNRS, I also started working on the predictability of ENSO. A prerequisite for an El Niño event is the accumulation of warm water in the western equatorial Pacific, held by the prevailing easterlies. Therefore, the warm water volume (volume of water above the 20°C isotherm in the equatorial Pacific) was used for predictions 9 months ahead of ENSO. Using the CMIP5 models, we brought further support for the mechanism suggested by Izumo et al. (2010), whereby the Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD) influences the following year’s ENSO ([Jourdain et al., 2016](#)). The connection is through an atmospheric bridge, with westerly wind anomalies in the western equatorial Pacific favouring the release of the accumulated warm water. Accounting for the IOD increases the skills in ENSO predictions 14 months ahead.

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The Indo-Australian monsoon consists of the Indian and South-East Asian summer monsoon that occurs from June to September, and the Australian and Maritime Continent monsoon that occurs in austral summer, from December to March. The Maritime Continent is in the “warm pool” region between the Indian and the Pacific Ocean and includes numerous islands

belonging to Indonesia, the Philippines, and Papua New Guinea, among others (Fig. 1). It was suggested that a relatively strong Indian monsoon is followed by a strong Australian monsoon half a year later and a relatively weak Indian monsoon in the subsequent year (and vice versa), which is sometimes referred to as the Tropospheric Biennial Oscillation (Meehl 1997; Li et al., 2012).

While the CMIP3 and CMIP5 models were shown to reproduce reasonably well the summer monsoon in India and Australia, as well as their mutual connections and teleconnections with ENSO, the Maritime Continent has been identified as one of the most poorly represented regions in climate models in numerous studies (e.g., Jourdain et al. 2013). Yue Li's PhD project was to use regional coupled ocean-atmosphere simulations at high resolution (NEMO-OASIS-WRF, Samson et al. 2014) to highlight mesoscale processes that would be missing from climate models because of their much lower resolution.

Going from resolutions typical of CMIP models to $1/12^\circ$, we found small differences in the diurnal rainfall propagation over the islands of the Maritime Continent, but the added value of high resolution was not striking (Li et al., 2017). Similarly, air-sea exchanges at high frequency were not found to significantly improve simulated rainfall (Li et al., 2020). It seems that the thermodynamical component of rainfall is relatively important in that region, with a lesser importance of the dynamical component (Argüeso et al., 2022), which may explain the lack of improvements at high resolution.

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The East-Australian Current (EAC) in the western South Pacific is Australia's strongest and most important boundary current, supporting temperate coastlines by transporting heat poleward. I collaborated with Chris Bull on this topic while he was doing his PhD in Sydney, and we set up a few ocean modelling experiments to better understand the EAC variability. We found that regional winds explain a large part of the variability of its transport and eddy shedding, with a significant stochastic part in this variability (Bull et al., 2017). The presence of the New Zealand submarine shelf is also crucial to the southern part of the EAC as it maintains a narrow, coherent current across the northern Tasman Sea (Bull et al., 2018).

We then used the NEMO-OASIS-WRF model driven by the CMIP5 multi-model mean anomalies to project the future EAC transport under the RCP8.5 scenario at an eddy-permitting resolution. These simulations show an increase of the EAC transport by 12 Sv in 2100, which warms the southern Tasman Sea by 4.5°C , i.e., 1°C warmer than the direct predictions by the relatively coarse CMIP5 models (Bull et al. 2020). This would have dramatic consequences for the marine ecosystems of the Tasman Sea.

Second part

Historical and scientific context

The discovery of ice shelves and of their links with the climate system

This part is dedicated to Gabriel García Márquez and his « Chronicle of a death foretold ».

Figure 2 – Map of Antarctica showing the main features discussed in this report. The bathymetry is in blue-yellow and the ice sheet surface elevation is in grey. The topography is from BedMachine-Antarctica-v2 (Morlighem et al., 2019) and the glacial drainage basins (pink) are from Rignot et al. (2019).

CHAPTER III

ICE BARRIERS, SHELVES AND TONGUES

La Barrière de la Langue

When James Clark Ross arrived in Antarctica, he probably didn't imagine that the gigantic ice barrier that had just dashed his dream of reaching the South Pole might be threatened with retreat a few centuries later.

After more than a year exploring the south seas, the Briton was dreaming of taking his fleet, *Erebus* and *Terror*, as far as the South Pole. But on 28th January 1841, as they were travelling south under full sail, a long white line on the horizon caught the crew's attention. It extended as far east as they could see. As they got closer, it turned out to be a great ice cliff, rising more than 45 m above sea level. This discovery left Ross with no hope of continuing the expedition as he considered it as unlikely to cross this ice barrier as to sail through the cliffs of Dover (Ross, 1847).

The next day, while discussions were going on about the nature of this ice cliff, the crew of the *Erebus* measured the ocean depth in front of the cliff, while the crew of the *Terror* collected fragments of ice. The lead sank 750 m into the ocean before entering a greenish mud. It was immediately deduced that the cliff was the edge of a large body of ice floating on the ocean (Ross, 1847).

From the account of this expedition, and for nearly a century, this great cliff was known as the "Great Ice Barrier" or "Ross Barrier". When they were lucky enough to get through the pack ice, other explorers came face to face with similar ice cliffs, and retained this terminology, as for the "Filchner Barrier" or the "Larsen Ice Barrier" (Wordie, 1950). At the dawn of the 20th century, with the first mapping work on the floating ice areas, the term "barrier" came to apply to all floating ice surfaces, not just to the cliffs.

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During his forays to the east of the Antarctic Peninsula in 1902, Otto Nordenskjöld was struck by these ice plateaus or low ice terraces, the extent of which could only be glimpsed from the top of the mast. On his return, Nordenskjöld wrote an account of the expedition in German, which was then the international language in this part of Europe (Nordenskjöld 1911). The Swede decided to call this type of floating ice "*Schelfeis*", which was easily translated into English as *shelf ice*.

This term was quickly adopted by explorers and scientists such as Raymond Priestley, who appreciated the toponymic similarity with *continental shelf*, the relatively shallow part of the ocean where shelf ice is only found (Priestley, 1914). The Briton popularised the term with his Canadian brother-in-law Charles Wright, when they published the book *Glaciology*, which reported the scientific discoveries of the Terra Nova expedition (Wright and Priestley, 1922). This book was an international reference for several decades and inspired other authors. Its cost

included a contribution to the public subscription in memory of Robert Scott and his four companions, also members of the Terra Nova expedition, who died after reaching the South Pole a few days after the Norwegian expedition led by Roald Amundsen. In those years, the Great Barrier had finally become the passage to the South Pole that Ross had dreamed of, but by sledge for lack of a navigable route.

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Before being recalled to take part in the Second World War, the American fleet which mapped the coasts of the Amundsen Sea only used the name *shelf ice*, as in "George Getz Shelf Ice". From this expedition, a strong need to clarify and standardise place names in Antarctica was reported, and a special committee was appointed for this purpose in 1943 (Burrill et al., 1956). The Americans decided to stop with this great diversity of names, and only "Ross Shelf Ice" or "Larsen Shelf Ice" were kept, while "Cape Amery" was replaced with "Amery Shelf Ice" (Archives of the *US Board on Geographical Names*, 1947).

These new names were not to everyone's taste. Frank Debenham, who had also taken part in the Terra Nova expedition, tried in vain to re-establish the "Ross Barrier" (Debenham, 1948). For many, it was hard to forget these *barriers* that surrounded so many legendary tales. But *shelf ice* inexorably gained the upper hand, and the debate shifted for a time to *ice shelf* instead of *shelf ice*.

Tired of seeing all the missions of his contemporaries travelling through the same region to increase their chances of reaching the South Pole, Douglas Mawson preferred to lead his expedition southward from Australia in 1911. There he discovered and named the "Shackleton Ice Shelf", in tribute to the explorer Ernest Shackleton, another pioneer in the exploration of the Ross Barrier, whose Antarctic expedition he had joined four years earlier (Mawson, 1914). In 1950, James Wordie, a British scientist and former member of the same Shackleton expeditions, argued for the generalisation of *ice shelf* as a countable geographical entity, and proposed retaining *shelf ice* or *barrier ice* for the type of ice, which could not be counted (Wordie, 1950). The Americans followed this enlightened advice and then only indicated "Ross Ice Shelf", "Larsen Ice Shelf" or "Getz Ice Shelf" on their maps of Antarctica (Archives of the *US Board on Geographical Names*, 1953).

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In 1949, the French finally returned to Antarctica. The loss of Jean-Baptiste Charcot's *Pourquoi Pas?* in 1936 had been followed by a blank period for the French polar expeditions that had just ended thanks to Paul-Émile Victor. Travelling along the coast of Adélie Land aboard *Commandant Charcot*, they named the floating ice bodies in that region. These had been photographed by the American aircraft a few years earlier, and had probably also been seen by Jules Dumont d'Urville and the crews of the *Astrolabe* and the *Zélée* in January 1840.

Dumont d'Urville does not seem to have paid much attention to the ice shelves, although he did marvel at the numerous "floating islands" that seemed to have broken away from the icy coastline. He assumed that the ocean was very deep there, although he had not been able to measure it because all their lines were out of order. Of far greater interest to Dumont d'Urville's crew was the discovery of a rocky archipelago where they planted their flag, following "an

ancient custom that the English had treasured", and in honour of which they opened a bottle of Bordeaux, following another custom (Dumont d'Urville, 1845).

Let's go back to the French who were exploring the coast of Terre Adélie at the dawn of the 1950s. All the discovered stretches of floating ice were named *langue glaciaire* (glacier tongue) together with the naval names *Pourquoi Pas*, *Commandant Charcot*, *Astrolabe* and *Zélée* (Liotard and Barré, 1953). The name "glacier tongue" did not come out of the blue; it had become a common term, generally designating the extension of a single glacier over the ocean, and had been in use since the beginning of the 20th century.

Scott indeed discovered a long, narrow extrusion of floating ice in the Ross Sea in 1902, and had named it "Drygalski Ice Tongue" in tribute to Erich von Drygalski, who was leading a German expedition in the Antarctic seas at the time (Scott was unaware that Drygalski had just been trapped by the ice pack and would remain there for 14 months). Similarly, ten years later, when Mawson returned alone with a few dogs from the tragic sledge expedition that had cost his two companions their lives, he named two glaciers and their floating termini in their honour: the "Mertz Ice Tongue" and the "Ninnis Ice Tongue" (Mawson, 1914).

The terms *ice tongue* and *glacier tongue* were retained alongside *ice shelf* in the post-war American standardisation. No strict, universal criterion was given to distinguish the two terms, even though a glacier tongue seems to always be fed by a single glacier. Nevertheless, the scientific literature established *ice shelf* as a glaciological entity, and "Totten Ice Shelf", for example, has become more common than the official name "Totten Glacier Tongue" in the scientific literature.

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No ice shelves were named by French people apart from the ice tongues of Adélie Land, so that there was no strong historical basis for translating this term into French. The French abstracts that appeared systematically in the *Journal of Glaciology* from 1947 to 1986 adopted "*plateformes de glace*" or "*plateformes glaciaires*", and sometimes even "*ice shelves*" (in French). The French dictionary *Le Petit Larousse* introduced "*ice-shelf*" in 1998, but it has rarely been used since then, possibly because its plural "*ice-shelfs*" confuses bilinguals.

Other French speakers came up with the common name for an ice shelf, although they never officially claimed that name. Belgium had its share of polar legends with Adrien de Gerlache de Gomery. After unsuccessfully offering his services to Nordenskjöld's uncle in 1891, he decided to lead his own expedition with the *Belgica*, on board which they would be forced to winter (de Guerlache, 1902). His son Gaston took advantage of the International Geophysical Year sixty years later to organise a second Belgian expedition. He established the "Roi Baudouin base" on an ice shelf in Queen Maud Land that remained unnamed for a few decades.

In the 1980s, the Japanese scientist Fumihiko Nishio described this ice shelf (Nishio et al., 1984) and suggested naming it after the Belgian base, although he did not use the name himself in his publication. As the base had closed in 1967, Belgian scientists saw an opportunity to maintain the name "Roi Baudouin" in Antarctica, and Frank Pattyn and his colleagues (1992) began using the name "Roi Baudouin Ice Shelf" just one year before the King's death. The name has since made its way into the scientific literature, and the French-language Belgian press regularly mentions the "*plateforme de glace Roi Baudouin*".

CHAPTER IV

UNSTABLE GROUNDING LINES

Un profond ancrage

In the 1970s, glaciologists were no longer speaking of ice barriers in Antarctica, but some of them perhaps ended up regretting that the term had not been retained. Not because they impeded access to the South Pole, but because it was discovered that they exerted a buttressing effect, restraining the ice sheet flow into the ocean.

From the beginning of the 20th century, it was found that Antarctic ice shelves were systematically attached to one or more glaciers, leaving little doubt as to their main origin: a flow of continental ice that ended up floating on the ocean before melting or fracturing into a multitude of icebergs (Balch, 1912).

In 1926, Hans Mothes developed seismic echo sounding to measure the thickness of a glacier in the Austrian Alps. This method was used on the polar ice sheets from the early 1930s, although the need to transport tens of kilograms of explosives for each measurement severely limited its application (Sorge, 1933). The second expedition led by Richard Byrd Jr, the first to fly over the South Pole a few years earlier, used these soundings to show that a connection between the Ross and Weddell Seas was unlikely (Mill, 1936). This was confirmed in the following decades by Charles Bentley and Ned Ostenso (1961) who also pointed out that a large part of West Antarctica was grounded below sea level.

The concept of grounding line was introduced by John Hollin (1962). This line separates three environments: the ice grounded on the continental shelf, the floating ice shelf and the ocean. Hollin emphasised the role of sea level in the movement of the grounding line during glaciations and deglaciations.

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The increasing number of observations of ice shelves in the 1950s revealed the importance of rocky pinning points, acting as anchors, for the existence of ice shelves (Swithinbank 1955). In 1968, the American John Mercer added a climatic limit to their existence. Inspired by a meticulous review of the climatic and glaciological conditions of the Peninsula by de Gordon de Quetteville Robin and Raymond Adie (1964), he proposed that an ice shelf was not viable for a surface air temperature above 0°C in January, at the pick of the austral summer (Mercer, 1968).

Having observed geological evidence of large past variations in the ice sheet thickness, he argued that the disappearance of ice shelves could have caused the disappearance of most of the West Antarctic ice sheet during the last interglacial period, about 120,000 years ago. Referring to earlier work by Robin, he argued that an ice sheet grounded more than 170 m below sea level could not be stable without an ice shelf. The disappearance of ice shelves in

West Antarctica would therefore imply the disintegration of the ice sheet which is grounded well below sea level (Mercer, 1968).

Mercer took up this argument again ten years later when considering the future of West Antarctica, but consolidated it with new scientific advances.

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At the end of the 1950s, Syukuro Manabe joined the group at Princeton University, USA, that was developing the first numerical models of the atmospheric general circulation. In the years that followed, he developed a way of representing the evolution of the radiative effects of water vapour, carbon dioxide and ozone, and was behind the first climate model able to represent the heat transported by the ocean to the poles thanks to the inclusion of the ocean model developed by his colleague Kirk Bryan (Manabe, 1969; Manabe and Bryan, 1969).

In 1975, with his colleague Richard Wetherald, he carried out the first three-dimensional simulations of the atmospheric response to a doubling of carbon dioxide concentration. These simulations were limited to the Northern Hemisphere and did not represent the seasonal cycle or ocean currents, but they showed a polar amplification of global warming attributed to the recession of the continental snow cover and of the sea-ice cover. Surface air warming averaged 2.9°C globally, but reached 7°C at 70°N and 10°C at 80°N (Manabe and Wetherald, 1975).

In 1976, Bert Bolin, of Stockholm University, testified before a subcommittee of the US House of Representatives on the environment, which led to the first National Climate Program Act in 1978. He indicated that if the acceleration in the use of coal and oil continued at the rate of the 1970s, the concentration of carbon dioxide would double in the next 50 years. By contrast, this doubling would take around 200 years if the use of carbon-based energy remained constant (Correll, 1998).

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At the same time, a controversy had arisen about West Antarctica as to whether the ice sheet was growing or shrinking, or even becoming unstable (Weertman, 1974). In view of the available observations, it seemed possible to Terence Hughes that this part of the ice sheet was in the process of disintegrating (Hughes, 1973). This led Johannes Weertman (1974) to establish equations for the grounding line position of an unconfined ice shelf. He found an expression for the depth at which a grounding line could be stable.

This theory indicated that a prograde continental bedrock, i.e., one that sinks from the centre towards the periphery of the ice sheet, was favourable to the grounding line stability. In contrast, a retrograde bedrock was favourable to an instability. For Weertman (1974), only a rise in sea level could trigger instability in West Antarctica. Robert Thomas (1976) envisaged oscillations in the position of the grounding line linked to isostasy. Weertman and Thomas did not believe at the time that atmospheric changes could lead directly to an instability in West Antarctica.

Mercer followed the early climate projections with interest, and used them to make the first projection of the fate of the West Antarctic ice shelves and ice sheet in response to anthropogenic emissions. He used the climatic limit of viability of ice shelves that he derived

in 1968 (0°C in January). From the aforementioned climate projections, he concluded that the ice shelves of the Antarctic Peninsula could be in the process of disappearing or close to it, while the Ross and Ronne-Filchner ice shelves were threatened in the decades to come. Indeed, on the one hand their temperature in January was already thought to be close to -5°C, and on the other hand, the carbon emissions projected by Bolin and the polar amplification of Manabe and Wetherald made a 10°C warming plausible in the next 50 years near 80°S (Mercer, 1978).

Mercer concluded that the increase in the use of carbon-based energy would lead to the rapid disappearance of a large part of West Antarctica, with a sea level rise of around 5 meters. He warned that the early warming indicator would be the progressive disintegration of ice shelves from the north to the south of the Antarctic Peninsula (Mercer, 1978). This began to happen some twenty years later.

CHAPTER V

ICE SHELF COLLAPSES IN THE ANTARCTIC PENINSULA

Un cap, une Péninsule

Five years before its final collapse, an ice shelf in the northern end of the Antarctic Peninsula (64°S) was officially named “Prince Gustav Ice Shelf” by the United Kingdom Antarctic Place-Names Committee. They took the name from the channel on which it was floating, discovered in 1902 by Nordenskjöld. In 1995, the British Antarctic Survey announced to the press the near complete disintegration of this ice shelf, as well as the part of the Larsen Ice Shelf located just north of 65°S, which would later be called "Larsen A" (Cooper, 1997; Rott et al., 1996).

As early as 1991, Christopher Doake and David Vaughan reported that the Wordie Ice Shelf, on the other side of the Peninsula, near 69°S, was significantly shrinking (Doake and Vaughan, 1991), and its complete disintegration was announced in 2009. Vaughan and Doake (1996) reviewed all the observations of ice shelf retreat on both sides of the Peninsula, as well as data from weather stations, and explained the retreat by a 2.5°C warming since 1945. The first estimates of the extent and duration of surface melting using microwave satellite images (Ridely, 1993; Zwally and Fiegles, 1994) confirmed this trend since 1978.

Vaughan and Doake (1996) adjusted the climatic limit of ice shelf viability used by Mercer (1978). They figured out that the -5°C isotherm for mean annual air temperature was a better indicator. Its southward progression since 1945 could explain the gradual disintegration of ice shelves in the Antarctic Peninsula. However, they lacked perspective to be able to attribute these disintegrations to anthropogenic emissions, and noted that the processes involved remained poorly understood, particularly those involving the percolation of meltwater into the snow.

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The second report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) was published in February 1995, the month when the disintegration of the Prince Gustav and Larsen-A ice shelves was announced to the press. This report, like the previous one five years earlier, devoted a page to the risk of ice sheet instability in West Antarctica, and this time mentioned the disintegration of these ice shelves, but was unable to attribute it, even broadly, to human activities (Houghton et al., 1990, 1995).

This disintegration led to more work on the stability of ice shelves. By modelling the mechanical strain rates of the Larsen B Ice Shelf, Doake (1998) highlighted the existence of a compressive arch across the ice shelf, separating the part in compression, responsible for the buttressing effect, from the part in extension, floating almost freely. The idea was that a retreat of the calving front through this arch would generate an instability of the ice shelf, which would then disintegrate largely or entirely. The disintegration of Larsen A in 1995 was accompanied by the calving of a large tabular iceberg from Larsen B, but the compressive arch was not

reached. Doake nonetheless noted that the progressive retreat of the front from 1995 to 1998 brought it dangerously close to the compressive arch. The disintegration of most of Larsen B occurred four years after his publication, in early 2002.

While revisiting the 1995 disintegration, Theodore Scambos and his colleagues (2000) noted the systematic presence of meltwater ponds over the ice shelves before their disintegration. The mechanical model of the Larsen A-B ice shelves developed by Christina Hulbe also suggested the need for meltwater to exert pressure in the crevasses and keep them open until the zone that fractured in 1995. This work built on previous studies describing the role of liquid water pressure on crevasse depth (Weertman, 1973; Hughes 1983; van der Veen 1998), and this phenomenon started to be referred to as hydro-fracturing.

Just before the disintegration of Larsen B, an Argentinian team including Pedro Skvarca and Hernán De Angelis was preparing various measurements on the ice shelf and was hampered by the omnipresence of meltwater ponds (Skvarca et al., 2004). These numerous ponds were later seen on satellite images (Scambos et al., 2003). The exceptional nature of the melting event was confirmed through the estimation of melt rates based on weather station data and energy budgets by Michiel van de Broeke (2005) in Utrecht and by Olga Sergienko and Douglas Macayeal (2005) in Chicago. Much later, [Jonathan Wille and his colleagues \(2022\)](#) linked this event, as well as that of 1995, to occurrences of atmospheric rivers, i.e., intrusions of moist air of tropical origin.

On the basis of these disintegrations, Scambos and colleagues (2003) adjusted the ice shelf viability criterion to a mean summer temperature of -1.5°C . By re-analysing all the available air and snow temperature data for the 20th century, Elizabeth Morris and David Vaughan (2003) found that no ice shelf on the Peninsula had been viable north of the -5°C annual isotherm, while those south of the -9°C annual isotherm all appeared stable. But the community was beginning to see a more subtle role for melting than a simple temperature criterion.

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In 1991, William Tad Pfeffer and two colleagues from Boulder Colorado looked at the mass balance of the Greenland Ice Sheet, which is much more affected by surface melting than the Antarctic ice sheet. Using a very simple firn physics model applied to conditions typical of Greenland, they showed that if the annual melt rate was less than approximately 70% of the annual snow accumulation, then all the liquid water percolated into the firn and refroze there. Peter Kuipers Munneke and others (2014) modelled the firn physics in climate projections and found that percolation and refreezing in the firn had a buffering effect, limiting the availability of liquid water for hydro-fracturing on many ice shelves of Antarctica.

Using a regional climate model and Pfeffer's aforementioned considerations, [Marion Donat-Magnin and colleagues \(2021\)](#) predicted that more than half of the ice shelves in the Amundsen Sea could be safe from hydro-fracking during the 21st century even under the most adverse emission scenario. Ella Gilbert and Christoph Kittel (2021) predicted that a warming of 4°C would be fatal to two-thirds of the ice shelves in East Antarctica and the Peninsula. In 2023, Melchior van Wessem and his colleagues confirmed a viability threshold of -5°C annual temperature for ice shelves experiencing relatively heavy snowfall, but found that colder, drier ice shelves such as Amery, Ross and Filchner-Ronne could be subject to hydro-fracturing as early as -15°C .

These results on ice shelf surface conditions were obtained using two regional atmospheric models whose representation of polar processes had gradually become sufficiently reliable. Since the 1990s, MAR, the *Modèle Atmosphérique Régional*, had been developed in Belgium and France (Gallée et al., 2001; Agosta et al., 2019), and RACMO, the Regional Atmospheric Climate Model, had been developed in the Netherlands (van den Broeke and van Lipzig 2003; Lenaerts et al., 2012). These two models had improved cloud microphysics, turbulence under stable conditions, blowing snow and albedo in polar conditions. They had both included a snow model of several layers, making it possible to represent firn densification as well as meltwater percolation and refreezing.

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Alison Banwell, Douglas Macayeal and Olga Sergienko led several studies highlighting a complementary mechanism for fracturing ice shelves through melting. By modelling the elastic deformation of ice shelves, they showed that the accumulation of water in a lake (at the surface) or an aquifer (in the firn) caused local deflection under the weight of water, generating stress and possibly the appearance of concentric crevasses around the accumulation zone, as well as radial crevasses underneath. These radial crevasses could lead to a sudden drainage of the accumulated water, as it has sometimes been observed, and to reverse bending, favouring the creation of other crevasses (Macayeal and Sergienko, 2013; Banwell et al., 2019).

Banwell and her colleagues (2013) suggested that the disintegration of Larsen B may have been induced by a chain reaction in which the crevasses from the above mechanism reached other areas with accumulated liquid water, promoting drainage, and so on. Subsequent estimates by Alexander Robel and Alison Banwell (2019) with a simple model pointed more towards a large-scale melting event than a chain mechanism.

It is in this context that David Pollard, Robert DeConto and Richard Alley proposed a new ice sheet instability mechanism in 2015, in which ice shelf disintegration was the precursor. This was named Marine Ice Cliff Instability (MICI). They put forward the idea that a complete and sudden ice shelf disintegration would give way to ice cliffs so high that they would collapse under their own weight. On the basis of observations and ice mechanics models, Jeremy Bassis and Catherine Walker (2012) had shown that an ice front facing the ocean was unstable if its height exceeded 900 to 1000 meters.

This instability mechanism and its implementation in the model used by DeConto and Pollard (2016) resulted in ice sheet mass loss projections that were much higher than those produced by other models. Such projections were considered plausible but with a low level of confidence by the authors of the 6th IPCC report (Fox-Kemper et al., 2021). The elements supporting or invalidating this mechanism were synthesised by Bassis and others in 2024. As far as Larsen B is concerned, the 2002 disintegration led to a high ice cliff facing the ocean at Crane Glacier's front, but the lack of measurements made it impossible to characterise the cliff failure unambiguously, and the glacier stabilised and then regrew a few years after the ice shelf collapse (Needell and Holschuh, 2023).

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Whether the marine ice cliff instability exists or not, the presence of surface meltwater is not sufficient to disintegrate an ice shelf. Since the 1940s, most expeditions crossing the George VI ice shelf, on the west coast of the Peninsula, have noted the presence of numerous melt ponds, without any resulting ice shelf weakening (Wager, 1972; Cook and Vaughan, 2010). This contributed to demonstrate the need for mechanical stress favourable to ice damage and eventually hydro-fracturing.

With regard to the Larsen Ice Shelf, Andrew Shepherd (2003) and his colleagues showed that the disintegration of Larsen B had been preceded by a longer-term thinning that could only be explained by melting by the ocean. This thinning had therefore probably preconditioned the disintegration by making it more vulnerable to the presence of crevasses.

The idea of mechanical preconditioning of hydro-fracturing was generalised by Ching-Lao Lai and her colleagues in 2020. Based on satellite observations, artificial neural networks and a fracture model, they estimated that in 2020, approximately 60% of the ice shelf surface was both in the zone buttressing the upstream ice flow, and in a mechanical regime conducive to hydro-fracturing in the presence of heavy surface melting conditions.

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From approximately 2009, satellite images revealed the progressive fragmentation of Thwaites glacier's western tongue, in the Amundsen Sea (Wild et al., 2022). This time, surface melting had nothing to do with it, as snow accumulation was much greater than surface melting (Lenaerts et al., 2018; [Donat-Magnin et al., 2020](#)). In 2020, Stef Lhermitte, Sainan Sun and their colleagues showed that the ice shelf had become progressively damaged as a result of its thinning, with the effect of reducing the ice rigidity and accelerating its flow.

Ice shelf damage and fracturing are still difficult to represent reliably in ice sheet models. That said, the models clearly show that if all the Antarctic ice shelves were to disintegrate at once, the ice flow acceleration all over Antarctica would lead to a rise in sea level of 1 to 5 metres in 150 years (Sun et al., 2020).

CHAPTER VI

WARM WATER IN THE AMUNDSEN SEA

Coup de chaud à l'île des Pins

With a name originating from Florida, Pine Island Glacier was predestined for warmth. At the height of the Second World War, the Pine Island Bay, in Florida, gave its name to a warship equipped to deploy seaplanes: the USS Pine Island. As soon as peace was restored, this ship was sent to the Amundsen Sea and served as a rear base for the first aerial observations. This led to the first mapping of the bay to which the ship name was given. In the 1960s, American aircraft returned to map the glaciers, and it was very natural that the one flowing into Pine Island Bay should take the same name.

As mentioned previously, it was clear in the early 1980s that Pine Island Glacier and its neighbour Thwaites Glacier drained most of the ice below sea level in West Antarctica. Some scientists (e.g., Hughes, 1981) suggested that these glaciers might be unstable, but the few observations available did not seem to support this hypothesis. All the ingredients were then becoming available to estimate changes in the mass of Pine Island Glacier: the first Landsat satellite launched in 1972 by the United States had provided successive images of the glacier from which it was possible to follow the motion of crevasses and deduce the glacier velocity; the observation of firn stratigraphy in the glacial drainage basin of Pine Island in the early 1960s made it possible to estimate the snow accumulation rate (Shimizu 1964); aerial surveys using radio echo sounding had provided the thickness of the glacier. Richard Crabtree and Christopher Doake (1982) concluded that the Pine Island glacier was gaining mass, but pointed out that this result was weakly reliable because of the many uncertainties involved.

Crabtree and Doake (1982) were also the first to properly establish the existence of an ice shelf at the end of Pine Island Glacier, extending over 80 km from a grounding line located on a bathymetric ridge. The melt rates beneath this ice shelf did not arouse much interest the following decade, and they were largely neglected in glaciological studies. Arguably, most observations had focused on the Ross and Ronne-Filchner ice shelves, and suggested that low melt rates and abundant refreezing (marine ice) were the norm under all ice shelves of Antarctica (Jacobs, 1991). Yet, the Pine Island ice shelf was in the process of becoming a kind of polar black swan.

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Stanley Jacobs thought it was important to go and explore the Amundsen Sea from an oceanographic point of view, and he managed to organise a mission aboard the American icebreaker *Nathaniel B. Palmer* in 1994. They set off from the Ross Sea, where the water at any depth is close to the surface freezing point (-1.9°C). As they entered the Amundsen Sea, and all the way down to the Bellingshausen Sea, they measured temperatures at depth that were 2 to 3°C warmer than this freezing point. All these measurements indicated that Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW) penetrated abundantly over the entire continental shelf of this region, which had never been observed around Antarctica (Jacobs et al., 1996).

Together with Hartmut Hellmer and Adrian Jenkins, two collaborators who took part in the expedition, Jacobs used two temperature and salinity profiles measured along the front of Pine Island Glacier to estimate the currents, assuming the geostrophic balance (between the Coriolis force and the effect of ocean density gradients on pressure). This was used to calculate the heat budget of what enters and what leaves the sea underneath Pine Island. An average melt rate of 10 to 12 metres of ice per year was estimated. This was consistent with the results of a simple thermohaline circulation model, with measurements of dissolved oxygen (from bubbles trapped in the ice) and with the concentration of water isotopes (oxygen-18) that helped identify meltwater from continental ice that is highly depleted in heavy isotopes (Hellmer et al., 1998).

Based on these new estimates and on what was known at the time about surface snow accumulation and iceberg calving, Jacobs et al (1996) estimated that the Antarctic ice sheet was possibly losing mass or was close to doing so. They suggested that this could explain some of the recent sea level rise that had not been attributed to other sources. However, these estimates were highly uncertain and difficult to verify.

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After mapping the Moon by satellite in preparation for the American mission that took the first humans there in 1966, Baerbel Lucchitta turned her attention to the ice on Mars and then in Antarctica. A year before Jacobs' publication, Lucchitta and her colleagues (1995) re-estimated the mass balance of Pine Island Glacier using new satellite technology. The European Space Agency had launched its first dedicated Earth observation satellite (ERS1) four years earlier. It was equipped with a radar echo sounding system which, unlike Landsat, was not sensitive to cloud cover and had a higher resolution enabling a better tracking of crevasses. Lucchitta found that the glacier velocity was higher than the previous estimates based on Landsat, and the new calculations indicated a slight mass loss. She cautiously concluded that the balance was less positive than in the previous estimates.

It was another use of the ERS technology that highlighted the ongoing evolution of Pine Island Glacier. Eric Rignot (1998) combined the interference between several successive radar images to isolate the changes in glacier surface elevation induced by tides. This made it possible to visualise the transition between the floating part of the glacier, affected by the tide, and the landed part. He found that the grounding line of Pine Island Glacier had retreated by 1,200 metres between 1992 and 1996 (with a precision of 300 m), which implied a thinning of 3.5 metres per year above the grounding line, with an accuracy of less than one metre per year. Three years later, similar results were published on the nearby Thwaites glacier (Rignot 2001), and quickly attributed to glacier acceleration rather than surface processes (Rignot et al., 2002).

For several years, the scientific community debated the cause of this change and whether it could be representative of a longer-term trend or even of the beginning of an instability. The development of satellite observations in the years following the first evidence of grounding line retreat would deserve a separate chronicle, with in particular the development of ice velocity measurements by correlation of successive images, direct measurement of ice mass by spatial gravimetry, as well as radar and laser altimetry. In short, the methodologies were gradually refined and the different methods converged in the early 2010s: the glaciers in the Amundsen sector had undeniably lost mass since the early 1990s (Shepherd et al., 2012; Flament and Rémy, 2012), and the ocean was largely responsible for this (Pritchard et al.,

2012). The autonomous submarines sent by Jenkins and his colleagues (2010) under the Pine Island ice shelf confirmed the presence of weakly modified Circumpolar Deep Water.

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The first large-scale numerical ice flow model was probably developed by Molly Mahaffy (1976) for the Barnes Ice Cap on Baffin Island, Canada. Numerical models of the thermomechanical behaviour of the Antarctic ice were subsequently developed in the 1990s. They suggested a fairly stable ice sheet over periods shorter than the glacial/interglacial cycles (Pattyn 2018), which probably contributed to make the community dubious about the imminent risk of instability predicted in the 1970s.

This first generation of ice sheet models did in fact not consider the influence of ice shelves on the upstream flow of grounded ice. Early ice sheet models were using the “Shallow Ice Approximation” of the Stokes equations, which was appropriate for coarse resolution and limited computing power but not suitable to model fast ice streams and ice shelves. A part of the community was putting forward the idea that ice shelves were too weak to influence the upstream flow (Hindmarsh and Lemeur 2001), while another part of the community believed in the role of ice shelves in a potential ice sheet instability and was developing models representing the ice shelf flow (Rommelaere and Ritz, 1996).

Christian Schoof (2007) provided mathematical proof of a Marine Ice Sheet Instability (MISI), by putting the grounding line dynamics in equations. This, together with the persistent ice mass loss observed in West Antarctica, forced the community to fundamentally revise the approximations and spatial resolutions used in ice sheet models, and to represent ice shelves and their basal melting. The new modelling requirements were highlighted in the MISMIP and MISMIP3d model intercomparisons coordinated by Frank Pattyn (2012, 2013).

In 2014, this new model generation revealed a strong sensitivity of the ice flow to increased melt rates beneath Pine Island (Favier et al., 2014) and Thwaites (Joughin et al., 2014). These studies emphasised the risk of crossing a tipping point, after which the contribution to sea level would become self-sustained. However, the big unknown remained the evolution of melting by the ocean, and its influence on the runaway’s probability, timing and amplitude. The few oceanographic campaigns in the Amundsen Sea since 1994 had shown some interannual variability in the volume of relatively warm water near the Pine Island and Dotson ice shelves (Dutrieux et al., 2014; Jenkins et al., 2018), but numerical modelling of the ocean and melt underneath ice shelves proved essential to understanding the past and future evolution of the glaciers terminating in the Amundsen Sea, as we will see in the next chapter.

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It was thought for a while that the Amundsen-Bellinghshausen Seas and West Antarctica were unique, but several observational indices suggested that a part of East Antarctica could play a similar role. At the height of the Pliocene epoch, approximately 3 million years ago, the climate was 2 to 4°C warmer than in the 2000s and the global mean sea level was 10 to 25 meters higher according to paleoclimatic indices. Such a high sea level suggested that part of the East Antarctic Ice Sheet had melted in addition to West Antarctica (Miller et al., 2012).

In addition, the methods used to reconstruct bedrock topography from ice-penetrating radar were refined and revealed that the ice sheet was resting on a continental bedrock below sea level in the Wilkes (BANZARE coast) and Aurora (Sabrina coast) sub-basins (**Fig. 2**), in the sector of East Antarctica facing the Indian Ocean (Young et al., 2011; Roberts et al., 2011). This made the sector potentially vulnerable to a Marine Ice Sheet Instability.

On their return from missions aboard the *Aurora Australis*, Nathan Bindoff (2000), then Guy Williams (2008), and their colleagues reported the presence of Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW) at the edge of the continental shelf off the Sabrina coast. In 2015, Jamin Greenbaum and others combined airborne radar echo sounding with measurements of the gravity field and magnetic field perturbations by bedrock to reconstruct the bathymetry of this sector. They found numerous deep passages that likely allowed CDW to access the Totten Ice Shelf.

At the same time, laser altimetry from the IceSat satellite enabled Hamish Pritchard and others (2009) to identify a thinning of Totten Glacier. When they estimated the mass balance of Antarctic ice shelves from satellite data and regional atmospheric models, Eric Rignot and colleagues (2013) reported that the Totten Ice Shelf was melting at rates far greater than any other ice shelf in East Antarctica. Stephen Rintoul and colleagues (2016) obtained the first oceanographic observations near the Totten front, and confirmed the intrusion of CDW beneath the ice shelf.

CHAPTER VII

MODELLING ICE SHELF MELTING, IMPACTS OF WINDS AND TIDES

Rester de glace, contre vents et marées

At Princeton University, where climate models had been developed some fifteen years earlier, Douglas MacAyeal (1984a,b) developed a numerical model of the tides under the Ross ice shelf. This model represented the barotropic tides, i.e., the planetary displacement of water volumes, and the interaction with the ice shelf was modelled via its friction on the water column. He deduced that the tide-induced vertical mixing was sufficient to bring heat from the dense water at depth to the ice shelf base, and that the resulting melting thus generated a thermohaline circulation.

The following year, MacAyeal (1985) proposed a simple numerical plume model along a unidirectional subglacial slope. The meltwater buoyancy created a flow towards the ocean surface, along the ice slope. He highlighted the key role played by turbulent entrainment of underlying water into the plume. Adrian Jenkins (1991) significantly improved this plume model, particularly the thermodynamical part, and obtained melt rates close to those deduced from glaciological observations of the Ronne Ice Shelf, at least away from the areas most influenced by tide.

At the same time, the Germans Hartmut Hellmer and Dirk Olbers (1989) had written the 200th paper of the Alfred Wegener Institute on a numerical model representing the entire overturning circulation in a vertical section across an ice shelf. This model would be used five years later to estimate melt rates beneath Pine Island after the first oceanographic campaign in the Amundsen Sea. For these first steps in numerical modelling of the ocean below ice shelves, the main motivation was mostly to understand an environment that remained unknown.

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The first numerical model to represent the global ocean and its extension beneath Antarctic ice shelves was probably the tidal model that Christian Le Provost and his colleagues developed in Grenoble in the early 1990s (Le Provost et al., 1994). They found that the ocean extension below Ronne-Filchner Ice Shelf was essential for simulating the tides in the Atlantic, and noted a strong influence of the ice shelf cavity shape as far north as the Gulf of Guinea, 8000 km away (IOC, 2002). Like the MacAyeal model (1984a,b), Le Provost's model only represented the barotropic tide, and neither the ocean thermodynamics nor ice shelf melting.

More or less at the same time, Jürgen Determann and Rüdiger Gerdes (1994), followed by their postdoc Klaus Grosfeld at the Alfred Wegener Institute, were the first to use a three-dimensional ocean circulation model solving the primitive equations of fluid dynamics under a highly idealised version of the Ronne-Filchner Ice Shelf. This model was derived from the one developed by Kirk Bryan and Michael Cox from the 1960s to the 1980s at Princeton University, which had just been named MOM (Modular Ocean Model), with a code already publicly available on an FTP server (Pacanowski et al., 1991). The Germans were motivated

by the need to estimate ice shelf melt rates, both because for the potential risks of instability proposed by Mercer (1978) and because of its role in the formation of Antarctic Bottom Water (AABW), which cools and densifies the abyssal ocean of our planet.

The formulation of exchanges at the ocean-ice interface benefited from interactions with Hellmer, who returned to Germany in 1996. The model was then extended to the near open ocean (Grosfeld et al., 1997). Grosfeld left for the University of Münster in 1998, and together with Malte Toma, they continued to develop this ocean model, calling it ROMBAX (Revisited Ocean Model based on Bryan And coX; Thoma et al., 2006). The model was widely used for the Weddell Sea, and for other ice shelves such as Amery (Williams et al., 1998). Grosfeld and Thoma then moved on to other professional activities and the model fell into disuse.

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During his time in Dale Haidvogel's team at Johns Hopkins University in the United States, Aike Beckmann developed expertise in SPEM, the Semi-spectral Primitive Equation Model, which was to serve as the basis for ROMS, the Regional Ocean Model System, a few years later (Haidvogel et al., 1991, 2000). When Beckmann later joined the Alfred Wegener Institute, he logically started from SPEM to develop BRIOS, the Bremerhaven Regional Ocean Simulations, with Hartmut Hellmer and Ralph Timmermann (Beckmann et al. 1999). This involved a circum-Antarctic configuration of the Southern Ocean and its extensions under the largest ice shelves, with a grid narrowed to 1.5° over the Weddell Sea. BRIOS made it possible to demonstrate the impact of ice shelf melting on the Southern Ocean stratification (Hellmer 2004). It was also the first model used for ice shelf melting projections under future greenhouse gases emission scenarios, revealing a possible tipping point in the melting of Ronne-Filchner if warm water were to penetrate into the ice shelf cavity (Hellmer et al., 2012).

Then, still at the Alfred Wegener Institute, BRIOS gave way to FESOM, the Finite-Element Sea ice-Ocean Model, whose unstructured grid made it possible to represent both the global ocean circulation and the circulation under numerous ice shelves (Timmermann et al., 2012). The first Antarctic-wide ice shelf melting projections were then produced for two emission scenarios by Ralph Timmermann and his colleagues (2013), and the exercise was repeated a few years later by Kaitlin Naughten and her colleagues (2018) for other scenarios. While these simulations were entirely plausible for the Ronne-Filchner and Ross ice shelves, the Amundsen Sea was far too cold in present conditions, making the FESOM projections in this sector implausible.

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During her postdoc at the Alfred Wegener Institute in 2001, Robin Robertson collaborated with Beckmann and Hellmer to include the representation of ice shelves in the newly released ROMS model. Previously, she had worked with Laurie Padman at Oregon State University in the United States, on how melt rates beneath the Filchner Ronne ice shelf were affected by internal tides, i.e., the waves in ocean density stratification induced by tides. Her attempts with POM, the Princeton Ocean Model, developed for coastal applications (Blumberg and Mellor, 1987), had been unsuccessful due to excessive errors in the calculation of the pressure gradient (Robertson et al. 1999). ROMS benefited from a new method of calculating this gradient (Shchepetkin and McWilliams, 2003) which reduced the errors, and Robertson was able to

emphasize the role of vertical mixing by internal tides on the properties of water masses reaching the Ross ice shelf (Robertson et al., 2003).

As Robertson's version was not made public, several groups redeveloped the ability of ROMS to simulate the ocean circulation under ice shelves, including Michael Dinniman and colleagues (2007) at Old Dominion University in Virginia, and Benjamin Galton-Fenzi (2009) at the University of Tasmania. Before switching to ROMS, Galton-Fenzi had first encountered the same problems as Robertson with an Australian version of POM. In various groups, ROMS made it possible to show that an important fraction of ice shelf melting was generated by tides in various regions. This was explained both by the turbulence generated by tidal currents under the ice and by the tidal vertical mixing near the ice shelf fronts (Mueller et al., 2009; Robertson 2013; Arzeno et al., 2014; Richter et al., 2022).

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The three-dimensional models of sub-glacial cavities mentioned so far were formulated using vertical coordinates known as "s" or " σ ", which follow the topography of the ocean floor and ice shelves. These coordinates had the advantage of simulating the circulation along the ice shelf base fairly smoothly and uniformly, but the disadvantage of generating significant numerical errors in the calculation of pressure gradients, which created non-physical currents, particularly in the presence of steep topographic slopes.

Other ocean modellers considered that isopycnal coordinates (i.e., in potential density) were more natural for the ocean, where exchanges mainly take place along layers of the same density. This was the case for Rainer Bleck and his colleagues at the University of Miami, who developed MICOM, the Miami Isopycnic Coordinate Ocean Model, in the early 1990s (Bleck et al., 1992). After fundamentally revising the formulation of thermodynamical exchanges between the ocean and ice shelves, David Holland and Adrian Jenkins decided to modify MICOM to make it capable of representing the circulation under Ronne-Filchner (Holland and Jenkins, 1999, 2001). MICOM was then used for Ross (Holland et al., 2003) and to represent tides (Makinson et al., 2011). The isopycnal model developed by Robert Hallberg (1997) in Princeton was also adapted for subglacial cavities by Christopher Little and others (2009).

MICOM was briefly and successfully used to represent the Amundsen Sea by Malte Thoma in collaboration with Jenkins, Holland and Jacobs (2008). They showed that the zonal wind above the continental shelf break modulated the interannual intrusions of warm CDW into the Amundsen Sea. This warm water then crossed the continental shelf via bathymetric channels extending all the way to the grounding line of Pine Island and Thwaites. The simulated variations in warm water inflow were found to be consistent with the observed acceleration phases of Pine Island Glacier.

These MICOM simulations were then reused by Eric Steig and his colleagues to show the link with intertropical variability: atmospheric convection anomalies in the central equatorial Pacific generate Rossby waves that propagate south-eastwards as far as the Amundsen-Bellinghausen Seas, affecting winds at the edge of the continental shelf and thereby warm water inflows (Steig et al., 2012). Having previously analysed ice cores from this sector of the Antarctic Ice Sheet, Steig had observed a strong climate anomaly in the 1940s concomitant with a strong El Niño event. Steig and his colleagues therefore suggested that the changes undergone by Pine Island Glacier may have begun in the 1940s, which was confirmed a few

years later by the analysis of marine sediments showing a grounding line retreat at this period (Smith et al., 2017).

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A third type of vertical coordinate, the height or “Z” coordinate, had other advantages such as low numerical error on the pressure gradient and good representation of diapycnal mixing (across density layers), so that it was largely used in global models. The difficulty of representing dense flows at the bottom of the ocean in Z-coordinate models had certainly dampened any motivation to include circulation under ice shelves, until Martin Losch (2008), from the Alfred Wegener Institute, looked at the implementation in MITgcm, the Massachusetts Institute of Technology, initiated by John Marshall and colleagues (1998).

The main problem with the Z coordinates under ice shelves was the potential jump of several vertical levels of the ocean-ice interface between a grid point and its neighbour. To overcome this problem, partially wetted cells were introduced to represent the actual ice shelf base topography, as proposed for the bathymetry by Alistair Adcroft and his colleagues (1997). But the thickness of model cells located right under the ice still had a strong impact, resulting in very noisy melting patterns. Losch greatly reduced this problem by averaging the temperature and salinity seen by the ice over a boundary layer of imposed thickness. This became known as the “Losch layer”, and has been used since then in all the Z-coordinate models that implemented interactions with ice shelves.

MITgcm then started to be widely used, notably at the British Antarctic Survey and at the California Institute of Technology. For example, it was used to emphasise that a good knowledge of ice topography is essential for simulating realistic basal melt rates (Schodlok et al., 2012; Millgate et al., 2013; DeRydt et al., 2014). Paul Holland developed a circum-Antarctic configuration of MITgcm to analyse the trends in sea ice extent over the Southern Ocean (Holland et al., 2014), and his simulations were largely used as boundary conditions for higher resolution regional studies focusing on individual regions or ice shelves.

These regional simulations advanced the understanding of the influence of winds on the interannual variability of CDW intrusions in the Amundsen Sea. Zonal wind variations at the continental shelf break change both the depth of the thermocline (Dotto et al., 2019) and the eastward undercurrent that favours the entry of circumpolar warm water into the bathymetric channels crossing the continental shelf (Assmann et al., 2013; Kimura et al., 2017; Silvano et al., 2022). This eastward undercurrent had been identified thanks to observations from the 2003 cruise aboard the *James Clark Ross* by Dziga Walker and others (2013).

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Pascale Delecluse developed her expertise in ocean modelling during her postdoctoral work at Princeton University. In the late 1980s, she took advantage of the arrival of a supercomputer in France and a position at the *Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique* to start developing a French ocean model based on the work of Bryan and Cox. This Z-coordinate model was quickly named OPA (Océan PARallélisé) and was developed by a number of researchers, including Gurvan Madec. OPA was coupled to atmospheric models at the *Centre Européen de Recherche et de Formation Avancée en Calcul Scientifique* in Toulouse and at the Institute

Pierre Simon Laplace in Paris from the mid-1990s, and then integrated into several European climate models in the 2000s and 2010s (Guilyardi et al., 2012).

The model was given the name of NEMO (Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean) in 2003 when a French-British development consortium was set up. When NEMO became the oceanic component of the Met Office Hadley Centre's climate model, Adrian Jenkins thought it would be a good idea to include the ability to represent the ocean under ice shelves. Pierre Mathiot implemented this during his postdoc, benefitting from the presence of Gurvan Madec, who was then working partly in England, as well as on the previous work of Martin Losch in MITgcm (Mathiot et al., 2017).

This new model capability came at the right time and was quickly used by the NEMO community in several studies, some of which are described later in this report. It was used to quantify the effect of sub-shelf melting on the circulation and sea ice in the Amundsen region (Jourdain et al., 2017; Donat-Magnin et al., 2017), and on the formation of water masses in the Ross and Weddell Seas (Hutchinson et al., 2023). This was used to estimate the impact of tides on ice shelf basal melting in the Amundsen (Jourdain et al., 2019), Weddell (Hausmann et al., 2020) and Dumont d'Urville (Huot et al., 2019) seas. Ice shelf melting projections were also produced for the Amundsen Sea under a high-end scenario by 2100 (Jourdain et al., 2022), and for all the Antarctic ice shelves under a high-end scenario by 2300 (Mathiot and Jourdain 2023).

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Thanks to the development of all these models, it was understood that melting under ice shelves is strongly influenced by changes in the shape of these shelves, which in turn is linked to the glacier dynamics (Little et al., 2009; De Rydt et al., 2014; Donat-Magnin et al., 2017). In addition, ice sheet modelers had great difficulties in prescribing melt rates from ocean models given that retreating grounding lines were exposing new ice–ocean interfaces. All this, in the context of the major changes observed in the Amundsen Sea, motivated the community to couple models of the ocean under ice shelves to ice sheet models.

Klaus Grosfeld and Henner Sandhäger (2004) coupled the ROMBAX ocean model to an ice shelf dynamics model, allowing the ice–ocean interface of a simplified shelf geometry to evolve. They then coupled it to the Revised Ice Model Based on frAnk pattYn (RIMBAY) and applied it to the Ronne-Filchner Ice Shelf (Thoma et al. 2015). Every 10 to 50 years, ROMBAX was reset with the new RIMBAY geometry, and after a few years of spin-up, ROMBAX was sending its melt rates to RIMBAY. This coupling method, discontinuous from the ocean's point of view, was then used in other models and for warm ice shelf cavities (Goldberg et al., 2012; DeRydt and Gudmundsson, 2016).

When they coupled the Z-coordinate Parallel Ocean Program (POP, Smith et al., 1992) to the BISICLES ice-sheet model developed by Stephen Cornford and others (2013), Xylar Asay-Davis and Daniel Martin developed a continuous approach. The method involved opening or closing ocean cells according to changes in geometry imposed by the ice sheet model, extrapolating neighbouring ocean properties where necessary. In order to avoid tsunamis and numerical instabilities resulting from abrupt changes in water column thickness, they corrected the ocean velocities in a way to preserve the barotropic transport (Martin et al., 2015). This approach was then used for other Z-coordinate models with coupling periods of a few months to a year (Favier et al., 2019; Naughten et al., 2021). Pierre Mathiot found that there were still

instabilities in NEMO with this method and proposed instead to preserve the divergence of the ocean transport when changing geometry. This was equivalent to adding or removing a certain volume of water when adjusting the geometry (Smith et al., 2021).

To avoid such instabilities, other groups chose to change the ice shelf thickness at shorter time steps. This meant allowing the geometry to modify the pressure gradients and generate the necessary advection, thus naturally conserving volume, salt and heat. This method was used in a Z-coordinate model by James Jordan and his colleagues (2018), solving the ice thickness equation at the ocean time step, and keeping a longer time step for solving the ice velocities. It was also used by Rupert Gladstone and his colleagues (2021) in a σ -coordinate model, calculating the thinning rate of the shelf in the ice sheet model and applying it to the ocean model at its time step. To simulate the ocean expansion in case of grounding line retreat, Daniel Goldberg and his colleagues (2018) introduced a passive film of water under the grounded ice, that becomes active when the ice floats. This method was inspired by coastal models simulating areas covered and uncovered by tides, and was subsequently used in other ocean–ice-sheet models (Zhao et al. 2022).

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These developments paved the way for the inclusion of an interactive Antarctic Ice Sheet in climate models. The scientific motivation was partly due to the difficulty of simulating the ice sheet mass loss using climate models that had not seen any ice shelf (Nowicki et al., 2020; Jourdain et al., 2020), and partly due to the lack of realistic freshwater fluxes from the Antarctic ice sheet to the ocean component of climate models. On the latter point, numerous studies showed that ice shelf melting had a greater or lesser effect on ocean stratification, with significant consequences for the evolution of sea ice (Bintanja et al., 2013; Swart and Fyfe 2013; Pauling et al., 2016; Merino et al., 2018), Antarctic bottom water formation (Menviel et al. 2010; Hansen et al. 2016; Li et al. 2023), Antarctic slope current (Moorman et al., 2020) and global climate (Bronselaeer et al., 2018; Purich and England, 2023).

Several groups included an interactive ice sheet for Greenland in climate models, neglecting interactions with the ocean (Barbi et al., 2014; Muntjewerf et al. 2021; Madsen et al. 2022). This approximation was not valid for Antarctica, which was therefore not included in these models. In spring 2024, UKESM remains the only global climate model to have incorporated both Greenland and Antarctica as interactive ice sheets, with explicit circulation of the ocean beneath ice shelves. This is the result of a national effort led by Robin Smith and numerous colleagues (2021) over approximately a decade.

Jun-Young Park, Sebastian Schloesser, Axel Timmermann and others (2024) developed a similar coupled model in a joint effort between Korea and Hawaii. They used a climate model of intermediate complexity, at very low resolution, in which ice shelf melting is parameterized without representing the ocean circulation under the ice. Thus, at different levels of complexity, some models are already able produce projections (Siahaan et al., 2022, Park et al., 2024). However, a number of challenges remain before these projections become plausible, namely initialisation, the representation of ice shelf melting at low resolution, and the damage and fragmentation of ice shelves (Rocha et al., 2022).

CHAPTER VIII

ICE SHELVES FROM OTHER ERAS AND PLACES

Là-bas jadis

In 1888, William Thomson, one of the pioneers of thermodynamics, postulated that if ocean circulation had ever stopped transporting heat to the Arctic Ocean, it would have been covered by a thick layer of ice. He expressed the hope that geomorphologists would look for evidence of such an ice cover. More than 80 years later, John Mercer (1970) drew an analogy with West Antarctica, and suggested that a large part of the Arctic Ocean may have been covered by ice shelves coming from the two great ice sheets that occupied northern Eurasia and North America at the last glacial maximum, just over 20,000 years ago.

Combined with a multitude of paleoclimatic and geomorphological indicators, as well as observations of the current isostatic rebound, the ice sheet models developed since the 1990s made it possible to understand that part of the Eurasian Ice Sheet laid below sea level. These marine parts occupied the present-day Barents and Kara Seas, to the north of present-day Russia, and the present-day British-Irish Isles. Numerical simulations (Gandy et al., 2018; van Aalderen et al., 2023) and geomorphological observations (Svendsen et al., 2004) suggest that ice shelves may have existed at the edge of these ice sheets.

The Baffin Sea, between the North American and the Greenland Ice Sheets, was also probably occupied by a large ice shelf during the last glacial maximum (Couette et al., 2022). Aurélien Quiquet and his colleagues (2021) also suggested the presence of ice shelves in proglacial lakes that formed to the south of the North American Ice Sheet as it was melting during the last deglaciation. They estimated that these lakes may have played a role in the ice sheet retreat, in a similar way as the marine ice sheet instability in West Antarctica but with an ice shelf thinning possibly driven by the atmosphere.

Martin Jakobsson and his colleagues (2010) showed that large ice shelves probably existed in the Arctic during the penultimate glacial period, 130 to 190 million years ago, but their geomorphological data did not support the hypothesis of a thick ice shelf covering the entire Arctic Ocean at that time or during the last glacial maximum.

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Today, only a few ice shelves remain in the Arctic: on Ellesmere Island at the northern tip of the Canadian territory of Nunavut; north of 77°N in Greenland; and in two archipelagos in the Russian High Arctic, near 80°N. They are all much smaller than the ice shelves of Antarctica.

In 1875, the British Arctic expedition led by George Nares sailed up the strait that would take his name, between Ellesmere Island and Greenland (Nares 1878). It was not known at the time that this strait had been covered by an ice shelf during the last deglaciation, around 9,000 years ago (Jenningset al., 2022). The expedition failed in its mission to reach the North Pole at a time

when it was thought that the Arctic Ocean might be largely free of sea ice, but it was the first to describe the ice shelves that still exist to the north of Ellesmere Island and Greenland.

The expedition first enabled Pelham Aldrich, with a few companions and sled dogs, to explore what would later be known as the Ellesmere Ice Shelf (Nares 1878). Robert Peary also travelled across this ice shelf by dog sled in 1906, calling it the "glacial fringe". Aerial observations in the late 1940s showed that parts of the ice shelf had disintegrated in the first half of the 20th century, suggesting that it may be the disappearing relic of a colder period (Koenig et al., 1952). Between 1906 and 1992, the ice shelf lost 90% of its surface area, giving way to several smaller ice shelves, some of which disappeared in the 2000s. By dating the remains of driftwood in fjords, John England and his colleagues (2008) showed that these ice shelf disappearances were unprecedented in the last 5,500 years, at a time when the region had experienced a relatively warm period (Briner et al., 2016).

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In spring 1876, after the wintering of the British Arctic Expedition, a party led by Reginald Fullford set out to explore the fjord where the Petermann Glacier terminates, to the north-west of Greenland. In his report, the ship surgeon Richard Copping described a wall of ice across the fjord (Nares 1878). From their camp, Fullford used his sextant to observe the tidal motions of the ice wall, highlighting what would later be called an ice shelf. Much later, in 1921, another dog-sled expedition, led by the Dane Lauge Koch and three Inuit companions, mapped the Petermann Glacier in greater detail (Münchow et al., 2016). They also identified three glaciers further east, which they named Steensby, Ryder and Ostenfeld, whose mapping suggested floating terminations and whose knowledge would be refined by aerial observations after the Second World War (Ahnert 1963).

Koch had also explored the Humboldt Glacier a little further south in 1911-12, where a narrow ice shelf would be described much later (Rignot et al., 2021). The young Koch had certainly been influenced by the tales of a cousin of his father, Johan Peter Koch, who had participated in the Danish expedition to Greenland between 1906 and 1908. This expedition had mapped other glacial fjords further east along the Greenland coast. One was named after Niels Hagen, who died of hunger and cold after describing it. Another was named *Nioghalyfjærd* ("79" in Danish), after the fjord location at 79°N, where the expedition leader Ludvig Mylius-Erichsen died shortly after Hagen. All of these glaciers, as well as those of Zachariæ, Storstrømmen and Bistrup, further south, have an ice shelf termination, as later shown by aerial then satellite observations (Hill et al., 2017). Between 1978 and 2022, the ice shelves in North Greenland lost 35% of their volume, and the Zachariæ, Ostenfeld and Hagen ice shelves disappeared almost entirely (Millan et al., 2023).

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Between 2002 and 2003, while the Ilulissat "Icefjord" was being nominated for UNESCO World Heritage status, a large part of the ice shelf at the end of the fjord disintegrated. The glacier that feeds it, on the west coast of Greenland and further south than those mentioned above, had long been called Jakobshavn, after the nearby market town, itself named after the Danish merchant who settled there in the 18th century. Following Greenland's independence in 1979, Jakobshavn was renamed *Ilulissat*, which in the Kalaallisut language means "icebergs",

produced in exceptional quantities by the nearby glacier. This glacier was later renamed *Sermeq Kujalleq*, the "south glacier". These sites have been occupied by a succession of peoples over thousands of years (Weidick et al., 2004).

By 1850, the Little Ice Age was coming to an end after more than five centuries of cooling, and the front of *Sermeq Kujalleq* was 35 km further offshore than in 2003. Between 1850 and 1950, the glacier front retreated and then stabilised for a few decades (Csatho et al., 2008), forming an ice shelf of about 15 km long (Echelmeyer et al., 1991). From 1998, the ice shelf experienced strong summer retreat until it disintegrated in 2003 (Joughin et al., 2008).

After that, the glacier front took the form of an ice cliff as high as 130 m above sea level, which reformed every few days between iceberg calving events. The cliff was examined to assess the plausibility of a Marine Ice Cliff Instability Mechanism (MICI, Pollard and DeConto, 2015), but it was difficult to find robust evidence for this mechanism (Joughin et al., 2020).

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On the other side of the Arctic, between the Kara and Laptev Seas, the Northern Land Archipelago (*Severnaya Zemlya*) remained off the maps until 1913. At that time, the Imperial Russian Navy sent two icebreakers on a mapping expedition led by Boris Vilkitsky. For a few years the archipelago was named after Tsar Nikolai II, but the October Revolution gave the central island its name and the archipelago was renamed *Severnaya Zemlya*. On this island was the Matusevich Ice Shelf, at the end of the eponym fjord, which was explored from land and then mapped from a Zeppelin airship in the 1930s. Aerial observations from the 1950s onwards, followed by satellite observations, allowed Russian researchers, notably Vladislav Koryakin (2014), and British researchers, notably Meredith Williams and Julian Dowdeswell (2001), to describe the floating part in more detail. The ice shelf experienced cycles of advance and retreat from the 1930s to the 1990s, but lost three-quarters of its surface area between 1995 and 2014.

The presence of small ice shelves in the Russian Franz Josef archipelago in the Barents Sea was also suggested by Dowdeswell (1994) on the basis of Landsat imagery. Satellite altimetry later enabled Whyjay Zheng and others (2018) to show that the glaciers terminating in these presumed ice shelves had experienced significant mass loss in 2000 and 2010.

In summary, all Arctic ice shelves have been undergoing profound changes since the beginning of the 21st century.

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Let's go back to West Antarctica and to the past. Robert Larer and his colleagues (2014) studied the nature and stratigraphy of sediments at the bottom of the Amundsen Sea. They were able to date the layers using carbon-14 from organic matter and rare calcareous microorganisms. They concluded that the entire Amundsen Sea, up to the continental slope, was occupied by the Antarctic Ice Sheet during the last glacial maximum. The ice sheet front then retreated between 20,000 and 10,000 years ago to a position close to the present day configuration. Alexandra Kirschner and her colleagues (2012) interpreted certain sedimentary deposits as evidence for the presence of ice shelves 12,000 to 10,000 years ago in the middle of today's Amundsen Sea.

Claus-Dieter Hillenbrand and others (2017) reconstructed the history of CDW intrusions into the Amundsen Sea from the chemical composition of the calcareous shells of foraminifers. Their analysis indicated that the presence of relatively warm CDW between 10,000 and 8,000 years ago could have caused a significant grounding line retreat, possibly related to the position of westerly winds. On the contrary, evidence of a weaker CDW presence between 7,500 and 1,200 years ago seemed consistent with other evidence of ice sheet stability in the Amundsen Sea between 5,500 years ago and the mid-20th century (Braddock et al., 2022).

Applied to more recent times, Hillenbrand's analyses indicated a weak presence of CDW in the Amundsen Sea since about 1850, with a transition to a stronger presence between the 1940s and 1960s. In the same year, James Smith and his colleagues showed that sedimentary deposits beneath Pine Island Ice Shelf indicated a grounding line retreat in the 1940s. In 2024, Rachel Clark and her colleagues found similar results for Thwaites. This confirmed the link to a strong El Niño event proposed by Eric Steig in 2012 based on modeling and continental ice core analyses in the region.

A similar deglaciation of the Amundsen Sea also occurred during the last interglacial period, the Eemian, between 130,000 and 115,000 years ago. During this period, the global temperature was about 0.5°C warmer than today, and the sea surface was 5 to 10 meters higher, suggesting that the marine ice sheet in West Antarctica was quite reduced compared to modern times. By analysing the genomes of a hundred small octopods from around Antarctica, Sally Lau and her colleagues (2023) were able to show that population mixing between the Ross, Amundsen, and Weddell Seas had stopped between 139,000 and 54,000 years ago. This indicated that the West Antarctic Ice Sheet had disappeared between these seas during the last interglacial. We can therefore imagine that, during short periods at least, ice shelves may have covered passages between these three seas.

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These alternating glacial and interglacial cycles were attributed to variations in the Earth orientation and distance from the Sun. Following the first accurate calculations of the Earth orbit by Johannes Kepler then Isaac Newton in the 17th century and numerous advances in mathematics in the following century, Pierre-Simon Laplace published his *Traité de Mécanique Céleste* in 1799, which included the calculation of perturbations of planetary orbits due to the presence of other planets. In 1843, the Frenchman Urbain Le Verrier published a formula giving the time evolution of the Earth eccentricity around the Sun. Three years later, similar calculations enabled him to predict the existence of the then-unknown Neptune from the orbits of the other known planets (Longair, 2021).

In 1875, the American James Croll published a theory explaining the ice ages on the basis of the eccentricity variations calculated by Le Verrier. He believed that the associated changes in insolation were not sufficient to explain the glaciations directly but postulated that climatic feedbacks, including the radiative effects of ice and clouds as well as the ocean circulation, could amplify the orbital effects. His theory aroused great interest in the scientific community, not the least from Charles Darwin, but it became obsolete in the following decades due to the lack of ice age dating at the time and because it only produced ice ages in one hemisphere (Fleming, 2006).

The Serbian Milutin Milankovitch (1941) refined Croll's orbital theory by taking into account variations in the obliquity of the Earth's axis of rotation and calculating the precise insolation at each terrestrial latitude. Beginning in the 1970s, the orbital theory became widely accepted as the only one able to explain the variations in paleoclimatic indices in marine and lake sediments over the past several hundred million years (Kerr 1987, Berger 1988). In particular, it explained the alternance of ice ages during the last 2.5 million years, the so-called Quaternary period.

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Shortly before joining Ernest Shackleton's 1907-1909 Antarctic expedition, Douglas Mawson became a lecturer in geology at the University of Adelaide in South Australia. His colleague Walter Howchin had just caused a controversy, widely reported in the local press, by identifying an ancient glaciation in the rock strata of the region, as far north as 6° below today's tropical belt. In the late 1940s, following in the footsteps of his mentor Edgeworth David and having learned of other evidence for glaciation in Africa, Mawson proposed a global glaciation to explain the presence of ice sheets at such latitudes (Sprigg 1986, Cooper 2010, Hoffman 2011a).

Mawson's argument was not really valid. He did not believe in the continental drift theory, which had just been revived by Alfred Wegener, and it was not until the late 1960s that a general consensus on plate tectonics was reached. Taking into account continental drift and the influence of latitude of rock formation on its magnetic properties, the British Walter Harland (1964) brought the possibility of global glaciation back to the fore. The American Joseph Kirschvink (1992) strengthened the evidence for the existence of global glaciations, which he called "Snowball Earth". He postulated that the end of these periods may have been triggered by a large accumulation of volcanic carbon dioxide in the atmosphere, which insulated oceanic and continental biology could no longer absorb. The global nature of these ice ages was later confirmed by the analysis of radioactive elements in rocks. Thus, over the past billion years, there were probably two periods of Snowball Earth, one between 646 and 636 million years ago and the other one between 717 and 659 million years ago (Hoffman et al., 2017).

The characteristics of certain sedimentary deposits from these eras were interpreted by Eugene Domack and Paul Hoffman (2011) as traces of ancient ice shelves close to their grounding line. Conceptually, a Snowball Earth implies a planetary ice shelf with a significant proportion of marine ice (Hoffman et al., 2017). The disappearance of some parts of the global ice shelf would then be an early indicator of the end of the global glaciation, with a possible positive feedback mechanism as the global ice shelf would no longer buttress ice sheet flows.

This kind of snowball exists today, but further out in the solar system. Europa, one of Jupiter's four moons, was observed by Galileo as early as 1610. Various American space programs sent probes to Jupiter from the 1970s onwards, giving more insights into the structure of its moons. Europa is probably covered by a planetary ice shelf: several tens of kilometres of water ice above an ocean of liquid water (Kivelson et al., 2000). Nevertheless, the very low ice temperature and great ice thickness likely make the ice dynamics closer to the Earth's crust than to Antarctic ice shelves.

Third part

Report on the work carried out at LGGE/IGE

*Modelling the interactions between the Antarctic ice sheet
and the climate system*

This part is dedicated to “Les Plateformistes” with whom it is such a great pleasure to work.

CHAPTER IX

WORK CONTEXT: PROJECTS OVERVIEW

Unie dans la diversité

I was recruited as a CNRS researcher at the *Laboratoire de Glaciologie et Géophysique de l'Environnement* (LGGE) in October 2013 to work on the modelling of the Antarctic Ice Sheet and its connections with the climate system. I only really started working on this topic in 2015, after a 1-year additional visit at UNSW Sydney and 2-month field work in Antarctica. LGGE merged with the hydrology lab of Grenoble (LTHE) in 2017 to become the *Institut des Géosciences de l'Environnement* (IGE). IGE now hosts about 300 people, and I work in a team that focuses on the ice sheet and mountain glacier dynamics, and on their interfaces with the climate system, through modelling, field work and remote sensing. I have strong collaborations with other teams working on atmosphere and ocean processes. These internal collaborations appeared in my first project to be funded at IGE: the ANR TROIS-AS project (2015-2020).

In France, I contribute to reinforce the links between IGE and both IPSL and CNRM, mostly on the topic of modelling ice-sheet–climate interactions. This took the form of several projects:

- ANR-EIS (2020-2023) aimed to develop Elmer/Ice as an ice sheet model.
- ANR-AIAI (2023-2027) aims to improve the integration of an ice sheet model into the IPSL climate model through the use of neural networks.
- PEPR TRACCS (2023-2033) is a large program (51 M€) designed to boost the climate models in France; my contributions are related to icebergs and ice sheets.

At the international level, I was significantly involved in ISMIP6, the Ice Sheet Model Intercomparison Project for CMIP6, for which I developed an ocean forcing protocol (Nowicki et al., 2020; Jourdain et al., 2020), and I am now co-lead of the ocean-focus group for ISMIP7. The ISMIP6 work was the primary source for sea level projections in the 6th IPCC Assessment Report, and ISMIP7 is part of the fast-track MIPs for CMIP7.

I have also participated in the first phase of the Marine Ice Sheet Intercomparison Project (MISOMIP, Asay-Davis et al., 2016), which aims to develop and verify models rather than provide projections, and I am co-leading the second phase (MISOMIP2), which was launched in early 2024 after several years of preparation (De Rydt, Jourdain, et al., 2024).

Many of my interesting collaborations since 2019 have happened thanks to 5 European projects that I contributed to write, organise and implement:

- OCEAN:ICE (2022-2026) supports new observations in Antarctica and related model developments (including improved iceberg and ice shelf modules).
- ESM2025 (2021-2025) supports the developments of the next generation of Earth System Models (including interactive ice sheets).
- CRiceS (2021-2025) supports observational and modelling work on sea ice, aerosols, and their feedbacks with other components of the climate system.
- PROTECT (2020-2024) supports the developments of the series of models used to predict the contribution of the cryosphere to sea level rise.
- TiPACCs (2019-2023) supported the investigations of possible ocean and ice sheet tipping points in Antarctica.

Table 1 – Summary of the main projects and how I contributed.

Acronym	funding	Duration	Role	Partners/community involved
TRACCS (PC7)	PEPR (Fr)	2023-2031	proposal, co-lead	CNRM, IGE, IPSL (LMD, LOCEAN, LSCE)
TRACCS (PC9)	PEPR (Fr)	2023-2031	proposal, SSC*, WP lead	IGE, CNRM, IPSL (LSCE, LOCEAN)
AIAI	ANR (Fr)	2023-2027	proposal, main lead	IGE, IPSL (LSCE, LOCEAN)
OCEAN:ICE	Horizon Europe	2022-2026	proposal, SSC*, WP lead	Observation and modelling of the Southern Ocean and Cryosphere
ESM2025	EU H2020	2021-2025	proposal, WP lead	Earth system modelling
CRiceS	EU H2020	2021-2025	participant (1 deliverable)	Climate, sea ice, aerosols (Arctic & Antarctic)
PROTECT	EU H2020	2020-2024	proposal, SSC*, WP lead	Cryosphere and sea-level modelling
EIS	ANR (Fr)	2020-2023	participant	IGE, IPSL-LSCE, CNRM
TiPACCs	EU H2020	2019-2023	DMP*, participant (3 deliverables)	Southern Ocean and Cryosphere modelling
TROIS AS	ANR (Fr)	2015-2020	proposal, main lead	LGGE/IGE

*SSC: participation to weekly or by-weekly meetings of the Scientific Steering Committee.

* DMP: in charge of the Data Management Plan.

CHAPTER X

WORK CONTEXT: SUPERVISIONS OVERVIEW

Les Plateformistes

In terms of supervision, there have been two periods of activity since I was hired at CNRS: the TROIS-AS period (my first ANR project) from 2015 to 2019, and the *Plateformistes* period, as we call the informal group working on ice shelves that I coordinate at IGE.

The TROIS-AS project focused on modelling climate–ice-sheet interactions in the Amundsen Sea. During this project, I supervised Marion Donat-Magnin's PhD thesis on melting at the base and surface of ice shelves (3 articles), while the work of Lionel Favier (postdoc) and Nacho Merino (engineer) enabled progress on coupling the NEMO and Elmer/Ice models (1 article). I also supervised Amine Drira (engineer) on various aspects aiming to make the MAR model more community based. Marion is now working in agrotourism, Lionel in scientific dissemination, while Nacho and Amine have moved to private companies.

From 2020, the success of several European and French projects allowed me to develop a working group focusing on ice shelves and more generally on climate–ice-sheet interactions. This started with the recruitment of Pierre Mathiot, a postdoctoral researcher in the TiPACCs project from 2020 to 2023. Pierre came with an internationally recognised expertise in the development of NEMO, and was able to further develop his expertise at IGE. He improved the global NEMO configuration to 0.25° (1 paper) and developed the NEMO-Elmer/Ice coupling at the scale of Antarctica (paper in preparation). He now works as an engineer on an 8-year contract for TRACCS-PC9 at IGE, and he leads the European NEMO Developers Committee.

Clara Burgard worked as a postdoc in the PROTECT European project and then in the DEEP-MELT project (funded by University Grenoble-Alpes) from 2020 to 2023. She first improved the calibration and assessment of basal ice shelf melting parameterisations (1 paper). Clara then used neural networks to propose more reliable parameterisations (1 article). This led to the creation of the AIAI French project, which started in 2023. Clara is currently employed as a researcher on a 7-year permanent contract in TRACCS-PC7 at LOCEAN. From June 2024, Clara and I will be co-supervising Helen Ockenden, a postdoc at IGE in the ANR AIAI project.

From December 2020 to June 2024, I supervised Justine Caillet's PhD which was funded by the ANR EIS project. Justine first analysed the mechanisms making the Amundsen Sea shift from a cold regime under pre-industrial conditions to a warm regime under present-day conditions (1 article). After characterising the impact of internal climate variability on projections of Antarctica's contribution to sea level rise (1 paper in review), she is now working on reconstructing the ice sheet mass loss since 1850 in order to propose a way to detect the anthropogenic part of the signal.

I then supervised Christoph Kittel, a postdoc in the CRiceS European project from 2022 to 2024. Christoph is working on how various sources of freshwater from Antarctica influence the Southern Ocean (1 paper in preparation). He is also reactivating and improving the ocean–sea-ice–atmosphere coupling consisting of MAR, NEMO and OASIS, for applications at the

Antarctic scale. Since March 2024, Christoph has been continuing his research at the University of Liège, where he has been awarded an FNRS project.

I also co-supervised (with Olivier Gagliardini and then Gaël Durand) Cyrille Mosbeux, a postdoc in the PROTECT and TiPACCs European projects, from 2021 to 2024. Cyrille worked on a high-resolution Elmer/Ice configuration in the Amundsen region and developed the damage parameterisation and its semi-Lagrangian advection to predict the worst possible scenarios in the coming decades (relevant information for sea level rise protection). Cyrille will continue as an engineer in TRACCS-PC9 at IGE for 7 years.

Since May 2023, I have been co-supervising (with Pierre Mathiot) Lucas Bastien, engineer in the ESM2025 European project. Lucas is in charge of the Elmer/Ice configuration of Greenland and of the development of the atmosphere–ice-sheet coupling within the IPSL-CM climate model.

Since June 2023, I have been co-supervising (with Pierre Mathiot) Anna Olivé Abello, a postdoc in the OCEAN:ICE European project. Anna is working on the Lagrangian iceberg module in NEMO, and has been revisiting the way in which their thickness is distributed geographically and across a finite number of categories. A follow-up to this work is planned in TRACCS-PC7.

Since October 2023, I have been co-supervising (with Pierre Mathiot) Antoine Nasser as a postdoc in the ESM2025 European project. Antoine is developing a volume penalisation method in NEMO. The aim of this postdoc is to represent the ocean–ice-shelf interface in a much smoother way than is normally possible using Z-coordinates.

I also hosted Dorothee Vallot, visiting postdoc from SMHI, Sweden, in 2021-2023. We worked on the influence of ice shelf roughness on the ocean–ice-shelf interactions.

Fig. 3 – “Les Plateformistes” in January 2024. From left to right: Cyrille Mosbeux, Christoph Kittel, Justine Caillet, Nicolas Jourdain, Clara Burgard, Pierre Mathiot, Dorothee Vallot, Lucas Bastien, Anna Olivé Abello, and Antoine Nasser.

CHAPTER XI

RESULTS: ANTARCTIC CONTRIBUTION TO SEA LEVEL RISE

Jusqu'à la ceinture

I participated in the design of the ISMIP6 protocol (Nowicki et al., 2020), in particular by proposing a way to derive ice shelf basal melting from the CMIP projections (Jourdain et al., 2020). The results of 18 Antarctic ice sheet simulations carried out by 15 international groups are presented in two papers, one for CMIP5 (Seroussi et al., 2020) and the other for CMIP6 (Payne et al., 2021). The Antarctic contribution in response to increased warming from 2005 to 2100 varies between -7.8 and +30.0 cm of global mean sea level, depending on the climate model, the ice sheet model and the chosen melting parameterisation and its calibration. The novelty of these projections was that they were closely linked to the projections of a selection of CMIP models (Barthel et al. 2020).

These projections were then emulated using Gaussian processes to provide more complete probabilities of Antarctica's contribution to sea level for different global warming trajectories (Edwards et al. 2021, Fig. 4), and then to identify the main sources of uncertainty (Séroussi et al. 2023). They provided input to the sea level projections presented in the latest 6th IPCC assessment report (Fox-Kemper et al., 2021). In the PROTECT European project, we have repeated a similar series of multi-model ice sheet simulations followed by statistical emulation, focusing on the time scales most relevant to society (Durand et al., 2022), integrating more processes as sources of uncertainty (publications in preparation), and using emulating regional atmospheric models to obtain surface conditions (Jourdain et al., in review).

No ocean model was used directly to project melting beneath ice shelves in ISMIP6. In fact, there is no representation of ocean circulation beneath ice shelves in the CMIP5 or CMIP6 models. Standalone ocean projections forced by CMIP5 or CMIP6 projections had begun to emerge when we designed the ISMIP6 protocol (e.g., Naughten et al. 2018), but from a single model (FESOM) and with substantial present-day biases in the critical Amundsen Sea region. In addition, standalone ocean models generally have static ice shelf geometry, making it difficult to extrapolate ocean conditions to an ice sheet model that updates the geometry. Finally, the deadlines for ISMIP6 and CMIP6 were too short to develop new ocean simulations.

To address these problems, I worked in three directions: (1) improving the ice shelf basal melt parameterisations that allow CMIP simulations to be linked to ice sheet models, (2) proposing ice shelf basal melt projections based on explicit simulations of the ocean circulation beneath ice shelves, and (3) implementing an interactive ice sheet in a climate model. The last point is presented in the next chapter.

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The ice shelf basal melt parameterisation proposed as standard in ISMIP6 (Jourdain et al. 2020) is the one that we had proposed and evaluated using idealised coupled ocean–ice-sheet simulations (Favier et al., 2019). It was based on the quadratic dependency to the thermal

forcing (Holland 2008), but its originality was the dependency on both local and ice-shelf-averaged thermal forcing, to account for the melt-induced circulation at the cavity scale (Jourdain et al., 2017). However, the transition from the idealised configuration to the whole ice sheet gave highly biased melt rates and required regional corrections to ocean temperatures and a rather wide range of parameterisation calibrations to be considered (Fig. 4c). As a result, the uncertainty on melt rates in ISMIP6 is about a factor of 10, leading to large uncertainties in sea level projections (Seroussi et al., 2020, 2023).

Fig. 4 - (a) Probability distributions of global mean surface air temperature change from 2015 to 2100 under five SSPs. **(b)** Distribution of parameter (κ) of Greenland ice front retreat. **(c)** Distribution of parameter (γ) of the Antarctic quadratic basal melt parameterisation. **(d)** Projected contribution of continental ice to sea level (in cm of equivalent sea level) from 2015 to 2100 under five SSPs. Solid lines and shaded areas: median and 5th-95th percentiles; five-year smoothing applied, with original data represented by dots. Light solid lines: 95th percentiles of low-risk projections. Boxes and whiskers indicate the [5, 25, 50, 75, 95]th percentiles at 2100 for the main projections (left) and the reduced-risk projections for Antarctica (right). Extracted from Edwards et al (2021).

In this context, I wrote a task in the PROTECT European project to improve melt parameterisations, and Clara Burgard was hired as a postdoc on this task. First, we evaluated five main families of ice shelf melt parameterisations and proposed a calibration of the parameters based on a series of NEMO simulations. The paper summarising this work (Burgard et al., 2022) now serves as a reference on parameterisations in the ice sheet modelling community. Clara then developed melt parameterisations based on neural networks trained on NEMO simulations with promising results (Burgard et al., 2023). On an independent ensemble of simulations that was produced with the same ocean model but with different model

parameters, cavity geometries and forcing, the neural network yields similar results to traditional parameterisations in present-day conditions. In much warmer conditions, both traditional parameterisations and neural networks struggle, but the neural networks tend to produce basal melt rates closer to the reference than a majority of traditional parameterisations.

We have also carried out a series of melt projections for the Amundsen Sector using a $1/12^\circ$ NEMO regional configuration (Jourdain et al., 2022) forced by atmospheric projections from the MAR atmospheric model (Donat-Magnin et al., 2021). These simulations were used to evaluate the ability of simple parameterisations to capture the melt response to ocean warming. The results suggest that the upper part of the ISMIP6 melt rates interval was unrealistically high and call for revisiting the calibration methods in ISMIP7. These high melt rates were used in the “risk-averse” projections of Edwards et al. (2021) shown in Fig. 4d.

CHAPTER XII

RESULTS: SIMULATING INTERACTIVE ICE SHEETS IN CLIMATE MODELS

Tango 3.0

For the last five years, part of my work has been to motivate the climate modelling community to include interactive ice sheets in their models. I have based my conviction of this need on international publications, of course, but also on a number of results obtained at IGE.

In [Spence et al. \(2014\)](#), we had shown that the southward shift of westerly winds in a warmer climate increases the presence of warm water on the continental shelf all around Antarctica. During Marion Donat-Magnin's PhD, we repeated Spence's scenarios for the Amundsen region, but in the presence of interactions with ice shelves. Our ocean simulations showed coastal cooling rather than warming, demonstrating the importance of simulating interactive melting in the climate models used to constrain ice dynamics simulations ([Donat-Magnin et al., 2017](#)).

Next came the question of the need for an ice sheet dynamical model. Under steady-state climatic conditions, the Antarctic ice sheet is static: the ice flow balances surface accumulation, iceberg calving and ice shelf melting. For an ice shelf, this means that ice melted by the ocean is almost immediately replaced by ice advection, or that the annual surface accumulation is almost immediately removed by ice advection. Such a steady-state regime may be a good approximation for the pre-industrial era in Antarctica, but satellite estimates for 1997-2021 show that of the 162 major ice shelves in Antarctica, 71 have lost mass, 29 have gained mass and 62 have not evolved significantly ([Davison et al., 2023](#)).

By prescribing significantly thinner ice shelves in the Amundsen Sea and a retreated grounding line from an ice sheet projection, we highlighted a positive feedback mechanism between melting and changes in ice shelf geometry at the scale of one to two centuries. A retreating grounding line exposes more ice to the warm water at depth, which intensifies the circulation under the whole ice shelf, generating more turbulent exchange with the ice and therefore more melting ([Donat-Magnin et al., 2017](#)). [De Rydt and Naughten \(2024\)](#) made a more general analyses and found situations with either suppression or amplification of melt rates by geometrical changes. This shows the difficulty of making reliable melt projections without an interactive ice sheet. This need also exists from the perspective of an ice sheet model as it is difficult to prescribe melt rates calculated with a steady grounding line in an ice sheet simulation where the grounding line is constantly moving.

The above arguments focus mainly on sea level prediction, and it will certainly take more than that to motivate a climate modelling centre to add a new component. Ice sheets are not as critical to the global climate as the ocean circulation or clouds, but numerous studies have highlighted the significant impact of melting ice shelves and icebergs on the ocean stratification, with important consequences for the evolution of sea ice ([Bintanja et al, 2013](#); [Swart and Fyfe 2013](#); [Merino et al., 2016, 2018](#)), Antarctic bottom water formation ([Hutchinson et al., 2023](#); [Li et al., 2023](#)), ocean currents around Antarctica ([Moorman et al., 2020](#)) and global climate ([Bronseleer et al., 2018](#); [Purich and England, 2023](#)).

All this motivated a number of groups to move towards the integration of ice sheet models into their climate models. To date, the only CMIP-type model that has integrated interactive ice sheets for Greenland and Antarctica is UKESM (Smith et al., 2021; Siahann et al., 2022). The Greenland ice sheet (without ocean interaction) is represented in some versions of the global models CESM2 (Muntjewerf et al., 2021) and EC-EARTH (Dösher et al., 2022). At IGE, we have developed the coupling between NEMO (ocean) and Elmer/Ice (ice sheet) (Favier et al., 2019; Mathiot et al., in prep.), and we are working on the coupling with the atmospheric component of IPSL-CM7 (Fig. 5) as part of the ESM2025 project. The coupling work is also continuing in the PEPR TRACCS and ANR AIAI projects.

Fig. 5 – Coupling scheme for Elmer/Ice in IPSL-CM (left). Elmer/Ice non-structured mesh in its Antarctic configuration (right).

CHAPTER XIII

RESULTS: ANTARCTIC TIPPING POINTS

Southern dominoes

Whether or not the tipping point concept is useful to motivate climate action (Kopp et al., 2024), it is now widely used in the scientific literature. In their Global Tipping Point Report, Lenton et al. (2023) define a tipping point as occurring when change in part of a system becomes self-sustained beyond a threshold, leading to substantial, widespread, frequently abrupt and often irreversible impact. This is generally related to the existence of multiple stable states. A tipping system can exhibit hysteresis when multiple stable states are found under a given external forcing due the dependence on the forcing history. This may lead to irreversible transitions in a range of external perturbations, i.e., reversing the external forcing after a transition does not make the system go back to its initial state.

Since the 2000s, theory, simulations and, to some extent, observations have brought evidence that the Antarctic Ice Sheet may be unstable in some conditions (see Pattyn's 2019 review). This is known as the Marine Ice Sheet Instability, where the thinning of an ice shelf may cross a threshold, an ice sheet tipping point, beyond which a large volume of grounded ice is irreversibly lost (i.e., reversing the forcing is not enough to make the ice sheet grow back to its initial mass). Based on ocean simulations of the Weddell Sea and the Ronne-Filchner Ice Shelf, Hellmer et al. (2012, 2017) identified an oceanic tipping point beyond which the intrusion of warm water beneath the ice shelf would be irreversible due to the self-sustained circulation induced by higher melting. The potential domino effect between the ocean and ice sheet tipping points motivated the TiPACCs European project.

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As the Amundsen Sea is relatively warm compared to the Weddell Sea, with seafloor temperatures on the continental shelf 2 to 4°C above the freezing point, we hypothesised that an oceanic tipping point similar to the one described by Hellmer et al. (2012, 2017) may have been crossed in the past. Justine Caillet started her PhD thesis by exploring this hypothesis. As we have no oceanographic observations prior to 1994 in this region, we opted for a modelling approach. And since atmospheric reanalyses are very unreliable in Antarctica before 1979 (Marshall et al., 2022), we chose to impose idealised perturbations corresponding to what would be expected in a colder climate, i.e., colder surface temperatures, less precipitation and westerly winds over the Southern Ocean shifted northwards.

These simulations, presented in [Caillet et al. \(2023\)](#), suggest that the Amundsen Sea may have been relatively cold (intermittently at the surface freezing point) under pre-industrial conditions, with a transition to a warm state close to present-day conditions for moderate global warming. Such a transition represents a clear regime shift, although it appears to be reversible. In this case, and whatever the type of forcing perturbation, the external control parameter was the surface buoyancy flux over the continental shelf (**Fig. 5**), which was not expected based on previous work. The mechanisms will be described in the next chapter.

Fig. 5 - Mean melt rate beneath the Amundsen Sea ice shelves as a function of the perturbation in surface buoyancy flux caused by (i) a change in surface air temperature (TEMP, green), (ii) a change in precipitation (PREC, blue), and (iii) a north-south shift in westerly winds (WIND, purple). The black star indicates current conditions, and the red star indicates the combined effect of the three disturbances expected in a climate 0.5°C colder than today. Adapted from *Caillet et al (2023)*.

There is evidence of ice sheet stability in the Amundsen Sea between 5,500 years ago and the mid-20th century (Braddock et al., 2022), and Adrian Jenkins questioned the fact that a relatively closed bay such as the Pine Island Bay could remain free of ice shelves with an ocean close to the surface freezing point because such a thermal and geomorphological situation is not currently observed elsewhere in Antarctica (personal communication). I would speculate that the presence of CDW between 10,000 and 8,000 years ago (Hillenbrand et al., 2017) may have removed ice shelves in Pine Island Bay, while the weaker or intermittent presence of CDW from 7,500 years ago to the mid-20th century have kept the ice shelves in an approximate steady state, with relatively small fluctuations in the grounding line position.

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In a much warmer climate than today, all Antarctic ice shelves could transition to a regime of strong melting, as shown in *Mathiot and Jourdain (2023)*. These results were obtained for physically plausible but high-end and low-probability conditions, corresponding to year 2300 in the SSP5-8.5 scenario. Ice shelf basal melt rates are increased by an order of magnitude under all ice shelves (**Fig. 6**), leaving little hope for their survival. The results of ISMIP6-2300, which are currently being analysed, confirm the disappearance of most ice shelves in an SSP5-8.5 scenario by 2300 (*Séroussi et al., in preparation*).

Similar work with the NEMO-Elmer/Ice coupling shows that such warming causes irreversible grounding line retreat, but the change in oceanic regime remains reversible (*Mathiot et al., in preparation*). On the reversibility, it should be noted that strong perturbations may switch the system from one side of a hysteresis to the other, thereby avoiding bi-stable regimes.

Identifying all possible bi-stable regimes and hysteresis would have required a large number of smaller perturbations or a slowly ramping perturbation. This is computationally prohibitive for ocean simulations but has been done for ice sheet simulations (Garbe et al., 2020).

Fig. 6 – (a-d) Sea floor temperature (°C) and ice shelf basal melt rates (metres per year) under plausible conditions for 2300 in the SSP5-8.5 scenario. (e) Integrated melt under the main Antarctic shelves today (blue, “REF”) and in 2300-SSP5-8.5 (red, “PERT”), in gigatons per year (Gt/yr). From Mathiot and Jourdain (2023).

CHAPTER XIV

RESULTS: MECHANISMS FOR WARM WATER INTRUSION INTO THE AMUNDSEN SEA

The shrieking sixties and melting seventies

Zonal wind at the continental shelf has been shown to modulate the inflow of circumpolar warm water (CDW) towards the Amundsen ice shelves on interannual scales (Thoma et al., 2008). This is connected to intertropical variability: convection anomalies in the central equatorial Pacific generate atmospheric Rossby waves that propagate southeast towards the Amundsen Sea, affecting the winds over continental shelf break and hence the inflow of warm water onto the continental shelf (Steig et al., 2012; Holland et al., 2019). The processes through which wind variations change the intrusions of CDW onto the continental shelf is complex and still a matter of research. I here present an overview of the main mechanisms at play.

First of all, there is the Ekman dynamics, whereby easterly winds push surface water southward due to the Coriolis force, which is compensated by a northward flow at depth (**Fig. 8a-b**). Convergence of surface water increases sea surface height and induces downwelling on the continental shelf. The sloping sea surface then generates a pressure gradient which gives rise to westward surface current in geostrophic balance, which is referred to as the Antarctic Slope Current. If the ocean is not stratified in density, the pressure gradient is vertically uniform and so is the westward current (**Fig. 8a**). In contrast, sloping isopycnals above a given depth modify the pressure gradient at that depth, which may compensate the influence of sloping sea surface and generate an eastward current near the sea floor at the shelf break (**Fig. 8b**). An eastward current at the shelf break can also result from regional cyclonic winds, like the Amundsen Sea Low, which invert the usual westerlies/easterlies wind system (**Fig. 8c**).

An eastward undercurrent along the shelf break is prone to CDW intrusions first because bottom friction induces a southward (upslope) Ekman transport at depth (**Fig. 7a**). In addition, if the zonal flow meets a north-south bathymetric channel across the continental shelf, the deeper layer undergoes “vortex stretching”, i.e., the conservation of potential vorticity induces a cyclonic circulation (**Fig. 7b**; St Laurent et al., 2013). The latter favours the intrusion of eastward under-currents into the bathymetric channels that often reach ice shelf cavities (Assmann et al., 2013; Kimura et al., 2017; Silvano et al., 2022).

Fig. 7 – Sketch of the main mechanisms favouring the CDW intrusion onto the continental shelf. The thin grey lines are the isobaths, the orange arrows are forces, and currents are in pink.

Fig. 8 – Typical structures of currents at the shelf break in the Amundsen Sea. All panels show a vertical north-south cross section. The zonal winds are shown in green, the main zonal currents at the shelf break are shown in black and the orange arrows represent the two forces involved in the geostrophic balance: the pressure gradient and Coriolis forces. The layers of different colours are the isopycnals (density increasing downward), with indicative temperature from cold (blue) to warm (red).

(a) Fresh Shelf: Easterly wind is prevailing over the continental shelf, leading to southward Ekman transport at the surface and thereby higher sea surface and downwelling on the continental shelf; sea surface height (SSH) gradient induces a westward flow, the **Antarctic Slope Current (ASC)**, which has a barotropic structure in the absence of stratification. The westward flow along the shelf break is unfavourable to an upward flow onto the shelf. If enough sea ice production occurs on the shelf, the fresh shelf turns into a “dense shelf” (not shown), with a dense cold overflow downward along the continental slope. Inspired from Thompson et al. (2018) and Spence et al. (2014).

(b) Warm Shelf (type A): Compared to (a), the easterlies over the shelf break are weaker and/or the wind system is shifted southward, and external circulation (e.g., ACC) and topography favour a large volume of CDW in front of the shelf break; a small SSH gradient still produces a westward ASC at the surface, but the pressure force associated with the vertically-integrated density gradients go against the effects of SSH, and the flow reverts at depth, which is referred to as the **Eastward undercurrent**. The eastward flow along the shelf break is favourable to an upward flow of CDW onto the shelf. Inspired from Caillet et al. (2023) and from Alban Planchat’s Master thesis at IGE.

(c) Warm Shelf (type B): Similar to (b) but with a different regional circulation and background stratification leading to an eastward current all over the shelf break. This typically occurs for some configurations of the Amundsen Sea Low. The eastward flow at depth is more on the shelf that right at the shelf break, but this is still favourable to an inflow of CDW onto the shelf. Inspired from Mathiot and Jourdain (2023), Moorman et al. (2020) and Thompson et al. (2018).

(d) Warm-Fresh Shelf: Much warmer situation with strong westerlies close to the shelf break, a lot of freshwater released by the Antarctic ice sheet and no more sea ice formation. Here, the cancellation of the westward flow at depth enables CDW to penetrate onto the shelf. Inspired from Mathiot and Jourdain (2023).

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In 2014, I contributed to an Australian study based on the MOM model (Spence et al., 2014). We imposed a southward shift of the westerlies/easterlies wind system, which is what the CMIP models predict in a warmer climate. This basically tends to make fresh shelves (Fig. 8a) evolve to type A warm shelves (Fig. 8b) due to a change in the Ekman dynamics and resulting modifications of the density gradients. This favours CDW intrusions and warms the continental shelf all around Antarctica.

During Marion Donat-Magnin's PhD, we repeated Spence's protocol using NEMO, with the novelty of simulating the interactions with the Amundsen ice shelves. The results showed a completely different story, demonstrating that wind alone is not sufficient to predict the warming of the Amundsen Sea and highlighting feedbacks with ice shelf melting (Donat-Magnin et al., 2017). This was generalised in Jourdain et al. (2017) where we showed that most of the circulation under the Amundsen Sea ice shelves and along their front is generated by ice shelf melting and its effect on density gradients and hence the geostrophic circulation (Jourdain et al., 2017).

Looking back, we can complete the explanation as follows: starting from a warm shelf (Fig. 8b,c) ice shelf melting freshens the upper part of the ocean, deepening the isopycnals southward on the continental shelf, which favours an eastward flow at the shelf break, and therefore CDW intrusions. The stronger stratification also prevents deep convection during sea ice production, which also favours the presence of CDW on the continental shelf.

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At the beginning of Justine Caillet's thesis, we re-examined the mechanisms by which multi-decadal atmospheric disturbances lead to changes in ice shelf basal melting (Caillet et al., 2023). Our results suggest that the ocean response is explained by changes in buoyancy fluxes, regardless of whether wind stress, precipitation or air temperature are perturbed (Fig. 5). Changes in wind stress and air temperature affect sea ice production and therefore modulate deep convection. Changes in precipitation affect the vertical density stratification and thereby the convection depth for a given sea ice production. Whatever the main contributor, surface buoyancy fluxes in warmer-climate conditions tend to tilt the isopycnals in a way that favours an eastward undercurrent and therefore CDW intrusions (Fig. 8), and vice versa in colder-climate conditions.

The impact of buoyancy fluxes was overlooked before our study, and this has motivated further work, in particular the complementary study of Haigh and Holland (2024) who showed the impact of surface buoyancy fluxes north of the shelf break. Changes in the circulation outside Amundsen, including the extent of the Ross Gyre, in warmer climates are also responsible for increased melting in warmer climates (Jourdain et al., 2022; Gómez-Valdivia et al., 2023; Mathiot and Jourdain 2023). Even in present-day climate, the Ross Gyre is responsible for the southward deflection of a branch of the Antarctic Circumpolar Current, bringing a thick CDW layer in front of the continental shelf (Fig. 8b). In much warmer climate, the Amundsen Sea would have characteristics of both warm and fresh continental shelves (Fig. 8d; Mathiot and Jourdain, 2023).

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Tides are another important driver of ice shelf basal melt rates at higher frequencies, and they have an effect on the mean state. Tides affect the ocean properties in front of ice shelves through vertical mixing due to the vertical shear of barotropic tides or the breaking of internal waves generated by tides, and through tidal residual circulation (**Fig. 9**). They also directly increase the vertical shear in the top ocean boundary layer beneath ice shelves, which favours upward heat transfer and therefore melting. This tide-induced melt also generates a residual circulation.

Modelling results presented in Jourdain et al. (2019) show that tides enhance ice shelf melting, with weakest effects for Pine Island and Thwaites (< +10%) and strongest effects for Dotson, Cosgrove and Abbot (> +30%). In Hausmann et al. (2020), we also describe a strong effect in the Weddell Sea, where approximately a third of ice shelf melting is attributed to tides. The effect is even more important in the Dumont d’Urville Sea, East Antarctica (Huot et al., 2019).

In the Amundsen Sea, the dominant process is increased vertical shear beneath the ice shelf, so we developed a parameterisation of this effect in the melt equations of NEMO, for models that do not represent explicit tides (Jourdain et al., 2019). This parameterisation gives very good results in the Amundsen Sea and we were confident that it could be applied all around Antarctica. However, recent unpublished simulations by Pierre Mathiot indicate that the parameterisation fails to produce a strong tidal effect under Ronne-Filchner. I now think that vertical tidal mixing and possibly the residual tidal circulation have an important effect in the Weddell Sea, which was also pointed out by Richter et al. (2022) using another model.

Fig. 9 – Main processes through which tides influence ice shelf basal melting.

CHAPTER XV

RESULTS: SURFACE PROCESSES THAT THREATEN ICE SHELVES

Quand les plateformes s'en vont à vau-l'eau

My contributions presented so far focused on the ocean, which is generally considered as the main threat to the Antarctic Ice Sheet stability. However, most ice shelf collapses so far have occurred in the Antarctic Peninsula region. They have been explained by the relatively warm surface conditions in the least southerly part of Antarctica. These collapses occurred in the 1990s and early 2000s and have generally been attributed to a slow weakening of ice shelves due to increased ocean melt and ice damage, followed by sudden hydrofracturing caused by meltwater pressure in the crevasses. In ISMIP6, ice shelf collapse by hydrofracturing was considered in a very simple way, by considering a threshold in surface melt rates, at the value estimated from observations on Larsen B before its collapse in 2002 (Nowicki et al., 2020).

In order to quantify this collapse potential more precisely, we have developed a regional configuration of the MAR atmosphere and snow model with a resolution of 10 km as part of Marion Donat-Magnin's PhD and in collaboration with the University of Liège. Projections based on this model show that the potential for hydro-fracturing is controlled by the melt to snowfall ratio, because a large part of the meltwater refreezes in the snowpack during the following winter (Donat-Magnin et al., 2020; 2021).

At the Antarctic scale, meltwater is projected to saturate the firm of many ice shelves around 2100 in the RCP8.5 or SSP5-8.5 scenarios (Kittel et al., 2021), but some ice shelves in the Amundsen Sea sector may remain protected from hydro-fracturing late in the 21st century due to heavy snowfall (Donat-Magnin et al., 2021). In a more recent study, we emulated other MAR projections at the scale of Antarctica to estimate the conditions under which firm becomes saturated with liquid water and therefore prone to hydro-fracturing if mechanical conditions are also favourable (Fig. 10). A majority of ice shelves could remain safe from hydro-fracturing under the SSP1-2.6 scenario, but all the Antarctic ice shelves could be prone to hydro-fracturing before 2130 under the SSP5-8.5 scenario (Jourdain et al., in review). It is important to have in mind that these dates are broad indications given the large uncertainty on melt and firm processes in regional climate models. Other models predict later saturation on the ice shelf firm (Dunmire et al., 2024).

I have also been working with Vincent Favier and Jonathan Wille at IGE on atmospheric rivers, which are intrusions of very moist air, generally from the tropics, that cross the Southern Ocean in the form of large-scale filaments (Wille et al., 2021). In the Antarctic Peninsula region, most intense melting events are associated with atmospheric rivers. These also weaken the sea ice pack, which promotes swell and facilitates ice calving. On the Peninsula, 60% of major iceberg calving events between 2000 and 2020 were associated with atmospheric rivers (Wille et al., 2022).

Likely emergence of runoff conditions necessary for hydrofracturing over 1850-2200

Fig. 10 – Time intervals at which the surface runoff production likely (17-83th percentiles) exceeds the threshold that makes hydro-fracturing possible, for 56 ice shelves or groups of ice shelves. The first time range, in *italic*, corresponds to the SSP1-2.6 scenario, while the second range corresponds to SSP5-8.5. The background map shows the runoff anomaly from present day to the end of the 22nd century, with topography contours in grey (every 1000 m) and ice shelves delineated in thin black. The contours of the drainage basins of individual ice shelves are in thick black. From Jourdain et al. (2024).

CHAPTER XVI

RESULTS: ICEBERGS AND THEIR ROLES IN THE CLIMATE SYSTEM

The long journey of floating islands

The fate of ice shelves is not limited to their direct melting. In the current climate, about half of the ice flow that feeds the shelves across the grounding line melts beneath ice shelves, while the other half calves icebergs that melt as they travel across the Southern Ocean (Rignot et al., 2013; Davison et al., 2023).

NEMO includes a Lagrangian iceberg module (Marsh et al., 2015) based on the one developed by Martin and Adcroft (2011): a calving mass flux is distributed into N reservoirs according to observed size distribution laws, and once a reservoir is full, a particle representing an iceberg or a collection of icebergs is created. The particle is then advected over the ocean in a Lagrangian way, subject to friction from currents, winds and sea ice. Melting and wave erosion are parameterised. The trajectories of the simulated icebergs are improved by taking into account the full vertical structure of ocean currents (Merino et al., 2016).

This Lagrangian module allows the calculation of freshwater fluxes from melting icebergs, which can then be used as climatology for models without Lagrangian iceberg tracking (Fig. 11). They can also be used to simulate future iceberg melting in climate scenarios (Merino et al., 2018; Mathiot et al., 2023), and can be fed by the evolving calving flux of an ice sheet model. When grounded on shallow ridges, icebergs can block sea ice and promote polynyas, which influences the formation of dense water on the continental shelf (Huot et al., 2019; Van Achter et al., 2022).

Fig. 11 – Climatological fresh water flux due to the melting of Lagrangian icebergs. From Merino et al. (2016).

Fourth part

Future work

*Modelling the interactions between the Antarctic ice sheet
and the climate system*

CHAPTER XVII

FUTURE WORK: IMPLEMENTING ICE SHEETS IN EARTH SYSTEM MODELS

The Rube Goldberg Machine Contest?

This is a long-term project, with a technical-scientific component detailed below, and a communication and exchange component with climate modelling centres to motivate them and give them confidence in the development of the climate–ice-sheet coupling. The scientific motivation for such a coupling is detailed in the previous chapters. This work was initiated at IGE in collaboration with the IPSL modelling centre, as part of several European and French projects, and motivated by international efforts such as ISMIP and MISOMIP. Discussions have also been held with CNRM in France and SMHI in Sweden (member of the EC-EARTH consortium), who are also interested in specific issues related to the representation of ice sheets.

Since the beginning of ice sheet modelling, there has been a focus on the long timescales of glaciations and deglaciations, which motivates the use of very low resolution climate models, with largely parameterised physical processes. However, the revelation from space observations that the Antarctic ice sheet had lost mass in just a few decades has widened the range of applications to the interannual time scales. For these reasons, I believe it is necessary to develop several approaches, with different levels of complexity (Fig. 12).

Fig. 12 – Examples of ocean–ice-sheet coupling strategies with three different levels of complexity.

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Low complexity climate–ice-sheet coupling

The idea here is to simulate the imbalance between the polar ice sheets and the freshwater they contain, without modelling the details of climate–ice-sheet interactions or even the details of glacier dynamics. Each ice sheet is divided into a small number of drainage basins, each containing a certain mass of ice. This mass evolves according to the properties of the ocean and the atmosphere, but the ice shelf basal melt rates are fully parameterised (Burgard et al., 2022, 2023; Jourdain et al., 2020) and the surface mass balance is also parameterised (e.g., via a Positive Degree Day model). The calving flux is derived as a function of the previous fluxes via emulation of the ISMIP6 ensemble rather than via an ice sheet model. Iceberg melt is applied proportionally to the current iceberg melt distribution (Merino et al., 2016).

This coupling approach is suitable for low or very low resolution climate simulations (e.g., IPSL-CM-VLR) that do not resolve the seas beneath ice shelves or the slope gradient at the ice sheet surface where most of the melting and precipitation occur. It is also suitable for the standard version of certain climate models whose priority is not to deploy and maintain a dynamic ice sheet model in their infrastructure (e.g., CNRM-CM). A drawback of this method is the difficulty in representing non-linear processes such as marine ice sheet instabilities (MISI) and the effects of ice shelf collapse on the ice sheet dynamics.

Climate–ice-sheet coupling of intermediate complexity

The idea here is to have a dynamic ice sheet model, but at low or very low resolution, in order to study long time scales with greater realism in terms of ice dynamics. On the other hand, low resolution still requires parameterisations for the exchanges between the ice sheet and the ocean or atmosphere, although we can envisage representing the circulation beneath the largest ice shelves (Fig. 12). The melting of icebergs is still prescribed because of the poor resolution of coastal currents and to reduce the computational cost, but we can increase the complexity, e.g., by having several melt distributions depending on the geographical origin of iceberg calving.

This type of coupling will be developed in collaboration with Christophe Dumas, Sylvie Charbit and Aurélien Quiquet, all three from LSCE, in particular for the GRISLI ice sheet model (Quiquet et al., 2018). The latter is adapted to long timescales and represents processes relevant to these scales, such as isostasy or an evolving calving front. This type of coupling would be suitable for deglaciation studies, including for the North American and Eurasian ice sheets (van Aalderen et al., 2024).

High complexity climate–ice-sheet coupling

This time, the idea is to have a dynamic ice sheet model that resolves the dynamics of most Antarctic ice shelves and the surface topographic slope at the edge of the ice sheet. The ocean model represents the circulation under many ice shelves, although melting near the grounding line and under smaller shelves remains parameterized. Icebergs calved from the ice sheet model are represented in a Lagrangian way by the ocean model (Fig. 12). Such complexity is compatible with low-resolution climate models such as IPSL-CM-LR, but will be particularly well suited to higher resolutions such as IPSL-CM-MR.

This type of coupling will be interesting for adding other processes to assess their importance and possibly parameterise them in couplings of lower complexity. One of the processes we've started to work on as part of the Horizon Europe OCEAN:ICE project is the grounding of

icebergs on shallow submarine ridges, which is not represented in current iceberg models. Such grounded icebergs block sea ice and promote the formation of polynyas and dense water, with possible impacts on the global thermohaline circulation. A warmer climate could lead to more icebergs, but they could also be thinner so that the overall effect is difficult to anticipate without well-designed modelling tools.

Other processes could also be included to assess their impact on the evolution of the ice sheets, in particular (i) ocean melt at the front of Greenland glaciers that ends up at the bottom of fjords, which is not resolved by climate models even at high resolution, (ii) the deposition of black carbon or the development of algae on the surface of ice sheets and their effect on albedo, and (iii) the impact of iron contained in melting icebergs and ice shelves on the biogeochemistry of the Southern Ocean and CO₂ sequestration.

This type of coupling is currently being established between Elmer/Ice and IPSL-CM. In addition to providing a reference for studying processes, it will be ideal for revisiting the period covered by satellite observations and producing projections for the next 50 to 150 years, which are particularly relevant for planning adaptation and protection against sea level rise (Durand et al., 2022). It will also be adapted to work on the detection and attribution of mass loss from the Antarctic ice sheet, which has yet to be determined.

Improving coupled interfaces through artificial intelligence

Instead of using simplified physics for all or the most poorly resolved parts, we will also use neural networks (Burgard et al., 2023). Training such networks on complex and high-resolution simulations inherently allows learning the physical laws of numerical models and gives a physical behaviour to these statistical methods.

In the AIAI project, we are developing these approaches both for the atmosphere–ice-sheet interface (work coordinated by Cécile Agosta at LSCE) and for the ocean–ice-sheet interface, which I coordinate with Clara Burgard and Julie Deshayes at LOCEAN. **Fig. 13** shows the learning approach and the use of neural networks as planned for IPSL-CM in the AIAI project.

Fig. 13 – Methodology developed in the AIAI project to enrich coupling with neural networks.

Conservation and spin-up challenges

A steady ice sheet seems to be a reasonably realistic assumption for Antarctica in pre-industrial climate as no dramatic change in the ice sheet morphology seems to have occurred in the 5,000–7,000 years preceding 1940 (Hillenbrand et al., 2017; Braddock et al., 2022) and where sea level proxies do not point to significant contributions from Antarctica from 1900 to 1990 (Frederikse et al. 2020). In contrast, it is not a very realistic assumption for Greenland which has contributed to approximately 4 cm of global mean sea level rise from 1900 to 1990 (Frederikse et al. 2020), which is not negligible in comparison to the 1.4 cm Greenland contribution to sea level rise from 1992 to 2021 (Ottosaka et al., 2023) or to the 14 ± 4 cm projected from 2015 to 2100 under the SSP5-8.5 scenario (IPCC-AR6).

Assuming a steady Greenland ice sheet in pre-industrial conditions is nonetheless often needed for the spin up of climate simulations designed to reach a stable climate without anthropogenic emissions (i.e., the pre-industrial CMIP simulations). Another option is to accept that the ice sheet drifts far away from its present-day geometry and to run extremely long spin-up simulations until the climate–ice-sheet system reaches a steady state. This may be computationally expensive and give a present-day ice sheet with a very unrealistic shape.

Beyond pre-industrial conditions, the aim of embedding an interactive ice sheet model into a climate model is to remove the steady-ice-sheet approximation that is made in climate models such as IPSL-CM6 and CNRM-CM6. Indeed, these models assume that the mass that falls on the ice sheet is released into the Southern Ocean over the next 10 years. This has the advantage of keeping the total ocean volume more or less constant, which avoids numerical problems when water columns empty completely, but this is highly unrealistic.

Conservation challenges will also arise in the oceanic and atmospheric components, in connection with the evolution of the ice sheet topography, and also because the parameterisations added to the ice sheet model interface will have to feed back the conservation equations of the oceanic and atmospheric components. In terms of topography evolution, the Brinkman volume penalization method (Nasser 2023) will be applied to the ocean–ice-shelf interface in NEMO as part of Antoine Nasser's postdoctoral research, which I am co-supervising at IGE. First, a porosity field that varies continuously over several vertical levels avoids the usual problems of overestimated diffusion for flows along topographic slopes in Z coordinates. And by varying this porosity field over time, conservation problems arising from movements of the ocean-ice interface will be more easily resolved than with the current version of NEMO.

CHAPTER XVIII

FUTURE WORK: STUDYING OTHER ICE SHELVES AND OTHER PERIODS

Ice shelves at the crossroad

Since my recruitment, my activities have had a regional tropism towards the Amundsen Sea, where significant changes have been observed in recent decades, and around which there are a lot of international activities. However, other areas of Antarctica deserve special attention because of the role they may play in a warmer climate.

First, there's the Aurora glacial sub-basin, which drains mainly through the Totten and Moscow University ice shelves. This region shares similarities with West Antarctica, including an ice sheet grounded below sea level (and therefore vulnerable to a marine ice sheet instability), and the presence of CDW, albeit to a lesser extent than in the Amundsen Sea.

Then there's the Wilkes glacial sub-basin, a little further east, which drains mainly through the Cook, Ninnis, Mertz, and Dibble ice shelves. This part of the ice sheet is also largely grounded below sea level and is therefore likely to be conditionally unstable, although the detail of fine topographic barriers in the bedrock makes this hypothesis very uncertain. Given the frequent presence of sea ice, the oceanographic characteristics of this region remain poorly understood.

Therefore, I intend to deploy the tools presented in the previous chapters to characterise the interannual variability and future evolution of these two areas. The main challenge is the small size of the continental shelf and ice shelves in these regions compared to the Amundsen Sea. I plan to address this by using AGRIF, which is a tool to interactively nest higher resolution areas within global simulations. In addition, depending on national and international opportunities, I'd like to devote part of my activities to observing these regions, especially via future oceanographic campaigns. The presence of the Dumont d'Urville base in the Wilkes sub-basin could also be an opportunity to collaborate on new measurements over or through the small Astrolabe Ice Shelf.

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Ice shelves still exist north of Greenland, north of Ellesmere Island in the Canadian Arctic, and in the Northern Land Archipelago (*Severnaya Zemlya*) in the Russian Arctic, but they are much smaller than in Antarctica. Most have lost much of their volume since the 2000s, and many have now disappeared (Willis et al., 2015; Bell and Brown 2018; Millan et al., 2023). In Greenland, the remaining ice shelves likely influence the ice sheet flow and sea level, but the Canadian and Russian ice shelves have a very small potential contribution to sea level rise. Ice shelf disintegration has been little observed in Antarctica with a limited number of cases, so a few more cases from the Arctic add to the list of available case studies. These are essential if we want to have confidence in our ability to model the future of Antarctic ice shelves.

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As part of this effort to assess the ability of our models to predict sea level rise, I would also be interested in modelling paleoclimatic conditions for which we have observations that indirectly inform on past sea levels, such as the former ice sheet front position (Larter et al., 2014) or even their grounding lines or the presence of CDWs (Hillenbrand et al., 2017). Recently, the genome of octopus populations on both sides of West Antarctica revealed population mixing dating back to the last interglacial period, suggesting that there was no grounded ice sheet between the Weddell and Amundsen Seas at that time (Lau et al., 2023).

This information is invaluable because modern observations cover a relatively short period compared to the ice sheet response time, and it is critical that our model configurations reproduce the major changes indicated by paleoclimatic data. In this way, the climate–ice-sheet coupled model will allow us to work together with climate modelling centres to simulate the major changes in the cryosphere during past deglaciations. I'm also interested in case studies of abrupt transitions in the past, such as Meltwater Pulse 1A (sea level rise of about twenty meters in 500 years at the end of the last glacial period), to assess the ability of our modelling systems to reproduce these rapid changes.

REFERENCES

- Adcroft, A., Hill, C. and Marshall, J. (1997). Representation of topography by shaved cells in a height coordinate ocean model. *Monthly Weather Review*, 125(9), 2293-2315. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493\(1997\)125%3C2293:ROTBSC%3E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(1997)125%3C2293:ROTBSC%3E2.0.CO;2)
- Agosta, C., Amory, C., Kittel, C., Orsi, A., Favier, V., Gallée, H. and others (2019). Estimation of the Antarctic surface mass balance using the regional climate model MAR (1979–2015) and identification of dominant processes. *The Cryosphere*, 13(1), 281-296. <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-13-281-2019>
- Ahnert F. (1963). The Terminal Disintegration of Steensby Gletscher, North Greenland. *Journal of Glaciology*. 4(35):537-545. <http://doi.org/10.3189/S0022143000028070>
- Argüeso, D., Di Luca, A., Jourdain, N. C., Romero, R., Homar, V. (2022). Spatial differential heating and extreme precipitation changes in a tropical archipelago. *J. Climate*, 35(17), 5519–5536. <http://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-21-0224.1>
- Arzeno, I. B., Beardsley, R. C., Limeburner, R., Owens, B., Padman, L. and others (2014). Ocean variability contributing to basal melt rate near the ice front of Ross Ice Shelf, Antarctica. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 119(7), 4214-4233. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2014JC009792>
- Ashok, K., Behera, S. K., Rao, S. A., Weng, H. and Yamagata, T. (2007). El Niño Modoki and its possible teleconnection. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 112(C11). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2006JC003798>
- Assmann, K. M., Jenkins, A., Shoosmith, D. R., Walker, D. P., Jacobs, S. S. and Nicholls, K. W. (2013). Variability of Circumpolar Deep Water transport onto the Amundsen Sea continental shelf through a shelf break trough. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 118(12), 6603-6620. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2013JC008871>
- Balch, E. S. (1912). Recent Antarctic Discoveries. *Bulletin of the American Geographical Society*, 44(3), 161-167. <http://www.jstor.com/stable/200670>
- Banwell, A. F., MacAyeal, D. R. and Sergienko, O. V. (2013). Breakup of the Larsen B Ice Shelf triggered by chain reaction drainage of supraglacial lakes. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 40(22), 5872-5876. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2013GL057694>
- Banwell, A. F., Willis, I. C., Macdonald, G. J., Goodsell, B. and MacAyeal, D. R. (2019). Direct measurements of ice-shelf flexure caused by surface meltwater ponding and drainage. *Nature Communications*, 10(1), 730. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-08522-5>
- Barbi, D., Lohmann, G., Grosfeld, K., and Thoma, M. (2014). Ice sheet dynamics within an earth system model: downscaling, coupling and first results, *Geoscientific Model Development*, 7, 2003–2013, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-7-2003-2014>
- Bassis, J. N. and Walker, C. C. (2012). Upper and lower limits on the stability of calving glaciers from the yield strength envelope of ice. *Proceedings of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 468(2140), 913-931. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspa.2011.0422>
- Bassis, J. N., Crawford, A., Kachuck, S. B., Benn, D. I., Walker, C. and others (2024). Stability of Ice Shelves and Ice Cliffs in a Changing Climate. *Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Sciences*, 52. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-earth-040522-122817>
- Beckmann, A., Hellmer, H. H. and Timmermann, R. (1999). A numerical model of the Weddell Sea: Large-scale circulation and water mass distribution. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 104(C10), 23375-23391. <https://doi.org/10.1029/1999JC900194>
- Bentley, C. R. and Ostenso, N. A. (1961). Glacial and subglacial topography of West Antarctica. *Journal of Glaciology*, 3(29), 882-911. <https://doi.org/10.3189/S0022143000027271>
- Berger, A. (1988). Milankovitch theory and climate. *Reviews of Geophysics*, 26(4), 624-657. <https://doi.org/10.1029/RG026i004p00624>
- Bindoff, N. L., Rosenberg, M. A. and Warner, M. J. (2000). On the circulation and water masses over the Antarctic continental slope and rise between 80 and 150 E. *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography*, 47(12-13), 2299-2326. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0967-0645\(00\)00038-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0967-0645(00)00038-2)
- Bintanja R., Van Oldenborgh G., Drijfhout S., Wouters B., Katsman, C. (2013). Important role for ocean warming and increased ice-shelf melt in Antarctic sea-ice expansion. *Nature Geoscience*, 6(5):376–9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/NNGEO1767>
- Bleck, R., Rooth, C., Hu, D. and Smith, L. T. (1992). Salinity-driven thermocline transients in a wind-and thermohaline-forced isopycnic coordinate model of the North Atlantic. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 22(12), 1486-1505. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485\(1992\)022%3C1486:SDTTIA%3E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485(1992)022%3C1486:SDTTIA%3E2.0.CO;2)
- Blumberg, A. F. and Mellor, G. L. (1987). A description of a three-dimensional coastal ocean circulation model. *Three-dimensional coastal ocean models*, 4, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1029/CO004p0001>

- Braddock, S., Hall, B.L., Johnson, J.S. and others (2022). Relative sea-level data preclude major late Holocene ice-mass change in Pine Island Bay. *Nature Geoscience*, 15, 568–572. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-022-00961-y>
- Briner, J. P., McKay, N. P., Axford, Y., Bennike, O., Bradley, R. S. and others (2016). Holocene climate change in Arctic Canada and Greenland. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 147, 340-364. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2016.02.010>
- Bronselaer, B., Winton, M., Griffies, S. M., Hurlin, W. J., Rodgers, K. B., Sergienko, O. V. and others (2018). Change in future climate due to Antarctic meltwater. *Nature*, 564(7734), 53-58. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-018-0712-z>
- Bull, C. Y. S., Kiss, A., Jourdain, N. C., England, M. H. and van Sebille, E. (2017). Wind forced variability in eddy formation, eddy shedding and the separation of the East Australian Current. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 122 (12), 9980–9998 <http://doi.org/10.1002/2017JC013311>
- Bull, C. Y. S., Kiss, A., van Sebille, E., Jourdain, N. C. and England, M. H. (2018). The role of the New Zealand plateau in the Tasman Sea circulation and separation of the East Australian Current. *Journal Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 123 (2), 1457-1470. <http://doi.org/10.1002/2017JC013412>
- Bull, C. Y. S., Kiss, A., Sen Gupta, A., Jourdain, N. C., Argüeso, D., Di Luca, A., Sérazin, G. (2020). Regional versus remote atmosphere-ocean drivers of the rapid projected intensification of the East Australian Current. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 125(7), JC015889. <http://doi.org/10.1029/2019JC015889>
- Bull, C. Y. S., Jenkins, A., Jourdain, N. C., Vankova, I., Holland, P., Mathiot, P., Hausmann, U., Sallée, J.-B. (2021). Remote control of Filchner-Ronne Ice Shelf melt rates by the Antarctic Slope Current. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 126 (2), e2020JC016550, <http://doi.org/10.1029/2020JC016550>
- Burgard, C., Jourdain, N. C., Reese, R., Jenkins, A., and Mathiot, P. (2022). An assessment of basal melt parameterisations for Antarctic ice shelves, *The Cryosphere*, 16, 4931–4975, <http://doi.org/10.5194/tc-16-4931-2022>
- Burgard, C., Jourdain, N. C., Mathiot, P., Smith, R., Schäfer, R., Caillet, J., Finn, T. and Johnson, J. (2023). Emulating present and future simulations of melt rates at the base of Antarctic ice shelves with neural networks. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 15 (12), e2023MS003829. <http://doi.org/10.1029/2023MS003829>
- Burrill, M. F., Bertrand, K. J. and Alberts, F. G. (1956). Geographic names of Antarctica, Gazetteer 14, U.S. Board on Geographic Names, Department of the Interior. <https://pubs.usgs.gov/fedgov/70039165/report.pdf>
- Caillet, J., Jourdain, N. C., Mathiot, P., Hellmer, H. H., Mouginit, J. (2023). Drivers and reversibility of abrupt ocean state transitions in the Amundsen Sea, Antarctica. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 128, e2022JC018929, <http://doi.org/10.1029/2022JC018929>
- Caillet, J., Jourdain, N. C., Mathiot, P., Gillet-Chaulet, F., Urruty, B., Burgard, C., Amory, C., Kittel, C. and Chekki, M. (2024). Uncertainty in the projected Antarctic contribution to sea level due to internal climate variability. *Submitted to Earth System Dynamics*. <http://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2024-128>
- Clark, R. W., Wellner, J. S., Hillenbrand, C.-D., Totten, R. L., Smith, J. A. and others (2024). Synchronous retreat of Thwaites and Pine Island glaciers in response to external forcings in the presatellite era. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 121 (11), e2211711120. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2211711120>
- Cooper, B. J. (2010). ‘Snowball Earth’: The early contribution from South Australia. *Earth Sci. Hist.* 29, 121–145. <https://doi.org/10.17704/eshi.29.1.j8874825610u68w5>
- Cornford, S. L., Martin, D. F., Graves, D. T., Ranken, D. F., Le Brocq, A. M., and others (2013). Adaptive mesh, finite volume modeling of marine ice sheets. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 232(1), 529-549. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2012.08.037>
- Correll, R. C. (1998). Our Changing Planet. *DIANE Publishing*. <https://books.google.fr/books?id=JHnw4eqAFRcC&lpg=PP9&ots=kAPNr58EmN&dq=%22our%20changing%20planet%22%20robert%20correll&lr&pg=PP5#v=onepage&q=%22our%20changing%20planet%22%20robert%20correll&f=false>
- Couette, P. O., Lajeunesse, P., Ghienne, J. F. and others (2022). Evidence for an extensive ice shelf in northern Baffin Bay during the Last Glacial Maximum. *Commun Earth Environ* 3, 225. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-022-00559-7>
- Crabtree, R. D. and Doake, C. S. M. (1982). Pine Island Glacier and its drainage basin: Results from radio echo-sounding. *Annals of Glaciology*, 3, 65-70. <http://doi.org/10.3189/S0260305500002548>
- Croll, J. (1875). Climate and time in their geological relations: a theory of secular changes of the Earth's climate. *New York: D. Appleton and Company*. <https://archive.org/details/climateandtimei00crolgoog/climateandtimei00crolgoog>
- Csatho, B., T. Schenk, C. J. Van der Veen, and W. B. Krabill (2008), Intermittent thinning of Jakobshavn Isbrae, west Greenland, since the Little Ice Age, *Journal of Glaciology*, 54(184), 131–144. <http://10.3189/002214308784409035>.
- Davison, B. J., Hogg, A. E., Gourmelen, N., Jakob, L., Wuite, J., Nagler, T. and others (2023). Annual mass budget of Antarctic ice shelves from 1997 to 2021. *Science Advances*, 9(41), eadi0186. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.adi0186>
- Debenham, F. (1948). The Problem of the Great Ross Barrier. *The Geographical Journal*, 112(4-6), 196-212. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1789698>

- DeConto, R. M. and Pollard, D. (2016). Contribution of Antarctica to past and future sea-level rise. *Nature*, 531(7596), 591-597. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature17145>
- De Guerlache, A. (1902). Voyage de la Belgica – Quinze mois dans l'Antarctique. Imprimerie Scientifique Ch. Bulens, Bruxelles. <https://ia800206.us.archive.org/31/items/voyagedelabelgi00unkngoog/voyagedelabelgi00unkngoog.pdf>
- De Rydt, J., Holland, P. R., Dutrieux, P. and Jenkins, A. (2014). Geometric and oceanographic controls on melting beneath Pine Island Glacier. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 119(4), 2420-2438. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2013JC009513>
- De Rydt, J. and Gudmundsson, G. H. (2016). Coupled ice shelf-ocean modeling and complex grounding line retreat from a seabed ridge. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface*, 121(5), 865-880. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015JF003791>
- De Rydt, J., Jourdain, N. C., Nakayama, Y., van Caspel, M., Timmermann, R., Mathiot, P., Asay-Davis, X. S. and others (2024). Experimental design for the marine ice sheet and ocean model intercomparison project - phase 2 (MISOMIP2). *Submitted to Geophysical Model Development* <http://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2024-95>
- De Rydt, J. and Naughten, K. (2024). Geometric amplification and suppression of ice-shelf basal melt in West Antarctica. *EGU sphere*, 1-36. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2023-1587>
- Dinniman, M. S., Klinck, J. M. and Smith Jr, W. O. (2007). Influence of sea ice cover and icebergs on circulation and water mass formation in a numerical circulation model of the Ross Sea, Antarctica. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 112(C11). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2006JC004036>
- Doake, C. S. M. and Vaughan, D. G. (1991). Rapid disintegration of the Wordie Ice Shelf in response to atmospheric warming. *Nature*, 350(6316), 328-330. <https://doi.org/10.1038/350328a0>
- Domack, E. W. and Hoffman, P. F. (2011). An ice grounding-line wedge from the Ghaub glaciation (635 Ma) on the distal foreslope of the Otavi carbonate platform, Namibia, and its bearing on the snowball Earth hypothesis. *GSA Bulletin*, 123(7-8), 1448-1477. <https://doi.org/10.1130/B30217.1>
- Donat-Magnin, M., Jourdain, N. C., Spence, P., Le Sommer, J., Gallée, H. and Durand, G. (2017). Ice-shelf melt response to changing winds and glacier dynamics in the Amundsen Sea Sector, Antarctica. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 122(12), 10206–10224. <http://doi.org/10.1002/2017JC013059>
- Donat-Magnin, M., Jourdain, N. C., Gallée, H., Amory, C., Kittel, C., Fettweis, X., Wille, J. D., Favier, V., Drira, A., and Agosta, C. (2020). Interannual Variability of Summer Surface Mass Balance and Surface Melting in the Amundsen Sector, West Antarctica. *The Cryosphere*, 14, 229-249. <http://doi.org/10.5194/tc-14-229-2020>
- Donat-Magnin, M., Jourdain, N. C., Kittel, C., Agosta, C., Amory, C., Gallée, H., Krinner, G., Chekki, M. (2021). Future ice-sheet surface mass balance and melting in the Amundsen region, West Antarctica. *The Cryosphere*, 15, 571–593, <http://doi.org/10.5194/tc-15-571-2021>
- Dotto, T. S., Garabato, A. C. N., Bacon, S., Holland, P. R., Kimura, S. and others (2019). Wind-driven processes controlling oceanic heat delivery to the Amundsen Sea, Antarctica. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 49(11), 2829-2849. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JPO-D-19-0064.1>
- Dowdeswell, J. A., Gorman, M. R., Glazovsky, A. F. and Macheret, Y. Y. (1994). Evidence for floating ice shelves in Franz Josef Land, Russian high Arctic. *Arctic and Alpine Research*, 26(1), 86-92. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00040851.1994.12003044>
- Dumont-d'Urville, M. J. (1845). Voyage au Pole Sud et dans l'Océanie sur les corvettes "l'Astrolabe" et "la Zélée – Histoire du Voyage – Tome 8.
- Dunmire, D., Wever, N., Banwell, A. F. and Lenaerts, J. T. (2024). Antarctic-wide ice-shelf firm emulation reveals robust future firm air depletion signal for the Antarctic Peninsula. *Communications Earth & Environment*, 5(1), 100. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-024-01255-4>
- Durand, G., van den Broeke, M., Le Cozannet, G., Edwards, T., Holland, P. R., Jourdain, N. C. and others (2022). Sea-level rise is a global issue with major local impacts. *Frontiers in Marine Science*. <http://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.709595>
- Dutheil C., Bador M., Lengaigne M., Lefevre J., Jourdain N. C., Jullien S., Vialard J., Peltier A., and Menkes C. (2019). Impact of surface temperature biases on climate change projections of the South Pacific Convergence Zone. *Climate Dynamics*, 53(5-6), 3197–3219. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-019-04692-6>
- Dutheil C., Bador M., Lengaigne M., Lefevre J., Jourdain N. C., Jullien S., Vialard J., Peltier A., Sultan, B. and Menkes C. (2020). Impact of projected sea surface temperature biases on tropical cyclones projections in the South Pacific. *Scientific Reports*, 10, 4838. <http://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-61570-6>
- Dutrieux, P., De Rydt, J., Jenkins, A., Holland, P. R. and others (2014). Strong sensitivity of Pine Island ice-shelf melting to climatic variability. *Science*, 343(6167), 174-178. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1244341>
- Edwards, T. L., Nowicki, S., Marzeion, B., Hock, R., Goelzer, H., Seroussi, H., Jourdain, N. C. and others (2021). Projected land ice contributions to twenty-first-century sea level rise. *Nature*, 593, 74–82. <http://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03302-y>
- England, J. H., Lakeman, T. R., Lemmen, D. S., Bednarski, J. M., Stewart, T. G. and Evans, D. J. (2008). A millennial-scale record of Arctic Ocean sea ice variability and the demise of the Ellesmere Island ice shelves. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 35(19). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2008GL034470>

- Echelmeyer, K., Clarke, T. S. and Harrison, W. D. (1991). Surficial glaciology of Jakobshavns Isbræ, West Greenland: Part I. Surface morphology. *Journal of Glaciology*, 37(127), 368-382. <http://doi.org/10.3189/S0022143000005803>
- Favier, L., Durand, G., Cornford, S. L., Gudmundsson, G. H., Gagliardini, O., Gillet-Chaulet, F., Zwinger, T., Paynes, A. J. and Le Brocq, A. M. (2014). Retreat of Pine Island Glacier controlled by marine ice-sheet instability. *Nature Climate Change*, 4(2), 117-121. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2094>
- Favier, L., Jourdain, N. C., Jenkins, A., Merino, N., Durand, G., Gagliardini, O., Gillet-Chaulet, F. and Mathiot, P. (2019). Assessment of sub-shelf melting parameterisations using the ocean–ice-sheet coupled model NEMO (v3.6) – Elmer/Ice (v8.3). *Geoscientific Model Development*, 12(6), 2255-2283. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-12-2255-2019>
- Flament, T. and Rémy, F. (2012). Dynamic thinning of Antarctic glaciers from along-track repeat radar altimetry. *Journal of Glaciology*, 58(211), 830-840. <http://doi.org/10.3189/2012JoG11J118>
- Fleming, J. R. (2006). James Croll in Context. *History of Meteorology*, 3, 43-53. <https://www.journal.meteohistory.org/index.php/hom/article/download/57/57>
- Fox-Kemper, B., H.T. Hewitt, C. Xiao, G. Aðalgeirsdóttir, S.S. Drijfhout, T.L. Edwards, N.R. Golledge, M. Hemer, R.E. Kopp, G. Krinner, A. Mix, D. Notz, S. Nowicki, I.S. Nurhati, L. Ruiz, J.-B. Sallée, A.B.A. Slangen, and Y. Yu (2021). Ocean, Cryosphere and Sea Level Change. In *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Masson-Delmotte, V., P. Zhai, A. Pirani, S.L. Connors, C. Péan, S. Berger, N. Caud, Y. Chen, L. Goldfarb, M.I. Gomis, M. Huang, K. Leitzell, E. Lonnoy, J.B.R. Matthews, T.K. Maycock, T. Waterfield, O. Yelekçi, R. Yu, and B. Zhou (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, pp. 1211–1362, <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157896.011>
- Frederikse, T., Landerer, F., Caron, L., Adhikari, S., Parkes, D., Humphrey, V. W. and others (2020). The causes of sea-level rise since 1900. *Nature*, 584(7821), 393-397. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2591-3>
- Gallée, H., Guyomarc'h, G. and Brun, E. (2001). Impact of snow drift on the Antarctic ice sheet surface mass balance: possible sensitivity to snow-surface properties. *Boundary-Layer Meteorology*, 99, 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1018776422809>
- Galton-Fenzi, B. K. (2009). Modelling ice-shelf/ocean interaction. *Doctoral dissertation, University of Tasmania*. <https://figshare.utas.edu.au/ndownloader/files/40943639>
- Gandy, N., Gregoire, L. J., Ely, J. C., Clark, C. D., Hodgson, D. M., Lee, V., Bradwell, T., and Ivanovic, R. F. (2018). Marine ice sheet instability and ice shelf buttressing of the Minch Ice Stream, northwest Scotland, *The Cryosphere*, 12, 3635–3651, <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-12-3635-2018>
- Garbe, J., Albrecht, T., Levermann, A., Donges, J. F. and Winkelmann, R. (2020). The hysteresis of the Antarctic ice sheet. *Nature*, 585(7826), 538-544. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2727-5>
- Gilbert, E. and Kittel, C. (2021). Surface melt and runoff on Antarctic ice shelves at 1.5 C, 2 C, and 4 C of future warming. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 48(8), e2020GL091733. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020GL091733>
- Gimbert, F., Jourdain, N. C., Marsan, D., Weiss, J., Barnier, B. (2012). Recent mechanical weakening of the Arctic sea ice cover as revealed from larger inertial oscillations. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 117:C00J12, 14pp. <http://doi.org/10.1029/2011JC007633>
- Gimbert, F., Marsan, D., Weiss, J., Jourdain, N. C., Barnier, B. (2012). Sea ice inertial oscillation magnitudes in the Arctic basin. *The Cryosphere* 6:2179-2220. <http://doi.org/10.5194/tc-6-1187-2012>
- Gladstone, R., Galton-Fenzi, B., Gwyther, D., Zhou, Q., Hattermann, T., Zhao, C. and others (2021). The Framework For Ice Sheet–Ocean Coupling (FISOC) V1. 1. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 14(2), 889-905. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-14-889-2021>
- Goldberg, D. N., Little, C. M., Sergienko, O. V., Gnanadesikan, A., Hallberg, R. and Oppenheimer, M. (2012). Investigation of land ice-ocean interaction with a fully coupled ice-ocean model: 1. Model description and behavior. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface*, 117(F2). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2011JF002246>
- Goldberg, D. N., Snow, K., Holland, P., Jordan, J. R., Campin, J. M., Heimbach, P. and others (2018). Representing grounding line migration in synchronous coupling between a marine ice sheet model and a z-coordinate ocean model. *Ocean Modelling*, 125, 45-60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocemod.2018.03.005>
- Gómez-Valdivia, F., Holland, P. R., Siahaan, A., Dutriex, P. and Young, E. (2023). Projected West Antarctic ocean warming caused by an expansion of the Ross Gyre. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 50(6), e2023GL102978. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023GL102978>
- Greenbaum, J. S., Blankenship, D. D., Young, D. A., Richter, T. G., Roberts, J. L. and others (2015). Ocean access to a cavity beneath Totten Glacier in East Antarctica. *Nature Geoscience*, 8(4), 294-298. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo2388>
- Grosfeld, K., Gerdes, R. and Determann, J. (1997). Thermohaline circulation and interaction between ice shelf cavities and the adjacent open ocean. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 102(C7), 15595-15610. <https://doi.org/10.1029/97JC00891>
- Grosfeld, K. and Sandhäger, H. (2004). The evolution of a coupled ice shelf–ocean system under different climate states. *Global and Planetary change*, 42(1-4), 107-132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha.2003.11.004>

- Guilyardi, E., Madec, G., Lévy, C., Harris, C. Hazeleger, W. and Scoccimarro, E. (2012). NEMO for climate modeling. *Mercator Ocean Quarterly Newsletter*, 46, 67-69. https://www.mercator-ocean.eu/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/Mercator-Ocean-newsletter-2012_46.pdf
- Haidvogel, D. B., Wilkin, J. L. and Young, R. (1991). A semi-spectral primitive equation ocean circulation model using vertical sigma and orthogonal curvilinear horizontal coordinates. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 94(1), 151-185. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9991\(91\)90141-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9991(91)90141-7)
- Haidvogel, D. B., Arango, H. G., Hedstrom, K., Beckmann, A., Malanotte-Rizzoli, P., & Shchepetkin, A. F. (2000). Model evaluation experiments in the North Atlantic Basin: simulations in nonlinear terrain-following coordinates. *Dynamics of atmospheres and oceans*, 32(3-4), 239-281. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-0265\(00\)00049-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-0265(00)00049-X)
- Haigh, M. and Holland, P. R. (2024). Decadal variability of ice-shelf melting in the Amundsen Sea driven by sea-ice freshwater fluxes. *Authorea Preprints*. <https://doi.org/10.22541/essoar.170593860.09639068/v1>
- Hallberg, R. (1997). HIM: The Hallberg isopycnal coordinate primitive equation model. *Princeton University and NOAA Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory*. https://www.gfdl.noaa.gov/wp-content/uploads/files/user_files/rwh/him_description.pdf
- Hansen J., Sato M., Hearty P., Ruedy R., Kelley M., Masson-Delmotte V. and others (2016). Ice melt, sea level rise and superstorms: evidence from paleoclimate data, climate modeling, and modern observations that 2°C global warming could be dangerous. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 16(6):3761–812. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-16-3761-2016>
- Harland, W. B. (1964). Critical evidence for a great infra-Cambrian glaciation. *Geologische Rundschau*, 54, 45-61. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01821169>
- Hausmann, U., Sallée, J.-B., Jourdain, N. C., Mathiot, P., Rousset, C., Madec, G., Deshayes, J. and Hattermann, T. (2020). The role of tides in ocean-ice-shelf interactions in the southwestern Weddell Sea. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 125(6), JC015847. <http://doi.org/10.1029/2019JC015847>
- Hellmer, H. H. and Olbers, D. J. (1989). A two-dimensional model for the thermohaline circulation under an ice shelf. *Antarctic Science*, 1(4), 325-336. <http://doi.org/10.1017/S0954102089000490>
- Hellmer, H. H. (2004). Impact of Antarctic ice shelf basal melting on sea ice and deep ocean properties. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 31(10). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2004GL019506>
- Hellmer, H., Kauker, F., Timmermann, R., Determann, J. and Rae, J. (2012). Twenty-first-century warming of a large Antarctic ice-shelf cavity by a redirected coastal current. *Nature*, 485, 225–228. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature11064>
- Hellmer, H. H., Kauker, F., Timmermann, R. and Hattermann, T. (2017). The fate of the southern Weddell Sea continental shelf in a warming climate. *Journal of Climate*, 30(12), 4337-4350. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-16-0420.1>
- Hill, E. A., Carr, J. R. and Stokes, C. R. (2017). A review of recent changes in major marine-terminating outlet glaciers in Northern Greenland. *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 4, 111. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2016.00111>
- Hillenbrand, C. D., Smith, J. A., Hodell, D. A., Greaves, M., Poole, C. R. and others (2017). West Antarctic Ice Sheet retreat driven by Holocene warm water incursions. *Nature*, 547(7661), 43-48. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature22995>
- Hindmarsh R. C. A. and Le Meur E. (2001). Dynamical processes involved in the retreat of marine ice sheets. *Journal of Glaciology*, 47(157):271-282. <http://doi.org/10.3189/172756501781832269>
- Hoffman, P. F. (2011a). A history of Neoproterozoic glacial geology, 1871–1997. In: *The Geological Record of Neoproterozoic Glaciations*. Geological Society of London. <https://doi.org/10.1144/M36.2>
- Hoffman, P. F. (2011b). Strange bedfellows: glacial diamictite and cap carbonate from the Marinoan (635 Ma) glaciation in Namibia. *Sedimentology*, 58(1), 57-119. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3091.2010.01206.x>
- Holland, D. M. and Jenkins, A. (1999). Modeling thermodynamic ice–ocean interactions at the base of an ice shelf. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 29(8), 1787-1800. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485\(1999\)029%3C1787:MTIOIA%3E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485(1999)029%3C1787:MTIOIA%3E2.0.CO;2)
- Holland, D. M. and Jenkins, A. (2001). Adaptation of an isopycnal coordinate ocean model for the study of circulation beneath ice shelves. *Monthly Weather Review*, 129(8), 1905-1927. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493\(2001\)129%3C1905:AOAICO%3E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(2001)129%3C1905:AOAICO%3E2.0.CO;2)
- Holland, D. M., Jacobs, S. S. and Jenkins, A. (2003). Modelling the ocean circulation beneath the Ross Ice Shelf. *Antarctic Science*, 15(1), 13-23. <http://doi.org/10.1017/S0954102003001019>
- Holland, P. R., Bruneau, N., Enright, C., Losch, M., Kurtz, N. T., and Kwok, R. (2014). Modeled Trends in Antarctic Sea Ice Thickness. *J. Climate*, 27, 3784–3801. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-13-00301.1>
- Holland, P. R., Bracegirdle, T. J., Dutrieux, P., Jenkins, A. and Steig, E. J. (2019). West Antarctic ice loss influenced by internal climate variability and anthropogenic forcing. *Nature Geoscience*, 12(9), 718-724. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-019-0420-9>
- Houghton J. T, Jenkins G., Ephraums J. J. (1990). Climate Change – The IPCC scientific assessment. *Cambridge University Press*. https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2018/03/ipcc_far_wg_I_full_report.pdf

- Houghton, J. T., Meira Filho, L. G., Callander, B. A., Harris, N., Kattenberg, A. and Maskell, K. (1995). *Climate Change 1995 – The science of climate change – Contribution of WGI to the Second Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press. https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2018/02/ipcc_sar_wg_I_full_report.pdf
- Hughes, T. (1973). Is the West Antarctic ice sheet disintegrating? *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 78(33), 7884-7910. <https://doi.org/10.1029/JC078i033p07884>
- Hughes, T. J. (1981). The weak underbelly of the West Antarctic ice sheet. *Journal of Glaciology*, 27(97), 518-525. <https://doi.org/10.3189/S002214300001159X>
- Hughes, T. (1983). On the disintegration of ice shelves: the role of fracture. *Journal of Glaciology*, 29(101), 98-117. <http://doi.org/10.3189/S0022143000005177>
- Huot, P.-V., Fichet, T., Jourdain, N. C., Mathiot, P., Rousset, C., Kittel, C., Fettweis, X. (2021). Influence of ocean tides and ice shelves on ocean-ice interactions and dense shelf water formation in the D'Urville Sea, Antarctica. *Ocean Modelling*, 101794. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocemod.2021.101794>
- Hutchinson, K., Deshayes, J., Ethé, C., Rousset, C., de Lavergne, C., Vancoppenolle, M., Jourdain, N. C. and Mathiot, P. (2023). Improving Antarctic Bottom Water precursors in NEMO for climate applications. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 16, 3629-3650. <http://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-16-3629-2023>
- IOC – Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (2002). *Improved Global Bathymetry – Final Report of SCOR, Working Group 107*. IOC Technical Series No. 63, UNESCO. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000127238.locale=en>
- Izumo, T., Vialard, J., Lengaigne, M., de Boyer Montegut, C., Behera, S. K. and others (2010). Influence of the state of the Indian Ocean Dipole on the following year's El Niño. *Nature Geoscience*, 3(3), 168-172. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo760>
- Jacobs, S. S. (1991). Sea-level response to ice sheet evolution: an ocean perspective. *NASA. Goddard Space Flight Center, West Antarctic Ice Sheet Initiative. Volume 2: Discipline Reviews*. <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/19910017261/downloads/19910017261.pdf>
- Jacobs, S. S., Hellmer, H. H. and Jenkins, A. (1996). Antarctic ice sheet melting in the Southeast Pacific. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 23(9), 957-960. <https://doi.org/10.1029/96GL00723>
- Jakobsson, M., Nilsson, J., O'Regan, M., Backman, J., Löwemark, L. and others (2010). An Arctic Ocean ice shelf during MIS 6 constrained by new geophysical and geological data. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 29(25-26), 3505-3517. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2010.03.015>
- Jennings, A., Reilly, B., Andrews, J., Hogan, K., Walczak, M., Jakobsson, M. and others (2022). Modern and early Holocene ice shelf sediment facies from Petermann Fjord and northern Nares Strait, northwest Greenland. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 283, 107460. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2022.107460>
- Jenkins, A. (1991). A one-dimensional model of ice shelf-ocean interaction. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 96(C11), 20671-20677. <https://doi.org/10.1029/91JC01842>
- Jenkins, A., Dutriex, P., Jacobs, S. S., McPhail, S. D., Perrett, J. R., Webb, A. T. and White, D. (2010). Observations beneath Pine Island Glacier in West Antarctica and implications for its retreat. *Nature Geoscience*, 3(7), 468-472. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo890>
- Jenkins, A., Shoosmith, D., Dutriex, P., Jacobs, S., Kim, T. W. and others (2018). West Antarctic Ice Sheet retreat in the Amundsen Sea driven by decadal oceanic variability. *Nature Geoscience*, 11(10), 733-738. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-018-0207-4>
- Jordan, J. R., Holland, P. R., Goldberg, D., Snow, K., Arthern, R., Campin, J. M. and others (2018). Ocean-forced ice-shelf thinning in a synchronously coupled ice-ocean model. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 123(2), 864-882. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017JC013251>
- Joughin, I., Howat, I. M., Fahnestock, M., Smith, B., Krabill, W., Alley, R. B. and others (2008). Continued evolution of Jakobshavn Isbrae following its rapid speedup. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface*, 113(F4). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2008JF001023>
- Joughin, I., Smith, B. E. and Medley, B. (2014). Marine ice sheet collapse potentially under way for the Thwaites Glacier Basin, West Antarctica. *Science*, 344(6185), 735-738. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1249055>
- Joughin, I., Shean, D. E., Smith, B. E. and Floricioiu, D. (2020). A decade of variability on Jakobshavn Isbrae: ocean temperatures pace speed through influence on mélange rigidity. *The Cryosphere*, 14(1), 211-227. <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-14-211-2020>
- Jourdain N. C., Marchesiello, P., Menkes, C. E., Lefèvre, J., Vincent, E., Lengaigne, M., Chauvin, F. (2011). Mesoscale simulation of tropical cyclones in the South Pacific: climatology and interannual variability. *Journal of Climate*, 24:3–25. <http://doi.org/10.1175/2010JCLI3559.1>
- Jourdain, N. C., Lengaigne, M., Vialard, J., Madec, G., Menkes, C. E., Vincent, E. M., Jullien, S. and Barnier, B. (2013). Observation based estimates of surface cooling inhibition by heavy rainfall under tropical cyclones. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 43, 205-221. <http://doi.org/10.1175/JPO-D-12-085.1>

- Jourdain, N. C., Sen Gupta, A., Taschetto, A. S., Ummenhofer, C. M., Moise, A. and Ashok, K. (2013). The Indo-Australian monsoon and its relationship to ENSO and IOD in reanalysis data and the CMIP3/CMIP5 simulations. *Climate Dynamics*, 41 (11), 3073-3102. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-013-1676-1>
- Jourdain, N. C., Barnier, B., Vialard, J., Ferry, N., Menkes, C. E., Lengaigne, M., Parent, L. (2014). Tropical cyclones in two atmospheric (re)analyses and their response in two oceanic reanalyses. *Ocean Modelling*, 73, 108-122. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocemod.2013.10.007>
- Jourdain, N. C., Lengaigne, M., Vialard, J., Izumo, T., Sen Gupta, A. (2016). Further insights on the influence of the Indian Ocean Dipole on the following year's ENSO from observations and CMIP5 models. *Journal of Climate*, 29(2), 637-658. <http://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-15-0481.1>
- Jourdain, N. C., Mathiot, P., Merino, N., Durand, G., Le Sommer, J., Dutrieux, P., Spence, P. and Madec, G. (2017). Ocean circulation and sea-ice thinning induced by melting ice shelves in the Amundsen Sea. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 122 (3), 2550–2573. <http://doi.org/10.1002/2016JC012509>
- Jourdain, N. C., Molines, J.-M., Le Sommer, J., Mathiot, P., Chanut, J., de Lavergne, C. and Madec, G. (2019). Simulating or prescribing the influence of tides on the Amundsen Sea ice shelves. *Ocean Modelling*, 133, 44-55. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocemod.2018.11.001>
- Jourdain, N. C., Asay-Davis, X., Hattermann, T., Straneo, F., Seroussi, H., Little, C. M., and Nowicki, S. (2020). A protocol for calculating basal melt rates in the ISMIP6 Antarctic ice sheet projections. *The Cryosphere*, 14, 3111–3134. <http://doi.org/10.5194/tc-14-3111-2020>
- Jourdain, N. C., Mathiot, P., Burgard, C., Caillet, J., Kittel, C. (2022). Ice shelf basal melt rates in the Amundsen Sea at the end of the 21st century. *Geophysical Research Letter*, 49(22), e2022GL100629, <http://doi.org/10.1029/2022GL100629>
- Jourdain, N. C., Amory, C., Kittel, C. and Durand, G. (2024). Changes in Antarctic surface conditions and potential for ice shelf hydrofracturing from 1850 to 2200. *Submitted to The Cryosphere*. <http://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2024-58>
- Jullien, S., Menkes, C. E., Marchesiello, P., Jourdain, N. C., Lengaigne, M., Koch-Larrouy, A., Lefèvre, J., Vincent, E.M., Faure, V. (2012). Impact of tropical cyclones on the heat budget of the South Pacific Ocean. *Journal of Physical Oceanography* 42:1882-1906. <http://doi.org/10.1175/JPO-D-11-0133.1>
- Jullien, S., Marchesiello, P., Menkes, C.E., Lefèvre, J., Jourdain, N.C., Samson, G., Lengaigne, M. (2014). Ocean feedback to tropical cyclones: climatology and processes. *Climate Dynamics*, 43(9-10), 2831-2854. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-014-2096-6>
- Kerr, R. A. (1987). Milankovitch Climate Cycles Through the Ages: Earth's orbital variations that bring on ice ages have been modulating climate for hundreds of millions of years. *Science*, 235(4792), 973-974. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.235.4792.973>
- Kimura, S., Jenkins, A., Regan, H., Holland, P. R., Assmann, K. M. and others (2017). Oceanographic controls on the variability of ice-shelf basal melting and circulation of glacial meltwater in the Amundsen Sea Embayment, Antarctica. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 122(12), 10131-10155. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017JC012926>
- Kirshner, A. E., Anderson, J. B., Jakobsson, M., O'Regan, M., Majewski, W. and Nitsche, F. O. (2012). Post-LGM deglaciation in Pine island Bay, west Antarctica. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 38, 11-26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2012.01.017>
- Kirschvink, J.L. (1992). Late Proterozoic low-latitude glaciation: the snowball Earth. In *The Proterozoic Biosphere*, Schopf, J.W. & Klein, C., eds., pp. 51-52, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge. https://authors.library.caltech.edu/36446/1/Kirschvink_1992p51.pdf
- Kittel C., Amory C., Agosta C., Jourdain N.C., Hofer S., Delhasse A., Doutreloup S., Huot P.-V., Lang C., Fichefet, T. and Fettweis, X. (2021). Diverging future surface mass balance between the Antarctic ice shelves and grounded ice sheet. *The Cryosphere*, 15, 1215–1236. <http://doi.org/10.5194/tc-15-1215-2021>
- Kittel, C., Amory, C., Hofer, S., Agosta, C., Jourdain, N. C., Gilbert, E., Le Toumelin, L., Gallée, H., and Fettweis, X. (2022). Clouds drive differences in future surface melt over the Antarctic ice shelves. *The Cryosphere*, 16, 2655–2669. <http://doi.org/10.5194/tc-16-2655-2022>
- Kivelson, M. G., Khurana, K. K., Russell, C. T., Volwerk, M., Walker, R. J. and Zimmer, C. (2000). Galileo magnetometer measurements: A stronger case for a subsurface ocean at Europa. *Science*, 289(5483), 1340-1343. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.289.5483.1340>
- Koenig, L. S., Greenaway, K. R., Dunbar, M. and Hattersley-Smith, G. (1952). Arctic ice islands. *Arctic*, 5(2), 66-103. <https://journalhosting.ucalgary.ca/index.php/arctic/article/download/66950/50863/>
- Kopp, R. E., Gilmore, E. A., Shwom, R. L., Adler, C., Adams, H., Oppenheimer, M. and others (2024). 'Tipping points' confuse and can distract from urgent climate action. *Authorea Preprints*. <https://doi.org/10.22541/essoar.170542965.59092060/v1>
- Koryakin V.S (2014). What happens to the glaciers of Severnaya Zemlya. *Priroda*, 11: 42–49 (Корякин В.С. Что происходит с ледниками Северной Земли, Природа). <https://naukarus.com/chto-proishodit-s-lednikami-severnoy-zemli>

- Larter, R. D., Anderson, J. B., Graham, A. G., Gohl, K., Hillenbrand, C. D. and others (2014). Reconstruction of changes in the Amundsen Sea and Bellingshausen sea sector of the West Antarctic ice sheet since the last glacial maximum. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 100, 55-86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2013.10.016>
- Lenaerts, J. T., Van den Broeke, M. R., Van de Berg, W. J., Van Meijgaard, E. and Kuipers Munneke, P. (2012). A new, high-resolution surface mass balance map of Antarctica (1979–2010) based on regional atmospheric climate modeling. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 39(4). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2011GL050713>
- Lenton, T. M., Armstrong McKay, D. I., Loriani, S., Abrams, J. F., Lade, S. J., Donges, J. F., Milkoreit, M., and others (eds), 2023, The Global Tipping Points Report 2023. *University of Exeter, Exeter, UK*. <https://global-tipping-points.org>
- Lhermitte, S., Sun, S., Shuman, C., Wouters, B., Pattyn, F. and others (2020). Damage accelerates ice shelf instability and mass loss in Amundsen Sea Embayment. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 117(40), 24735-24741. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1912890117>
- Li, Q., England, M. H., Hogg, A. M., Rintoul, S. R. and Morrison, A. K. (2023). Abyssal ocean overturning slowdown and warming driven by Antarctic meltwater. *Nature*, 615(7954), 841-847. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-05762-w>
- Li, Y., Jourdain, N. C., Taschetto, A. S., Ummenhofer, C. C., Ashok, K. and Sen Gupta, A. (2012). Evaluation of monsoon seasonality and the tropospheric biennial oscillation transitions in the CMIP models, *Geophysical Research Letter*, 39, L20713. <http://doi.org/10.1029/2012GL053322>
- Li, Y., Jourdain, N. C., Taschetto, A. S., Sen Gupta, A., Argüeso, D., Masson, S., Cai, W. (2017). Resolution dependence of the simulated precipitation and diurnal cycle over the Maritime Continent. *Climate Dynamics*, 48 (11), 4009–4028. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-016-3317-y>
- Li, Y., Sen Gupta, A., Taschetto, A. S., Jourdain, N. C., Di Luca, A., Done, J. M. (2020). Assessing the role of the ocean-atmosphere coupling frequency on the western Maritime Continent rainfall. *Climate Dynamics*, 54, 4935–4952. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-020-05266-7>
- Liotard, A. F. and Barré, M. (1953). French Antarctic Expedition, 1949–52. *Polar Record*, 6(46), 755-764.
- Little, C. M., Gnanadesikan, A. and Oppenheimer, M. (2009). How ice shelf morphology controls basal melting. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 114(C12). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2008JC005197>
- Longair, M. (2021). James Croll, celestial mechanics and climate change. *Earth and Environmental Science Transactions of the Royal Society of Edinburgh*, 112(3-4):231-238. <http://doi.org/10.1017/S1755691021000165>
- Losch, M. (2008). Modeling ice shelf cavities in az coordinate ocean general circulation model. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 113(C8). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2007JC004368>
- Lucchitta, B. K., Rosanova, C. E. and Mullins, K. F. (1995). Velocities of Pine island glacier, West Antarctica, from ERS-1 SAR images. *Annals of Glaciology*, 21, 277-283. <http://doi.org/10.3189/S0260305500015949>
- MacAyeal, D. R. (1984a). Numerical simulations of the Ross Sea tides. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 89(C1), 607-615. <https://doi.org/10.1029/JC089iC01p00607>
- MacAyeal, D. R. (1984b). Thermohaline circulation below the Ross Ice Shelf: A consequence of tidally induced vertical mixing and basal melting. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 89(C1), 597-606. <https://doi.org/10.1029/JC089iC01p00597>
- MacAyeal, D. R. (1985). Evolution of tidally triggered meltwater plumes below ice shelves. In: *Oceanology of the Antarctic continental shelf*, *Antarctic Research Series*, 43, 133-143. <https://doi.org/10.1029/AR043p0133>
- MacAyeal, D. R. and Sergienko, O. V. (2013). The flexural dynamics of melting ice shelves. *Annals of Glaciology*, 54(63), 1-10. <http://doi.org/10.3189/2013AoG63A256>
- Madsen, M. S., Yang, S., Aðalgeirsdóttir, G., Svendsen, S. H., Rodehacke, C. B. and Ringgaard, I. M. (2022). The role of an interactive Greenland ice sheet in the coupled climate-ice sheet model EC-Earth-PISM. *Climate Dynamics*, 59(3-4), 1189-1211. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-022-06184-6>
- Mahaffy, M. W. (1976). A three-dimensional numerical model of ice sheets: Tests on the Barnes Ice Cap, Northwest Territories. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 81(6), 1059-1066. <https://doi.org/10.1029/JC081i006p01059>
- Makinson, K., Holland, P. R., Jenkins, A., Nicholls, K. W. and Holland, D. M. (2011). Influence of tides on melting and freezing beneath Filchner-Ronne Ice Shelf, Antarctica. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 38(6). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2010GL046462>
- Manabe, S. (1969). Climate and the ocean circulation: I. The atmospheric circulation and the hydrology of the earth's surface. *Monthly Weather Review*, 97(11), 739-774. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493\(1969\)097%3C0739:CATOC%3E2.3.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(1969)097%3C0739:CATOC%3E2.3.CO;2)
- Manabe, S. and Bryan, K. (1969). Climate calculations with a combined ocean-atmosphere model. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, 26(4), 786-789. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493\(1969\)097%3C0806:CATOC%3E2.3.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(1969)097%3C0806:CATOC%3E2.3.CO;2)
- Manabe, S. and Wetherald, R. T. (1975). The effects of doubling the CO₂ concentration on the climate of a general circulation model. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, 32(1), 3-15. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469\(1975\)032%3C0003:TEODTC%3E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469(1975)032%3C0003:TEODTC%3E2.0.CO;2)

- Marsh, R., Ivchenko, V. O., Skliris, N., Alderson, S., Bigg, G. R., Madec, G. and others (2015). NEMO–ICB (v1. 0): interactive icebergs in the NEMO ocean model globally configured at eddy-permitting resolution. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 8(5), 1547-1562. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-8-1547-2015>
- Marshall, J., Adcroft, A., Hill, C., Perelman, L. and Heisey, C. (1997). A finite-volume, incompressible Navier Stokes model for studies of the ocean on parallel computers. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 102(C3), 5753-5766. <https://doi.org/10.1029/96JC02775>
- Martin, T. and Adcroft, A. (2010). Parameterizing the fresh-water flux from land ice to ocean with interactive icebergs in a coupled climate model. *Ocean Modelling*, 34(3-4), 111-124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocemod.2010.05.001>
- Martin, D., Asay-Davis, X., Cornford, S., Price, S., Ng, E. and Collins, W. (2015). A tale of two forcings: Present-day coupled antarctic ice-sheet/southern ocean dynamics using the popsicles model. In *EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts* (Vol. 17, p. 7564). <https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU2015/EGU2015-7564.pdf>
- Mathiot, P. and Jourdain, N. C. (2023). High-end projections of Southern Ocean warming and Antarctic ice shelf melting in conditions typical of the end of the 23rd century, *Ocean Science*, 19, 1595–1615, <http://doi.org/10.5194/os-19-1595-2023>
- Mawson, D. (1914). Australasian Antarctic Expedition (1911-1914). *The Geographical Journal*, 44(3), 257-284. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1778688>
- Meehl, G. A. (1997). The south Asian monsoon and the tropospheric biennial oscillation. *Journal of Climate*, 10(8), 1921-1943. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0442\(1997\)010%3C1921:TSAMAT%3E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0442(1997)010%3C1921:TSAMAT%3E2.0.CO;2)
- Menkes, C. E., Lengaigne, M., Marchesiello, P., Jourdain, N. C., Vincent, E. M., Lefèvre, J., Chauvin, F., Royer, J. F. (2012). Comparison of tropical cyclogenesis indices on seasonal to interannual timescales. *Climate Dynamics*, 38(1–2): 301-321. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-011-1126-x>
- Menviel, L., Timmermann, A., Timm, O. E. and Mouchet, A. (2010). Climate and biogeochemical response to a rapid melting of the West Antarctic Ice Sheet during interglacials and implications for future climate. *Paleoceanography*, 25(4). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2009PA001892>
- Merino, N., Le Sommer, J., Durand, G., Jourdain, N. C., Madec, G., Mathiot, P. and Tournadre, J. (2016). Antarctic icebergs melt over the Southern Ocean: climatology and impact on sea ice. *Ocean Modelling*, 104, 99-110. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocemod.2016.05.001>
- Merino, N., Jourdain, N. C., Le Sommer, J., Goosse, H., Mathiot, P. and Durand, G. (2018). Impact of increasing antarctic glacial freshwater release on regional sea-ice cover in the Southern Ocean. *Ocean Modelling*, 121, 76-89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocemod.2017.11.009>
- Mill, H. R. (1936). Modern Methods in the Antarctic. *Nature*, 137(3471), 759-760. <https://doi.org/10.1038/137759a0>
- Millan, R., Jager, E., Mouginot, J., Wood, M. H., Larsen, S. H., Mathiot, P., Jourdain, N. C., Bjørk, A. (2023). Rapid disintegration and weakening of ice shelves in North Greenland. *Nature Communications*, 14, 6914. <http://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-42198-2>
- Miller, K. G., Wright, J. D., Browning, J. V., Kulpecz, A., Kominz, M., Naish, T. R. and others (2012). High tide of the warm Pliocene: Implications of global sea level for Antarctic deglaciation. *Geology*, 40(5), 407-410. <https://doi.org/10.1130/G32869.1>
- Millgate, T., Holland, P. R., Jenkins, A. and Johnson, H. L. (2013). The effect of basal channels on oceanic ice-shelf melting. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 118(12), 6951-6964. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2013JC009402>
- Morris, E. M. and Vaughan, D. G. (2003). Spatial and temporal variation of surface temperature on the Antarctic Peninsula and the limit of viability of ice shelves. *Antarctic Research Series*, 79(10.1029). <https://doi.org/10.1029/AR079p0061>
- Moorman, R., Morrison, A. K. and Hogg, A. M. (2020). Thermal responses to Antarctic ice shelf melt in an eddy-rich global ocean–sea ice model. *Journal of Climate*, 33(15), 6599-6620. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-19-0846.1>
- Mueller, R. D., Padman, L., Dinniman, M. S., Erofeeva, S. Y., Fricker, H. A. and King, M. A. (2012). Impact of tide-topography interactions on basal melting of Larsen C Ice Shelf, Antarctica. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 117(C5). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2011JC007263>
- Münchow, A., Padman, L., Washam, P. and Nicholls, K. (2016). The Ice Shelf of Petermann Gletscher, North Greenland, and Its Connection to the Arctic and Atlantic Oceans. *Oceanography*, 29(4). <http://doi.org/10.5670/oceanog.2016.101>
- Muntjewerf, L., Sacks, W. J., Lofverstrom, M., Fyke, J., Lipscomb, W. H. and others (2021). Description and Demonstration of the Coupled Community Earth System Model v2–Community Ice Sheet Model v2 (CESM2-CISM2). *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 13(6), e2020MS002356. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020MS002356>
- Nares, G. S. (1878). Narrative of a voyage to the polar sea during 1875-6 in H. M. ships ‘Alert’ and ‘Discovery’. *Eds. Sampson Low, Marston, Searle, & Rivington, London*.
- Naughten, K. A., Meissner, K. J., Galton-Fenzi, B. K., England, M. H., Timmermann, R. and Hellmer, H. H. (2018). Future projections of Antarctic ice shelf melting based on CMIP5 scenarios. *Journal of Climate*, 31(13), 5243-5261. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-17-0854.1>

- Naughten, K. A., De Rydt, J., Rosier, S. H., Jenkins, A., Holland, P. R. and Ridley, J. K. (2021). Two-timescale response of a large Antarctic ice shelf to climate change. *Nature communications*, 12(1), 1991. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-22259-0>
- Needell, C. and Holschuh, N. (2023). Evaluating the Retreat, Arrest, and Regrowth of Crane Glacier Against Marine Ice Cliff Process Models. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 50(4), e2022GL102400. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022GL102400>
- Nishio, F., Ishikawa, M., Ohmae, H., Takahashi, S. and Katsushima, T. (1984). A preliminary study of glacial geomorphology in area between Breid Bay and the Sør Rondane Mountains in Queen Maud Land, East Antarctica.
- Nordenskjöld, O. (1911). Die Schwedische Südpolar Expedition und ihre Geographische Tätigkeit.
- Nowicki, S., Payne, A., Goelzer, H., Seroussi, H., Lipscomb, W., Abe-Ouchi, A., Agosta, C., Alexander, P. and others (2020). Experimental protocol for sea level projections from ISMIP6 standalone ice sheet models. *The Cryosphere*, 14, 2331–2368. <http://doi.org/10.5194/tc-14-2331-2020>
- Pacanowski, R. C., Dixon, K. and Rosati, A. (1991). The GFDL modular ocean model user guide. *The GFDL Ocean Group Technical Report number 2*.
- Park, JY., Schloesser, F., Timmermann, A., Choudhury, D., Lee, J.-Y. and Nellikkattil, A. B. (2023). Future sea-level projections with a coupled atmosphere-ocean-ice-sheet model. *Nature Communications*, 14, 636. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-36051-9>
- Pattyn, F., Declerq, H. and Huybrechts, P. (1992). Glaciation of the central part of the Sør Rondane, Antarctica: glaciological evidence. *Recent progress in Antarctic earth science*. Tokyo: Terra Scientific Publishing Company, 669-678. <https://www.vliz.be/imisdocs/publications/ocrd/215745.pdf>
- Pattyn, F., Perichon, L., Durand, G., Favier, L., Gagliardini, O., and others (2013). Grounding-line migration in plan-view marine ice-sheet models: Results of the ice2sea MISIP3d intercomparison. *Journal of Glaciology*, 59(215), 410-422. <http://doi.org/10.3189/2013JoG12J129>
- Pattyn, F. (2018). The paradigm shift in Antarctic ice sheet modelling. *Nature Communications*, 9(1), 2728. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-05003-z>
- Payne, A., Nowicki, S., Abe Ouchi, A., Agosta, C., Albrecht, T., Asay-Davis, X., Barthel, A., Calov, R., Chambers, C., Cullather and others (2021). Contrasting contributions to future sea level under CMIP5 and CMIP6 scenarios from the Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets. *Geophysical Research Letter*, 48(16), e2020GL091741. <http://doi.org/10.1029/2020GL091741>
- Pollard, D., DeConto, R. M. and Alley, R. B. (2015). Potential Antarctic Ice Sheet retreat driven by hydrofracturing and ice cliff failure. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 412, 112-12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2014.12.035>
- Priestley, R. E. (1914). Antarctic Ice. *The Geographical Teacher*, 7(6), 359-368. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/40555875>
- Pritchard, H., Ligtenberg, S. R., Fricker, H. A., Vaughan, D. G., van den Broeke, M. R., & Padman, L. (2012). Antarctic ice-sheet loss driven by basal melting of ice shelves. *Nature*, 484(7395), 502-505. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature10968>
- Purich, A. and England, M. H. (2023). Projected Impacts of Antarctic Meltwater Anomalies over the Twenty-First Century. *Journal of Climate*, 36(8), 2703-2719. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-22-0457.1>
- Quiquet, A., Dumas, C., Ritz, C., Peyaud, V. and Roche, D. M. (2018). The GRISLI ice sheet model (version 2.0): calibration and validation for multi-millennial changes of the Antarctic ice sheet. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 11(12), 5003-5025. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-11-5003-2018>
- Quiquet, A., Dumas, C., Paillard, D., Ramstein, G., Ritz, C. and Roche, D. M. (2021). Deglacial ice sheet instabilities induced by proglacial lakes. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 48(9), e2020GL092141. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020GL092141>
- Rack, W. and Rott, H. (2004). Pattern of retreat and disintegration of the Larsen B ice shelf, Antarctic Peninsula. *Annals of glaciology*, 39, 505-510. <http://doi.org/10.3189/172756404781814005>
- Richter, O., Gwyther, D. E., King, M. A. and Galton-Fenzi, B. K. (2022). The impact of tides on Antarctic ice shelf melting. *The Cryosphere*, 16(4), 1409-1429. <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-16-1409-2022>
- Ridley, J. (1993). Surface melting on Antarctic Peninsula ice shelves detected by passive microwave sensors. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 20(23), 2639-2642. <https://doi.org/10.1029/93GL02611>
- Rignot, E. J. (1998). Fast recession of a West Antarctic glacier. *Science*, 281(5376), 549-551. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.281.5376.549>
- Rignot, E. (2001). Evidence for rapid retreat and mass loss of Thwaites Glacier, West Antarctica. *Journal of Glaciology*, 47(157), 213-222. <http://doi.org/10.3189/172756501781832340>
- Rignot, E., Vaughan, D. G., Schmelz, M., Dupont, T. and MacAyeal, D. (2002). Acceleration of Pine island and Thwaites glaciers, west Antarctica. *Annals of Glaciology*, 34, 189-194. <http://doi.org/10.3189/172756402781817950>
- Rignot, E., An, L., Chauche, N., Morlighem, M., Jeong, S., Wood, M. and others (2021). Retreat of Humboldt Gletscher, North Greenland, driven by undercutting from a warmer ocean. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 48(6), e2020GL091342. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020GL091342>

- Robel, A. A. and Banwell, A. F. (2019). A speed limit on ice shelf collapse through hydrofracture. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 46(21), 12092-12100. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019GL084397>
- Roberts, J. L., Warner, R. C., Young, D., Wright, A., Van Ommen, T. D. and others (2011). Refined broad-scale sub-glacial morphology of Aurora Subglacial Basin, East Antarctica derived by an ice-dynamics-based interpolation scheme. *The Cryosphere*, 5(3), 551-560. <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-5-551-2011>
- Robertson, R. (1999). Mixing and Heat Transport Mechanisms in the Upper Ocean in the Weddell Sea. *PhD thesis, Oregon State University, USA*. <https://ir.library.oregonstate.edu/downloads/7p88ck00z>
- Robertson, R., Beckmann, A. and Hellmer, H. (2003). M2 tidal dynamics in the Ross Sea. *Antarctic Science*, 15(1), 41-46. <http://doi.org/10.1017/S0954102003001044>
- Robertson, R. (2013). Tidally induced increases in melting of Amundsen Sea ice shelves. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 118(6), 3138-3145. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jgrc.20236>
- Robin, G. D. Q. (1953). Norwegian-British-Swedish Antarctic Expedition, 1949–52. *Polar Record*, 6(45), 608-616.
- Robin, G. D. Q. and Adie R. J. (1964). The Ice Cover. *In: Antarctic Research: A review of British scientific achievement in Antarctica* (Eds Butterworths, London). 100-117.
- Rocha, M., Jourdain, N. and Smith, R. (2023). Modelling Ice sheets in Earth System Models: pushing the boundaries of our scientific and technical capabilities. *ESM2025 Research Highlight*, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7691451>
- Rommelaere V and Ritz C. (1996). A thermomechanical model of ice-shelf flow. *Annals of Glaciology*, 23:13-20. <http://doi.org/10.3189/S0260305500013203>
- Ross, J. C. (1847). *A Voyage or Discovery and Research in the Southern and Antarctic regions during the years 1839-43*. Vol. I, London.
- Rott, H., Skvarca, P. and Nagler, T. (1996). Rapid collapse of northern Larsen ice shelf, Antarctica. *Science*, 271(5250), 788-792. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.271.5250.788>
- Samson, G., Masson, S., Lengaigne, M., Keerthi, M., Vialard, J., Pous, S., Madec, G., Jourdain, N. C. and others (2014). The NOW Regional Coupled Model: Application to the Tropical Indian Ocean Climate and Tropical Cyclones Activity. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 6(3), 700-722. <http://doi.org/10.1002/2014MS000324>
- Scambos, T. A., Hulbe, C., Fahnestock, M. and Bohlander, J. (2000). The link between climate warming and break-up of ice shelves in the Antarctic Peninsula. *Journal of Glaciology*, 46(154), 516-530. <http://doi.org/10.3189/172756500781833043>
- Scambos, T., Hulbe, C. and Fahnestock, M. (2003). Climate-induced ice shelf disintegration in the Antarctic Peninsula. *Antarctic Peninsula climate variability: Historical and paleoenvironmental perspectives*, 79-92. <https://doi.org/10.1029/AR079p0079>
- Schodlok, M. P., Menemenlis, D., Rignot, E. and Studinger, M. (2012). Sensitivity of the ice-shelf/ocean system to the sub-ice-shelf cavity shape measured by NASA IceBridge in Pine Island Glacier, West Antarctica. *Annals of Glaciology*, 53(60), 156-162. <http://doi.org/10.3189/2012AoG60A073>
- Sérazin, G., Di Luca, A., Sen Gupta, A., Rogé, M., Jourdain, N. C., Argüeso, D. and Bull, C. (2021). East Australian cyclones and air-sea feedbacks. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmosphere*, 126(20), e2020JD034391 <http://doi.org/10.1029/2020JD034391>
- Sergienko, O. and Macayeal, D. R. (2005). Surface melting on Larsen ice shelf, Antarctica. *Annals of Glaciology*, 40, 215-218. <http://doi.org/10.3189/172756405781813474>
- Seroussi, H., Nowicki, S., Payne, A. J., Goelzer, H., Lipscomb, W. H., Abe Ouchi, A., Agosta, C., Albrecht, T., Asay-Davis, X., Barthel, A., Calov, R., Cullather, R. and others (2020). ISMIP6 Antarctica: a multi-model ensemble of the Antarctic ice sheet evolution over the 21st century. *The Cryosphere*, 14, 3033–3070. <http://doi.org/10.5194/10.5194/tc-14-3033-2020>
- Seroussi, H., Verjans, V., Nowicki, S., Payne, A. J., Goelzer, H., Lipscomb, W. H., Abe Ouchi, A., Agosta, C., Albrecht, T., Asay-Davis, X., Barthel, A. and others (2023). Insights on the vulnerability of Antarctic glaciers from the ISMIP6 ice sheet model ensemble and associated uncertainty. *The Cryosphere*, 17, 5197–5217. <http://doi.org/10.5194/tc-17-5197-2023>
- Seroussi, H., Pelle, T., Lipscomb, W. H., Abe-Ouchi, A., Albrecht, T., Álvarez-Solas, J., Asay-Davis, X. Barre, J.-B., Berends, C. J., Bernales, J., Blasco, J., Caillet, J., Chandler, D. M., Coulon, V., Cullather, R., Dumas, C. and others (2024). Evolution of the Antarctic Ice Sheet over the next three centuries from an ISMIP6 model ensemble. *Submitted to Earth's Future*.
- Sharov, A., Nikolskiy, D., Troshko, K. and Zaprudnova, Z. (2015). Interferometric control for mapping and quantifying the 2012 breakup of Matusевич Ice Shelf, Severnaya Zemlya. *In Proc. of the Intern. FRINGE2015 International Workshop, ESRIN, Frascati, Italy, Volume: ESA SP731*. <http://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.2444.9121>
- Shchepetkin, A. F. and McWilliams, J. C. (2003). A method for computing horizontal pressure-gradient force in an oceanic model with a nonaligned vertical coordinate. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 108(C3). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2001JC001047>
- Shepherd, A., Wingham, D., Payne, T. and Skvarca, P. (2003). Larsen ice shelf has progressively thinned. *Science*, 302(5646), 856-859. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1089768>

- Shimizu, H. (1964). Glaciological studies in West Antarctica, 1960–1962. *Antarctic Snow and Ice Studies*, Antarct. Res. Ser. 2, 37-64.
- Siahaan, A., Smith, R. S., Holland, P. R., Jenkins, A., Gregory, J. M., Lee, V and others (2022). The Antarctic contribution to 21st-century sea-level rise predicted by the UK Earth System Model with an interactive ice sheet. *The Cryosphere*, 16(10), 4053-4086. <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-16-4053-2022>
- Silvano, A., Holland, P. R., Naughten, K. A., Dragomir, O., Dutrieux, P. and others (2022). Baroclinic Ocean Response to Climate Forcing Regulates Decadal Variability of Ice-Shelf Melting in the Amundsen Sea. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 49(24), e2022GL100646. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022GL100646>
- Skvarca, P., De Angelis, H. and Zakrajsek, A. F. (2004). Climatic conditions, mass balance and dynamics of Larsen B ice shelf, Antarctic Peninsula, prior to collapse. *Annals of Glaciology*, 39, 557-562. <http://doi.org/10.3189/172756404781814573>
- Smith, R. D., Dukowicz, J. K. and Malone, R. C. (1992). Parallel ocean general circulation modeling. *Physica D: Nonlinear Phenomena*, 60(1-4), 38-61. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-2789\(92\)90225-C](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-2789(92)90225-C)
- Smith, J., Andersen, T., Shortt, M. and others (2017). Sub-ice-shelf sediments record history of twentieth-century retreat of Pine Island Glacier. *Nature*, 541, 77–80. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature20136>
- Smith, R. S., Mathiot, P., Siahaan, A., Lee, V., Cornford, S. L., Gregory, J. M. and others (2021). Coupling the UK Earth System Model to dynamic models of the Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 13(10), e2021MS002520. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021MS002520>
- Spence, P., Griffies S., England, M., Hogg, A., Saenko, O. Jourdain, N. C. (2014). Rapid subsurface warming and circulation changes of Antarctic coastal waters by poleward shifting winds. *Geophysical Research Letter*, 41(13), 4601-4610. <http://doi.org/10.1002/2014GL060613>
- Sprigg, R. C. (1986). The Adelaide Geosyncline: a century of controversy. *Earth Sciences History*, 5(1), 66-83. <https://doi.org/10.17704/eshi.5.1.c5rn11w3001t50j1>
- St-Laurent, P., Klinck, J. M. and Dinniman, M. S. (2013). On the role of coastal troughs in the circulation of warm Circumpolar Deep Water on Antarctic shelves. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 43(1), 51-64. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JPO-D-11-0237.1>
- Steig, E. J., Ding, Q., Battisti, D. S. and Jenkins, A. (2012). Tropical forcing of Circumpolar Deep Water inflow and outlet glacier thinning in the Amundsen Sea Embayment, West Antarctica. *Annals of Glaciology*, 53(60), 19-28. <http://doi.org/10.3189/2012AoG60A110>
- Sun, S., Pattyn, F., Simon, E. G., Albrecht, T., Cornford, S., Calov, R. and others (2020). Antarctic ice sheet response to sudden and sustained ice-shelf collapse (ABUMIP). *Journal of Glaciology*, 66(260), 891-904. <http://doi.org/10.1017/jog.2020.67>
- Svensen, J. I., Gataullin, V., Mangerud, J. and Polyak, L. (2004). The glacial history of the Barents and Kara Sea region. In *Developments in Quaternary Sciences* (Vol. 2, pp. 369-378). Elsevier. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1571-0866\(04\)80086-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1571-0866(04)80086-1)
- Swart N. C. and Fyfe J. C. (2013). The influence of recent Antarctic ice sheet retreat on simulated sea ice area trends. *Geophysical Research Letter*, 40(16):4328–32. <https://doi.org/10.1002/grl.50820>
- Swithinbank, C. (1955). Ice shelves. *The Geographical Journal*, 121(1), 64-76. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1791807>
- Taschetto, A. S., Sen Gupta, A., Jourdain, N. C., Santoso, A., Ummenhofer, C. C., England, M. H. (2014). Cold Tongue and warm pool ENSO events in CMIP5: mean state and future projections. *Journal of Climate*, 27(8):2861-2885. <http://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-13-00437.1>
- Timmermann, R., Wang, Q. and Hellmer, H. H. (2012). Ice-shelf basal melting in a global finite-element sea-ice/ice-shelf/ocean model. *Annals of Glaciology*, 53(60), 303-314. <http://doi.org/10.3189/2012AoG60A156>
- Timmermann, R. and Hellmer, H. H. (2013). Southern Ocean warming and increased ice shelf basal melting in the twenty-first and twenty-second centuries based on coupled ice-ocean finite-element modelling. *Ocean Dynamics*, 63, 1011-1026. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10236-013-0642-0>
- Thoma, M., Grosfeld, K. and Lange, M. A. (2006). Impact of the Eastern Weddell Ice Shelves on water masses in the eastern Weddell Sea. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 111(C12). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2005JC003212>
- Thoma, M., Jenkins, A., Holland, D. and Jacobs, S. (2008). Modelling circumpolar deep water intrusions on the Amundsen Sea continental shelf, Antarctica. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 35(18). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2008GL034939>
- Thoma, M., Determann, J., Grosfeld, K., Goeller, S. and Hellmer, H. H. (2015). Future sea-level rise due to projected ocean warming beneath the Filchner Ronne Ice Shelf: A coupled model study. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 431, 217-224. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2015.09.013>
- Thomas, R. H. (1976). Thickening of the Ross Ice Shelf and equilibrium state of the West Antarctic ice sheet. *Nature*, 259(5540), 180-183. <https://doi.org/10.1038/259180a0>
- Thomas, R. H., Sanderson, T. J. and Rose, K. E. (1979). Effect of climatic warming on the West Antarctic ice sheet. *Nature*, 277(5695), 355-358. <https://doi.org/10.1038/277355a0>

- Thompson, A. F., Stewart, A. L., Spence, P. and Heywood, K. J. (2018). The Antarctic Slope Current in a changing climate. *Reviews of Geophysics*, 56(4), 741-770. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018RG000624>
- van Aalderen, V., Charbit, S., Dumas, C. and Quiquet, A. (2024). Relative importance of the mechanisms triggering the Eurasian ice sheet deglaciation in the GRISLI2. 0 ice sheet model. *Climate of the Past*, 20(1), 187-209. <https://doi.org/10.5194/cp-20-187-2024>
- Van Achter, G., Fichet, T., Goosse, H. and Moreno-Chamarro, E. (2022). Influence of fast ice on future ice shelf melting in the Totten Glacier area, East Antarctica. *The Cryosphere*, 16(11), 4745-4761. <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-16-4745-2022>
- van den Broeke, M. R. and van Lipzig, N. P. M. (2003). Factors controlling the near-surface wind field in Antarctica. *Monthly Weather Review*, 131(4), 733-743. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493\(2003\)131%3C0733:FCTNSW%3E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(2003)131%3C0733:FCTNSW%3E2.0.CO;2)
- van den Broeke, M. (2005). Strong surface melting preceded collapse of Antarctic Peninsula ice shelf. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 32(12). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2005GL023247>
- van der Veen, C. J. (1998). Fracture mechanics approach to penetration of surface crevasses on glaciers. *Cold Regions Science and Technology*, 27(1), 31-47. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-232X\(97\)00022-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-232X(97)00022-0)
- van Wessem, J. M., van den Broeke, M. R., Wouters, B. and Lhermitte, S. (2023). Variable temperature thresholds of melt pond formation on Antarctic ice shelves. *Nature Climate Change*, 13(2), 161-166. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-022-01577-1>
- Vaughan, D. G. and Doake, C. S. M. (1996). Recent atmospheric warming and retreat of ice shelves on the Antarctic Peninsula. *Nature*, 379(6563), 328-331. <https://doi.org/10.1038/379328a0>
- Verfaillie, D., Pelletier, C., Goosse, H., Jourdain, N. C., Bull, C. Y. S., Dalaiden, Q., Favier, V., Fichet, T. and Wille, J. (2022). The circum-Antarctic ice-shelves respond to a more positive Southern Annular Mode with regionally varied melting. *Communications Earth & Environment*, 3, 1, <http://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-022-00458-x>
- Vincent, E., Lengaigne, M., Menkes, C. E., Jourdain, N. C., Marchesiello, P., Madec, G. (2011): Interannual Variability of the South Pacific Convergence Zone and Tropical Cyclone Genesis. *Climate Dynamics*, 36(9):1881–1896. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-009-0716-3>
- Vincent, E. M., Lengaigne, M., Vialard, J., Madec, G., Jourdain, N. C., Masson, S. (2012). Assessing the Oceanic Control on the Amplitude of Sea Surface Cooling induced by Tropical Cyclones. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans* 117, C05023 <http://doi.org/10.1029/2011JC007396>
- Vincent, E. M., Lengaigne, M., Madec, G., Vialard, J., Samson, G., Jourdain, N. C., Menkes, C. E., Jullien, S. (2012). Processes setting the characteristics of sea surface cooling induced by tropical cyclones. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 117:C02020. <http://doi.org/10.1029/2011JC007396>
- Wager, A. C. (1972). Flooding of the ice shelf in George VI Sound. *British Antarctic Survey Bulletin*, 28, 71-74. https://nora.nerc.ac.uk/id/eprint/526223/1/bulletin28_07.pdf
- Walker, D. P., Jenkins, A., Assmann, K. M., Shoosmith, D. R. and Brandon, M. A. (2013). Oceanographic observations at the shelf break of the Amundsen Sea, Antarctica. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 118(6), 2906-2918. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jgrc.20212>
- Weertman, J. (1973). Can a water-filled crevasse reach the bottom surface of a glacier? *Symposium on the Hydrology of Glaciers, Cambridge, 7-13 September 1969, 139-45 (Publication No. 95 de l'Association Internationale d'Hydrologie Scientifique)*.
- Weertman, J. (1974). Stability of the junction of an ice sheet and an ice shelf. *Journal of Glaciology*, 13(67), 3-11. <http://doi.org/10.3189/S0022143000023327>
- Weidick, A., Mikkelsen, N., Mayer, C. and Podlech, S. (2004). Jakobshavn Isbræ, West Greenland: the 2002–2003 collapse and nomination for the UNESCO World Heritage List. *GEUS Bulletin*, 4, 85-88. <https://geusbulletin.org/index.php/geusb/article/download/4792/10431>
- Wild, C. T., Alley, K. E., Muto, A., Truffer, M., Scambos, T. A. and Pettit, E. C. (2022). Weakening of the pinning point buttressing Thwaites Glacier, West Antarctica. *The Cryosphere*, 16(2), 397-417. <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-16-397-2022>
- Wille, J. D., Favier, V., Gorodetskaya, I. V., Agosta, C., Kittel, C., Beeman, J. C., Jourdain, N. C., Lenaerts, J. T. M. and Codron, F. (2021). Antarctic atmospheric river climatology and precipitation impacts. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmosphere*, 126 (8), e2020JD033788. <http://doi.org/10.1029/2020JD033788>
- Wille, J. D., Favier, V., Jourdain, N. C., Kittel, C., Turton, J. V., Agosta, C. and others (2022). Intense atmospheric rivers can weaken ice shelf stability at the Antarctic Peninsula. *Communications Earth & Environment*, 3(1), 90. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-022-00422-9>
- Williams, M. J. M., Warner, R. C. and Budd, W. F. (1998). The effects of ocean warming on melting and ocean circulation under the Amery Ice Shelf, East Antarctica. *Annals of Glaciology*, 27, 75-80. <http://doi.org/10.3189/1998AoG27-1-75-80>
- Williams, M. and Dowdeswell, J. A. (2001). Historical fluctuations of the Matusevich ice shelf, Severnaya Zemlya, Russian high Arctic. *Arctic, Antarctic, and Alpine Research*, 33(2), 211-222. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15230430.2001.12003424>

- Williams, G. D., Meijers, A. J. S., Poole, A., Mathiot, P., Tamura, T. and Klocker, A. (2011). Late winter oceanography off the Sabrina and BANZARE coast (117–128 E), East Antarctica. *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography*, 58(9-10), 1194-1210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsr2.2010.10.035>
- Wordie, J. (1950). 'Barrier' versus 'Shelf'. *Journal of Glaciology*, 1(8), 416-420. <http://doi.org/10.3189/S0022143000012739>
- Wright, C. S. and Priestley, R. E. (1922). *Glaciology, in British (Terra Nova Bay) Antarctic Expedition (1910-1913)*, London.
- Young, D. A., Wright, A. P., Roberts, J. L., Warner, R. C., Young, N. W. and others (2011). A dynamic early East Antarctic Ice Sheet suggested by ice-covered fjord landscapes. *Nature*, 474(7349), 72-75. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature10114>
- Zhao, C., Gladstone, R., Galton-Fenzi, B. K., Gwyther, D., & Hattermann, T. (2022). Evaluation of an emergent feature of sub-shelf melt oscillations from an idealized coupled ice sheet–ocean model using FISOC (v1. 1)–ROMSIceShelf (v1. 0)–Elmer/Ice (v9. 0). *Geoscientific Model Development*, 15(13), 5421-5439. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-15-5421-2022>
- Zheng, W., Pritchard, M. E., Willis, M. J., Tepes, P., Gourmelen, N., Benham, T. J. and Dowdeswell, J. A. (2018). Accelerating glacier mass loss on Franz Josef land, Russian Arctic. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 211, 357-375. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2018.04.004>
- Zwally, H. J. and Fiegles, S. (1994). Extent and duration of Antarctic surface melting. *Journal of Glaciology*, 40(136), 463-475. <http://doi.org/10.3189/S0022143000012338>